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2014-2020

Cod și Nume proiect: POIM 2014+ 120008 Managementul adecvat al speciilor invazive din România, în conformitate cu Regulamentul UE 1143/2014 referitor la prevenirea și gestionarea introducerii și răspândirii speciilor alogene invazive

Rezultatul a fost recepționat și
este conform cerințelor C.F.

Avizat,
Nicolae MANTA
Manager proiect

RAPORT TEHNIC PRIVIND METODOLOGIA DE INCLUDERE A SPECIILOR PE LISTA UNIUNII ȘI DOCUMENTAȚIA ELABORATĂ PENTRU PATRU SPECII

Obiectivul specific 2. Identificarea căilor prioritate de introducere și prioritizarea speciilor alogene invazive din România

Activitatea 2.2. Prioritizarea speciilor invazive și potențial invazive din România

Subactivitatea 2.2.5. Elaborarea documentației pentru includerea a doua specii alogene invazive de interes pentru Romania în lista UE și coordonarea activității

Partener 1: Universitatea din București

Beneficiar: Ministerul Mediului, Apelor și Pădurilor

Manager tehnic UB:

Prof. dr. Paulina Anastasiu

MINISTERUL MEDIULUI,
APELOR ȘI PĂDURILOR

UNIVERSITATEA DIN
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— ȘCOALA DE ȘTIINȚĂ —

MANAGEMENTUL
SPECIILOR INVAZIVE
DIN ROMÂNIA

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Titlul proiectului: Managementul adecvat al speciilor invazive din România, în conformitate cu Regulamentul UE 1143/2014 referitor la prevenirea și gestionarea introducerii și răspândirii speciilor alogene invazive

Cod proiect: POIM 2014+ 120008

Obiectivul general al proiectului este de a crea instrumentele științifice și administrative necesare pentru managementul eficient al speciilor invazive din România, în conformitate cu Regulamentul UE 1143/2014 privind prevenirea și gestionarea introducerii și răspândirii speciilor alogene invazive.

Data încheierii contractului: 27 noiembrie 2018

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Echipa de experți:

Paulina Anastasiu – manager tehnic

Ioana-Minodora Sîrbu – asistent manager

Petronela Camen-Comănescu – expert specii invazive

Eugenia Nagodă – expert specii invazive

Mihaela Urziceanu – expert specii invazive

Notă:

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2

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Cuprins

Introducere	4
Metodologie	4
Rezultate obținute	6
<i>Ambrosia tenuifolia</i>	6
<i>Commelina communis</i>	60
<i>Phytolacca americana</i>	149
<i>Verbesina encelioides</i>	256
Bibliografie	334

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Introducere

Raportul de față prezintă rezultatele subactivității 2.2.5. *Elaborarea documentației pentru includerea a doua specii alogene invazive de interes pentru România în lista UE și coordonarea activității*, realizată în cadrul activității 2.2. *Prioritizarea speciilor invazive și potențial invazive din România*, pentru îndeplinirea *Obiectivului specific 2. Identificarea căilor prioritate de introducere și prioritizarea speciilor alogene invazive din România*, din cadrul proiectului POIM 120008 Managementul adecvat al speciilor invazive din România, în conformitate cu Regulamentul UE 1143/2014 referitor la prevenirea și gestionarea introducerii și răspândirii speciilor alogene invazive.

Motivul pentru care subactivitatea este necesară: conform Art 12(1) din Reglementarea 1143/2014 a Uniunii Europene (UE), Statele membre pot cere includerea unor specii alogene în lista Uniunii.

Metodologie

În urma evaluării listelor consolidate privind speciile alogene din România și ținând cont de speciile aflate deja în lista Uniunii, au fost selectate pentru realizarea evaluării de risc patru specii: *Ambrosia tenuifolia*, *Commelina communis*, *Phytolacca americana* și *Verbesina encelioides*.

În selectarea acestor specii au fost luate în considerare următoarele criterii prevăzute de Reglementarea 1143/2014 a Uniunii Europene (UE):

- Să fie specii alogene pe teritoriul României, în baza dovezilor științifice;
- Să fie capabile să creeze populații viabile și să se răspândească în condițiile actuale și în condițiile previzibile de schimbare climatică,
- Să aibă un efect dăunător semnificativ asupra biodiversității, asupra serviciilor ecosistemice aferente și/ sau asupra sănătății umane sau economiei.

Pentru realizarea evaluărilor de risc ale celor patru specii selectate s-au avut în vedere prevederile Articolul 5 din Regulamentul 1143/2014 al Uniunii Europene, respectiv:

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

- (a) o descriere a speciei cu identitatea taxonomică, istoricul, aria naturală și aria potențială de răspândire a acesteia;
- (b) o descriere a modalităților și a dinamicii de reproducere și de răspândire a speciei, inclusiv o evaluare a existenței condițiilor de mediu necesare pentru reproducerea și răspândirea acesteia;
- (c) o descriere a potențialelor căi de introducere și de răspândire a speciei, atât în mod intenționat, cât și neintenționat, inclusiv, dacă este cazul, mărfurile cu care specia este asociată în general;
- (d) o evaluare aprofundată a riscului de introducere, de stabilire și de răspândire a speciei în regiunile biogeografice relevante în condițiile actuale și în condițiile schimbărilor climatice previzibile;
- (e) o descriere a nivelului actual de răspândire a speciei, precizându-se inclusiv dacă specia este deja prezentă în Uniune sau în țările învecinate, precum și o anticipare a potențialei răspândiri viitoare;
- (f) o descriere a efectului dăunător asupra biodiversității și a serviciilor ecosistemice aferente, inclusiv asupra speciilor indigene, a siturilor protejate, a habitatelor pe cale de dispariție, precum și asupra sănătății umane, a siguranței și a economiei, inclusiv o evaluare a efectelor viitoare potențiale, ținând cont de cunoștințele științifice disponibile;
- (g) o evaluare a costurilor potențiale ale pagubelor;
- (h) o descriere a utilizărilor cunoscute pentru specia respectivă și a beneficiilor sociale și economice care decurg din aceste utilizări.

Pecizăm că evaluările de risc au fost realizate în limba engleză pentru a fi transmise adecvat Comisiei Europene în cazul în care România va decide să solicite includerea vreuneia dintre ele în Lista Uniunii. De asemenea, unele evaluări necesită completări, mai ales în ceea ce privește modelarea distribuției sub impactul schimbărilor climatice. La momentul realizării evaluărilor nu a fost posibilă realizarea și a acestor modelări.

Rezultate obținute

Ambrosia tenuifolia

Risk assessment template developed under the project POIM/178/4/1/120008 “Managementul adecvat al speciilor invazive din Romania, în conformitate cu Regulamentul UE 1143/2014 referitor la prevenirea și gestionarea introducerii și răspandirii speciilor alogene invazive”

Name of organism: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* Spreng.

Author(s) of the assessment:

Eugenia Nagodă, Botanical Garden “Dimitrie Brandza”, University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

Risk Assessment Area: The risk assessment area is the territory of the European Union.

Date of completion: 20/06/2023

Date of revision:

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Contents

SECTION A – Organism Information and Screening	8
SECTION B – Detailed assessment	28
1 PROBABILITY OF INTRODUCTION AND ENTRY	28
2 PROBABILITY OF ESTABLISHMENT	34
3 PROBABILITY OF SPREAD	39
4 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT	46
Biodiversity and ecosystem impacts	
Ecosystem Services impacts	
Economic impacts	
Social and human health impacts	
Other impacts	
REFERENCES	53

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

SECTION A – Organism Information and Screening

A1. Identify the organism. Is it clearly a single taxonomic entity and can it be adequately distinguished from other entities of the same rank?

including the following elements:

the taxonomic family, order and class to which the species belongs;

the scientific name and author of the species, as well as a list of the most common synonym names;

names used in commerce (if any)

a list of the most common subspecies, lower taxa, varieties, breeds or hybrids

As a general rule, one risk assessment should be developed for a single species. However, there may be cases where it may be justified to develop one risk assessment covering more than one species (e.g. species belonging to the same genus with comparable or identical features and impact). It shall be clearly stated if the risk assessment covers more than one species, or if it excludes or only includes certain subspecies, lower taxa, hybrids, varieties or breeds (and if so, which subspecies, lower taxa, hybrids, varieties or breeds). Any such choice must be properly justified.

Response: This risk assessment covers one species, Slimleaf bur ragweed, *Ambrosia tenuifolia* Spreng.

Taxonomy

Kingdom	<i>Plantae</i>
Phylum	<i>Tracheophyta</i>
Class	<i>Magnoliopsida</i>
Order	<i>Asterales</i>
Family	<i>Asteraceae</i> Dumort./ <i>Compositae</i> Giseke
Subfamily	<i>Asteroideae</i> (Cass.) Lindl.
Genus	<i>Ambrosia</i> L.
Species	<i>Ambrosia tenuifolia</i> Spreng

Ambrosia tenuifolia Spreng., in in Syst. Veg., ed. 16. 3: 851 (1826), is the valid name of the species with an native range of this species is Bolivia to Brazil and N. Argentina in the genus *Ambrosia* (family *Asteraceae*) (Euro+Med 2006-; IPNI (2023); Plants of the World Online (2023); The Plant List 2013). The genus *Ambrosia* is classified within the subfamily *Asteroideae*, the biggest subfamily of the *Asteraceae*, which comprises 1135 genera and more than 17,200 species (Stevens, 2018). The genus *Ambrosia* includes about 45 species, commonly known as ragweeds, that occur primarily across subtropical and warm temperate regions (León de la Luz and Rebman, 2010). Most species are native to the Americas, and the deserts of southwestern USA and northwestern Mexico have been proposed as the center of origin and diversity for this genus (Payne, 1964; León de la Luz and Rebman, 2010).

Synonyms

After cross-checking the information available at IPNI (2023), Plants of the World Online (2023), GBIF (2023), Euro+Med (2006-) it can be concluded that main synonyms for the species are:

Ambrosia fruticosa DC. in *Prodr.* 5: 525 (1836), *nom. illeg.*

Ambrosia longistylis Nutt. in *Trans. Amer. Philos. Soc., n.s.*, 7: 344 (1840)

Ambrosia maritima Vell. in *Fl. Flumin.* 10: t. 26 (1831), *sensu auct.*

Ambrosia simulans Shinnery in *Field & Lab.* 17: 173 (1949)

Franseria tenuifolia Harv. & A.Gray in *Mem. Amer. Acad. Arts, n.s.*, 4(1): 80 (1849)

Xanthidium tenuifolium Delpino in *Studi Lign. Anemof.*: 62 (1871)

Common names

According to CABI (2023), EPPO (2023), Euro+Med (2006-), Greuter (2006+): common names in the European region are:

English: Bur ragweed, Lacy ambrosia, Narrow-leaf ragweed, Slimleaf bur ragweed, Field ragweed

French: Ambrosie à petites feuilles, Ambrosie à feuilles étroites, Armoise, Absinthe bâtarde, Thym marron

German: Schmalblättrige Ambrosie, Schmalspaltige Ambrosie

Hebrew: Ambrosia tzarat-alim

Italian: Ambrosia a foglie sottili

Swedish: Dillambrosia

Most common subspecies, lower taxa, varieties, breeds or hybrids

Subspecies, lower taxa, breeds or hybrids are not known.

A2. Provide information on the existence of other species that look very similar [that may be detected in the risk assessment area, either in the environment, in confinement or associated with a pathway of introduction]

Include both native and non-native species that could be confused with the species being assessed, including the following elements:

other alien species with similar invasive characteristics, to be avoided as substitute species (in this case preparing a risk assessment for more than one species together may be considered);

other alien species without similar invasive characteristics, potential substitute species;

native species, potential misidentification and mis-targeting

Response: The following description is adapted from Parsons and Cuthbertson (2001) and Montagnani et al. (2017):

Ambrosia tenuifolia is a perennial herb; stem 30 to 60 cm high, terete, striate, hirsute; leaves bipinnatifid, hirsute-canescens with ascending hairs; petioles short; blades ovate or lance-ovate in outline; divisions narrowly linear, acute; staminate heads numerous in terminal racemes; involucre broadly obconic, hispidulous, crenate, 2.5 mm broad; paleae of the receptacle filiform, as long as the corollas; corolla puberulent; pistillate heads in the upper axils, mostly solitary; body 2-2.5 mm long,

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

obovoid, hispidulous; beak more than 1 mm long; tubercles 4 or 5, conic, more or less spreading, 0.5 mm long.

The following description is adapted from IantNET (The NSW Plant Information Network System). Royal Botanic Gardens and Domain Trust, Sydney, (<https://plantnet.rbgsyd.nsw.gov.au>):

Description: Erect perennial herb to 75 cm high with long runner roots. Leaves opposite or alternate, bipinnately divided; lobes linear to oblong, usually 2–8 cm long, 4–5 cm wide, covered with long white hairs giving a grey lacy appearance. Heads light green; female heads 1 or few together, with 1 floret. Bracts united to form a fruit, c. 2 mm long, with a few very short teeth, and with a central beak.

Existence of other non-native species that look very similar

Ambrosia artemisiifolia L. (Asteraceae, common ragweed): Annual herb (therophyte), (10-)20-60(-150) cm tall. Stems erect. Leaves opposite (proximal) and alternate, with blades lanceolate or elliptic [(20-)25-55(-90) × 20-30(-50) mm], 1-2-pinnately lobed, sparsely pubescent abaxially, glandular-dotted on both faces, petioled [petiole 25-35(-60) mm long]. Flowers arranged in capitula, the male capitula (5-20 flowers per capitulum, the involucre being cup-shaped, glabrous to pubescent) forming a terminal spike-like inflorescence, the female capitula proximal to the male ones. Fruit globose to pyriform, 2-3 mm long, more or less pubescent. (CABI: <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/10.1079/cabicompendium.4691>).

Ambrosia psilostachya DC. (Asteraceae, perennial ragweed): *A. psilostachya* is an erect perennial broadleaved weed, spreading by seeds and rhizomes. The stems are unbranched or branched, harshly pubescent with stiff, short, minutely glandular hairs. It grows from 30 to 105 cm tall. Leaves are 5-10 cm long, opposite at the base, alternate above, hairy, pinnately to bi-pinnately lobed, thickish, light green to greyish green, subsessile or occasionally on short-winged petioles. Flower heads contain either male or female flowers and are on different parts of the same plant. Flowers are produced from summer to early autumn (July to October). Staminate (male) flowers numbering 10 to 40 per plant are yellowish-white and stalked to subsessile, arranged in spikes terminating the stems and branchlets. The involucre is hirsutulous with usually tuberculate-based hairs; corolla five-lobed (Bassett and Crompton, 1975). Male flowers produce excessive wind-dispersed pollen. Pistillate (female) heads 1-flowered, sessile, single or clustered in the upper axils. The fruits are obovate achenes, greenish-brown, grey or dark grey, 2.5-3(-6) mm long and 2-3.5 mm broad with a short blunt spine. Seeds are obovate, approximately 2-3 mm long and 1.8-2.5 mm broad, smooth and shiny. (CABI: <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/10.1079/cabicompendium.4692>)

Ambrosia confertiflora DC. (Asteraceae, burr ragweed): is a perennial species up to 80 cm tall, occasionally to 150-200 cm. Stems are erect, with aromatic leaves 40-85(-150) mm long and 20-35(-55) mm wide, opposite at the base, alternating higher up, with petioles 10-35 mm; lanceolate to ovate, 2-4-pinnately lobed, bases cuneate to truncate, ultimate margins entire, abaxial and adaxial faces strigillose to sericeous (often greyish) and gland-dotted. *A. confertiflora* is monoecious, with numerous small male flowers borne on erect clusters, while female flowers lack petals and are concentrated in leaf axils in a cup-shaped involucre. Pistillate heads clustered, proximal to staminate, 1-2 florets, peduncles 0.5-2 mm; involucres cup-shaped, 1.5-3 mm or more in diameter, strigillose. Fruit is a spiny bur, pyramidal to pyriform, 1-2 mm long, strigillose to pilosulous, bearing 10-20 hooked spines, each containing a single seed 3-4 mm in diameter. (CABI: <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/10.1079/cabicompendium.120550>).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Artemisia verlotiorum Lamotte (Asteraceae, chinese wormwood): Description: Herbaceous perennial, dying back to rootstock annually, c. 1 m high; stems erect, ± tomentose becoming glabrous below, ribbed, unbranched below inflorescence. Leaves 2- or 3-pinnatisect, c. 7 cm long, c. 3 cm wide; ultimate segments subulate to lanceolate, upper surface ± glabrous; lower surface tomentose, sparsely glandular; reticulum of small veins conspicuous; upper leaves ± sessile, and usually unlobed. Inflorescence paniculate; outer involucre bracts herbaceous; inner bracts with broad scarious margins and apex; ± hairy; receptacle glabrous. Florets c. 15–25, scattered glandular hairs, yellow to reddish brown. Achenes 1–1.5 mm long, ± smooth; pappus absent or a small scarious ring. (PlantNET (The NSW Plant Information Network System). Royal Botanic Gardens and Domain Trust, Sydney. <https://plantnet.rbgsyd.nsw.gov.au>)

	<i>Ambrosia tenuifolia</i>	<i>Artemisia verlotiorum</i>
Leaf arrangement at the base	opposite leaves	alternate leaves
Upper surface of leaf (Hairiness)	pubescent	glabrous
Upper surface of leaf (colour)	glaucous green	dark green

Ambrosia tenuifolia can be confused with *Ambrosia psilostachya* but it can be differentiated by its stalked leaves, narrower leaf segments and involucre of the spiny capitulum. (<https://portal.wiktrop.org/species/show/24>).

A. psilostachya and *A. tenuifolia* appeared to be very genetically close to *A. artemisiifolia*. Former morphological classification considered *A. artemisiifolia*, *A. psilostachya* and *A. tenuifolia* as related species belonging to one same group. These SSRs can readily be used for studying key aspects of the biology and population dynamics of the two species most closely related to *A. artemisiifolia* (*A. psilostachya* and *A. tenuifolia*) (Meyer et al., 2017).

Possible reason of misidentify: as shown above, the perennial ragweed from Romania has previously been misidentified as *A. coronopifolia* (today a synonym of *A. psilostachya*). This is not a singular case. As Payne (1964) pointed out, "specimens of *A. tenuifolia* are occasionally misidentified as *A. psilostachya* DC., probably because of similarity of fruiting involucre morphology, or as *A. confertiflora* DC., which may have similar leaves" (Karrer et al., 2021).

The three investigated perennial species vary in their leaf morphology *A. confertiflora* is usually a tall plant (0.5–3 m). It has large leaves, 2–4-pinnately lobed, with long winged petioles. *A. confertiflora* leaves show high polymorphism, and can be small and almost unlobed (not shown). *A. tenuifolia* has shorter stature (0.4–1.5 m), has less lobed leaves, and bipinnate and sometimes short petioles. *A. confertiflora* and *A. tenuifolia* are sometimes difficult to differentiate by their leaves, thus specific identification requires observing their fruit morphology as well (problematic when the fruits are not in season or in young plants). In *A. tenuifolia*, we saw two types of non-glandular trichomes: the more abundant type are basillate trichomes they have a round wide base with surface sculpting, and then abruptly become slender, reminding a curved fencing sword. The cells are joined with round joints. In addition, *A. confertiflora* and *A. tenuifolia* both have capitate glandular trichomes. However, *A. tenuifolia* trichomes show a distinct morphology. They have an unusual bifurcate head, which

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

reminded us of rabbit's ears. Those trichomes usually are situated in a small pit in the epidermis (Matzrafi, 2023).

Existence of other native species that look very similar

No information about native species looking very similar are found.

A3. Does a relevant earlier risk assessment exist? Give details of any previous risk assessment, including the final scores and its validity in relation to the risk assessment area.

Response: No.

Ambrosia tenuifolia not was added to the any EPPO Alert List.

Inside of the risk assessment area

Not exist any risk assessment inside of the risk assessment area.

Outside of the risk assessment area

Australia

In Australia, *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is considered Invasive [NSW's Noxious Weeds] in following habitats type: Agricultural land, Coastal vegetation/sand dunes, Disturbed areas (including trails), Pastures, Roadsides, Wastelands. According National Climate Change Impact is considered like a "Invasive Class 3". The area of suitable habitat and the habitat suitability of observations, for this species, are projected to decrease or remain the same under RCP 8.5 2065 compared to current climate suitability. (<http://www.weedfutures.net/species.php?id=1010>).

Lacy ragweed is a highly competitive perennial plant that is difficult to control. Lacy ragweed grows in thick patches and excludes desirable plant species in native environments, agricultural situations and orchards. Its burrs can contaminate wool and are not easily removed during scouring, in orchards the burrs and pollen cause discomfort to pickers. Like other ragweed species, lacy ragweed produces large amounts of air-borne pollen, causing severe hay fever in susceptible people. Lacy ragweed reproduces by seed and by shoots that develop along its creeping underground roots (runners). Infestations can quickly increase in size and density from new shoots that emerge from the extensive root network. Cultivation equipment contaminated with root fragments can cause spread. The seed of lacy ragweed can be spread large distances by attaching to the fur and wool of grazing stock and native animals. Seed may also be spread by flood waters, roadside slashers, attachment to clothing and contaminated mud stuck to vehicles and earth moving equipment. Seeds germinate in autumn. Seedlings develop a mass of creeping roots throughout winter and early spring. Flowering stems first appear in late spring, followed by flowering in mid-summer and continuing into autumn if favorable conditions persist. Plants die back in autumn, with new growth emerging from the root network. Lacy Ragweed grows in sub-humid temperate regions, in lighter soils in open areas, occurring as a weed of roadsides, railway reserves, sand dunes, cultivated fields, degraded pastures and waste areas. Cultivation and mechanical control are not viable control options and could potentially make an infestation worse. Always use property hygiene practices when operating in areas infested with lacy ragweed. High volume foliar (boom and spot spray) application of registered herbicides can be applied at the budding stage of growth and when plants are actively growing. Repeat applications will be required. Regularly monitor control efforts and follow-up as necessary.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

The content provided here is for information purposes only and is taken from the Biosecurity Act 2015 and its subordinate legislation, and the Regional Strategic Weed Management Plans (published by each Local Land Services region in NSW). It describes the state and regional priorities for weeds in New South Wales, Australia. (<https://weeds.dpi.nsw.gov.au/Weeds/LacyRagweed>).

The impact assessment method used in the Victorian Pest Plant Prioritisation Process uses three broad resource categories: social, environmental and agricultural, each with a number of related attributes. For example, social resources include such attributes as how the plant affects human access for recreation, or if it creates a health risk due to toxicity or by producing allergens

(https://vro.agriculture.vic.gov.au/dpi/vro/vrosite.nsf/pages/impact_lacy_ragweed).

Question	Comments	Rating	Confidence
Recreation			
1. Restrict human access?	Grows between 30 to 60 cm high. Forms dense colonies but unlikely to have impact on human access (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001).	L	MH
2. Reduce tourism?	Most species are 'so ordinary in appearance that they are rarely noticed despite their abundance'. All species noted for allergens (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Some recreational uses affected.	MH	MH
3. Injurious to people?	'Most important hay-fever producing plant in North America'. All species are noted for their allergens and are a major contributor to hay fever in US, with some places advertising as 'ragweed free' (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Also associated with asthma and dermatogenic properties. Major component in allergies.	MH	MH
4. Damage to cultural sites?	Not known to cause structural damage. Little or negligible effect on aesthetics.	L	MH
Abiotic			
5. Impact flow?	Terrestrial species (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001).	L	MH
6. Impact water quality?	Terrestrial species (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001).	L	MH
7. Increase soil erosion?	Plants have 'creeping runner-like roots' (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Aerial growth dies off but unlikely that the species would contribute to large-scale soil erosion.	L	MH
8. Reduce biomass?	Occurs principally in open areas or waste lands (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Likely that biomass would slightly increase.	L	MH
9. Change fire regime?	Herbaceous plant (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001) so assume that it would have small or negligible effect on fire risk.	L	MH
Community Habitat			
10. Impact on composition (a) high value EVC	EVC=Plains Grassy Woodland (E), CMA=Glenelg-Hopkins, Bioreg.=Dundas Tablelands, CLIMATE=VH. Weed	L	MH

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	doesn't occur in healthy, well-established ecosystems. Occurs mostly in open, disturbed areas where less than 3 strata are present (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Very little displacement of any indigenous species.		
(b) medium value EVC	EVC=Coastal Alkaline Scrub (D), CMA=West Gippsland, Bioreg=Gippsland Plain, CLIMATE=H. Weed doesn't occur in healthy, well-established ecosystems. Occurs mostly in open, disturbed areas where less than 3 strata are present (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Very little displacement of any indigenous species.	L	MH
(c) low value EVC	EVC=Coastal Tussock Grassland (LC), CMA=West Gippsland, Bioreg.=Gippsland Plain, CLIMATE=H. Weed doesn't occur in healthy, well-established ecosystems. Occurs mostly in open, disturbed areas where less than 3 strata are present (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Very little displacement of any indigenous species.	L	MH
11. Impact on structure?	Weed doesn't occur in healthy, well-established ecosystems. Occurs mostly in open, disturbed areas where less than 3 strata are present (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Usually only affecting one of the strata.	L	MH
12. Effect on threatened flora?	No information available.	ML	L
Fauna			
13. Effect on threatened fauna?	No information available.	MH	L
14. Effect on non-threatened fauna?	Tends to grow in rural sites so assume that there is no reduction in habitat/food/shelter for non threatened fauna species (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001).	L	MH
15. Benefits fauna?	Lacy ragweed not documented to provide benefit to non-threatened fauna species.	H	MH
16. Injurious to fauna?	Not documented to be injurious to fauna species (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001).	L	MH
Pest Animal			
17. Food source to pests?	Not documented to provide a food source to pest species.	L	MH
18. Provides harbor?	Not likely that it provides harbour for pest species.	L	MH
Agriculture			
19. Impact yield?	Occurs in cultivated fields, stubble paddocks and degraded pastures but not documented to impact agricultural yield (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001).	L	MH
20. Impact quality?	Not documented to impact quality of yield (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001).	L	MH
21. Affect land value?	No information on whether or not the weed affects land value. Weed can be controlled by herbicides (Parsons &	L	M

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	Cuthbertson 2001).		
22. Change land use?	Weed can be controlled by herbicide (Parsons & Cuthbertson 2001). Often found on degraded lands. Assume no change in priority of land use.	L	MH
23. Increase harvest costs?	No documented evidence to suggest that harvest costs would increase due to the presence of lacy ragweed.	L	MH
24. Disease host/vector?	None evident.	L	MH

Ambrosia tenuifolia Spreng was estimated with Global Risk Score: 11.52, Rating: Medium in Australia (Randall, 2007).

Mauritius: *A. tenuifolia* develops in humid areas of the island where it forms dense populations on roadsides, in abandoned fields and cultivations. This species grows best in gravelly soils in semi-humid areas where it can be a very troublesome weed in sugar cane fields. It has a restricted distribution and is found in open and bright places because it does not tolerate shade. Due to its effective method of vegetative propagation and germination of fertile seeds, it is a major agricultural problem. It is very harmful in cultures where its rapid propagation competes severely with the culture. The best method of control against *Ambrosia tenuifolia* in the cultivation of sugarcane and noncultivated areas is the use of a herbicide mixture composed of picloram and amine salt of 2,4-D. To improve control and prevent re-infestation, it must re-treat regrowth with the same mixture (<https://portal.wiktrop.org/species/show/24>).

Reunion : *A. tenuifolia* is recorded in the north of the island (St Denis) *A. tenuifolia* is a ruderal species, but until now it has not been recorded in crop fields (<https://portal.wiktrop.org/species/show/24>).

A4. Where is the organism native?

including the following elements:

an indication of the continent or part of a continent, climatic zone and habitat where the species is naturally occurring

if applicable, indicate whether the species could naturally spread into the risk assessment area

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is native to Argentina Northeast, Argentina Northwest, Argentina South, Bolivia, Brazil South, Paraguay, Uruguay (POWO, 2023).

Ambrosia tenuifolia is native to temperate South America including Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, Uruguay and probably Peru. (Acevedo-Rodríguez and Strong, 2012; Montagnani et al., 2017; USDA-ARS, 2018).

Native of Uruguay and Argentina. It is now widespread in South America and became a weed in many temperate, subtropical and tropical regions; widely naturalized in the Mascarene. (<https://portal.wiktrop.org/species/show/24>).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020**A5. What is the global non-native distribution of the organism outside the risk assessment area?**

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is introduced into: Balears, Cape Provinces, France, Germany, Italy, Louisiana, Mauritius, New South Wales, Palestine, Puerto Rico, Réunion, South Australia, Spain, Turkey, Victoria, Yugoslavia (POWO, 2023). It can be found naturalized in Europe, the United States, Puerto Rico, Chile, Southern Africa, Australia, New Zealand, Turkey and Israel (Acevedo-Rodríguez and Strong, 2012; Montagnani et al., 2017; USDA-ARS, 2018). It is now widespread in South America and became a weed in many temperate, subtropical and tropical regions; widely naturalized in the Mascarene (<https://portal.wiktrop.org/species/show/24>).

Ambrosia tenuifolia is recorded as introduced in 9 countries and islands: United States of America, France, Australia, Italy, Turkey, Israel, Madagascar, Comoros and Serbia (GBIF, 2023).

It has also been introduced in other regions of the world, as: North America (Nelsson, 1917); South Africa (Lalla, 2015); West Asia: Israel (Greuter & Raus, 1995; Yair et al., 2019); Australia (Orchard, 2015). Global distribution of *A. tenuifolia* has been mapped by Montagnani et al. (2017) and Rojas-Sandoval (2018). A map of the European distribution of this species is also provided by Greuter (2006). The global distribution data published by Randall (2017) must be taken with some caution, as the cited author accepts the name *Franseria tenuifolia* Harv. & Gray as a synonym for *Ambrosia tenuifolia* Spreng., this synonymy being erroneous, as shown by Thellung (1912) (see also Montserrat, 1954, and Payne, 1964). (Karrer, 2021).

A. tenuifolia is also found, probably introduced, in South Africa, and was noted by first time in Europa, by Planchon (d. Thellung, Flore Adventive of Montpellier, 1912, p. 504), at Cette, probably introduced by ships from South America (1830-1840) and naturalized on the shores of the Thau Lagoon, where Serane later pointed it out; appeared on the shores of channel, near Cette, in 1841 (Girard) and in a nearby vineyard to the path of Cette a Salins (Touchy, 1843 and 1855; Blanc, 1851, and Cosson, 1859); in 1906, E. Mandon added the town of Palavas, while Daveau and Thellung found it abundant, like weeds difficult to exterminate, in the Botanical Garden of Montpellier. L. Verguin cites it as naturalized and abundant in the vicinity of La Seyne and Toulon (Bull. Soc. B. Fr., LVI, 1906, p. 581), and he found her in 1904 at Saint-Elme, near Sablettes. Jahandiez (Additions to the Flore du Var, Deuxieme partie. Adventive plants. Annales from the Soc. d'Hist. Nat. Toulon, 1928, p. 20) points to her at Cap Brun (Toulon), on the promontory of Ste. Marguerite (La Garde), islet of Porquerolles (since 1911), and collects the town of G. Hibon, 1915, on the beach of Cavalaire. It has also been naturalized in Algeria, and is reported as rarely adventitious in Germany (Montserrat, 1954).

Since our specimens were found as a weed among various cultivated plants in Malatya (B6), which is located in Turkey, the East Anatolia region far from the sea, with a long-lasting, harsh winter season, the existence of the species in Malatya is very interesting when considering the known the distribution area of the species. *A. tenuifolia* may have arrived in this region by means of cultivated plants such as cereal (wheat, barley, corn), vegetable (cucumber, tomato, pepper, eggplant) and sugar beet seeds as *A. tenuifolia* usually shows up as a weed among various cultivated plants....Turkey, East Anatolia, B7 Malatya: Yukar Banazl, in apricot (*Armeniaca vulgaris* Lam.) garden, wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) field where the effect of humidity is continuous, field, corn (*Zea mays* L.) field and areas of cultivated vegetables (such as cucumber [*Cucumis sativus* L.], tomato [*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.]), pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.), and uncultivated humid ruderal areas, 800 m, 10 viii 2000, L. Behçet (B 6390). The specimens are deposited at VANF (Behçet, 2004).

A. tenuifolia is naturalised in Turkey (Uludag et al. 2017).

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

For centuries, natural lowland ecosystems in Serbia were modified by human activities. Today they occur in fragments. Former steppes, sands and marshes became agricultural areas, and their remains are under constant anthropogenic influence. Great number of allochthonous species permanently affect natural community composition. Some of them became common and widely spread in this area. In the last ten years, new allochthonous, highly competitive species were recorded, ecological valences enabled them fast adaptation. Most important among them are *Ambrosia tenuifolia* Spreng 1826 (population with 200-300 individuals), *Solanum cornutum* Lam. 1797 (small number of individuals), *Salvia reflexa* Hornem. 1807 (along southern margin of Telečka loess plateau), *Humulus japonicus* Sieb. & Zucc. 1843 (ten individuals) and *Thladiantha dubia* Bunge 1833 (population of 300-400 individuals). These species are in the phase of immigration and for now they inhabit only ruderal habitats (Anačkov et al. 2013).

Three main *Ambrosia* species (Ragweed) grow in Israel; the most abundant invasive *Ambrosia confertiflora* DC, whereas *A. artemisiifolia* L. and *A. tenuifolia* Spreng., are of restricted distribution. Three naturalized perennial species *A. tenuifolia* Spreng; (Lacy ragweed) is found in several locations but its spread is limited; *A. tenuifolia* was first time identified in Israel in 1990 and now is naturalised. *A. tenuifolia* is not an invasive plant in Israel albeit the very high number of sprouts it rapidly produces (Yair et al., 2020).

In Israel, the total area infested with *A. tenuifolia* is about 0.5 ha, whereas *A. confertiflora* is much more dominant: a survey analysing the dispersion of ambrosia in Heffer valley during 2004–05 (ending in January 2006) showed that the plant covered >1000 ha, and had 80–100 stems m² (Yaacoby & Seplyarsky, 2011).

According CABI (<https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/10.1079/cabicompendium.109862>):

Continent/ Country/ Region	Distribution	Last Reported	Origin	First Reported	Invasive	Reference	Notes
Africa							
Mauritius	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
Réunion	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
South Africa	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	Weed
Asia							
Israel	Present		Introduced		Naturalized	<u>Yair et al. (2017)</u>	Weed
Turkey	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
Europe							

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Continent/ Country/ Region	Distribu tion	Last Reporte d	Origin	First Reporte d	Invasive	Reference	Notes
France	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	Weed
Germany	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
Italy	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	Weed
Serbia	Present		Introduced			<u>GRIIS (2017)</u>	Weed
Spain	Present		Introduced		Naturaliz ed	<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
- Balearic Islands	Present		Introduced		Naturaliz ed	<u>Fraga and García (2004)</u>	
North America							
Puerto Rico	Present		Introduced			<u>Acevedo-Rodríguez and Strong (2012)</u>	Weed
United States	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-NRCS (2018)</u>	Louisian a
- Louisiana	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-NRCS (2018)</u>	
Oceania							
Australia	Present		Introduced		Invasive	<u>Parsons and Cuthbertson (2001)</u>	Noxious weed
- New South Wales	Present		Introduced		Invasive	<u>Parsons and Cuthbertson (2001)</u>	Noxious weed
- South Australia	Present		Introduced		Invasive	<u>Parsons and Cuthbertson (2001)</u>	

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Continent/ Country/ Region	Distribu tion	Last Reporte d	Origin	First Reporte d	Invasive	Reference	Notes
New Zealand	Present		Introduced			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
South America							
Argentina	Present		Native			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
Bolivia	Present		Native			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
Brazil	Present		Native			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
Chile	Present		Introduced		Invasive	<u>Ugarte et al. (2011)</u>	
Paraguay	Present		Native			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
Peru	Present		Native			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	
Uruguay	Present		Native			<u>USDA-ARS (2018)</u>	

Continent/ region	Country	General remarks	Source
Africa	Madagascar	Introduced	GRIIS (2017); GBIF (2023);
Africa	Comores	Introduced	GRIIS (2017); GBIF (2023);
Africa	Mauritius	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018); POWO (2023);
Africa	South Africa	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018); POWO (2023); GRIIS (2017);
Africa	Algeria	Introduced/ Naturalized	Monserrat, 1954;
Africa	Reunion	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018); POWO (2023);
Asia	Israel	Introduced/Naturalized	GRIIS (2017); Euro+Med (2006-); GBIF (2023); Yair et al. 2017; Greuter & Raus, 1995; Yair et al., 2019; Yair et al., 2020; Yaacoby & Seplyarsky, 2011;
Asia	Turkey	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018); GRIIS (2017); POWO (2023); Euro+Med (2006-); Behçet, 2004;

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

			GBIF (2023); Uludag et al. 2017;
Asia	Palestina	Introduced	POWO (2023);
Europe	France	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018); POWO (2023);
Europe	Germany	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018); POWO (2023); Monserrat, 1954;
Europe	Italy	Introduced/Naturalized	USDA-ARS(2018); POWO (2023); GRIIS (2023); Euro+Med (2006-); GBIF (2023);
Europe	Serbia	Introduced/Casual	GRIIS (2017); Euro+Med (2006-); GBIF (2023);
Europe	Spain	Introduced/Naturalized	USDA-ARS (2018);POWO (2023); Euro+Med (2006-); Tamaracaz et al. 2005; Verloove, F. (2005);
Europe	France	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018); GRIIS (2017); POWO (2023); Euro+Med (2006-); Tamaracaz et al. 2005; GBIF (2023); Monserrat, 1954;
Europe	Germany	Introduced/Casual	USDA-ARS (2018); POWO (2023); Euro+Med (2006-)
Europe	Italy	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018); POWO (2023);
Europe	Romania	Introduced	GBIF (2023);
Europe	Netherlands	Introduced	Bijmoer R, Scherrenberg M, Creuwels J (2023)[sheet of herbaria]; GBIF (2023);
Europe	Yugoslavia	Introduced/Casual	POWO (2023); Euro+Med (2006-);
North America	Puerto Rico	Introduced	Acedo-Rodriguez and Strong (2012); POWO (2023);
North America	United States	Introduced	USDA-NRCS (2018); GRIIS (2017); POWO (2023); GBIF (2023);
North America	Louisiana (apartine de usa)	Introduced	USDA-NRCS (2018); POWO (2023); GBIF (2023);
Australia	New South Wales	Introduced/Invasive	GRIIS (2017); Parsons and Cuthbertson (2001); POWO (2023); GBIF (2023); Orchard, 2015;
Australia	South Australia	Introduced/Invasive	GRIIS (2017); Parsons and Cuthbertson (2001); POWO (2023); Orchard, 2015;
New Zealand	New Zealand	Introduced	USDA-ARS (2018);
South America	Argentina	Native	USDA-ARS (2018); Acevedo-Rodríguez and Strong, 2012; Montagnani et al., 2017;
South America	Bolivia	Native	USDA-ARS (2018);
South America	Brazil	Native	USDA-ARS (2018); Acevedo-Rodríguez and Strong, 2012; Montagnani et al., 2017;
South America	Chile	Introduced/Invasive	Ugarte et al. (2011); GRIIS (2017);
South America	Paraguay	Native	USDA-ARS (2018); Acevedo-Rodríguez and Strong, 2012; Montagnani et al., 2017;

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

South America	Peru	Native	USDA-ARS (2018); Acevedo-Rodríguez and Strong, 2012; Montagnani et al., 2017;
South America	Uruguay	Native	USDA-ARS (2018); Acevedo-Rodríguez and Strong, 2012; Montagnani et al., 2017;

A6. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area has the species been recorded and where is it established? The information needs to be given separately for recorded (including casual or transient occurrences) and established occurrences. “Established” means the process of an alien species successfully producing viable offspring with the likelihood of continued survival¹.

A6a. Recorded: List regions

A6b. Established: List regions

Freshwater / terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic

Marine regions:

Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea

Marine subregions:

Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel, Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast, Western Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Central Mediterranean Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea.

Comment on the sources of information on which the response is based and discuss any uncertainty in the response.

For delimitation of EU biogeographical regions please refer to <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2> (see also Annex VI).

For delimitation of EU marine regions and subregions consider the Marine Strategy Framework Directive areas; please refer to <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/msfd-regions-and-subregions/technical-document/pdf> (see also Annex VI).

Response: Biogeographical regions with recorded/ established *Ambrosia tenuifolia* occurrences (grey cell – biogeographical region not covered by the risk assessment area)

biogeographical region	recorded	established	source of recorded occurrences	source of established occurrences
Alpine	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	
Anatolian	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)	
Arctic	No	No	GBIF (2023)	

¹ Convention on Biological Diversity, Decision VI/23

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

biogeographical region	recorded	established	source of recorded occurrences	source of established occurrences
Atlantic	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	
Black Sea	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)	
Boreal	No	No	GBIF (2023)	
Continental	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	
Macaronesian	No	No	GBIF (2023)	
Mediterranean	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	
Pannonian	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)	
Steppic	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)	

Country	Alp	Ana	Arc	Atl	Bl.Sea	Bor	Cont	Mac	Med	Pan	Step
France	x			x			x		x		
Germany				x			x				
Italy							x		x		
Romania	x						x				x
Spain	x			x					x		
Serbia							x			x	
Netherlands				x							

Response (6a): *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is recorded in the Alpine, Anatolian, Atlantic, Continental, Pannonian, Mediterranean and Steppic biogeographical regions. No recorded occurrence data is available for the Arctic, Boreal, Black Sea and Macaronesian biogeographical regions.

Response (6b): According to the available information, *A. tenuifolia* can be considered as “established” in the Atlantic, Continental and Mediterranean biogeographical regions.

“Established” means the process of an alien species successfully producing viable offspring with the likelihood of continued survival. In the available references (mainly Euro+Med PlantBase), the term “naturalized” is used. In order to answer question 6b, “naturalized” is used as a synonym for “established”. The assessment of established occurrences in biogeographical regions is mainly deduced from the data available on national level.

A7. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area could the species establish in the future under current climate and under foreseeable climate change?

The information needs to be given separately for current climate and under foreseeable climate change conditions.

A7a. Current climate: List regions

A7b. Future climate: List regions

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

With regard to EU biogeographic and marine (sub)regions, see above.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the risk assessment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response: Not evaluated

A8. In which EU Member States has the species been recorded and in which EU Member States has it established? List them with an indication of the timeline of observations. The information needs be given separately for recorded and established occurrences.

A8a. Recorded: List Member States

A8b. Established: List Member States

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden

The description of the invasion history of the species shall include information on countries invaded and an indication of the timeline of the first observations, establishment and spread.

Response:

country	reco ded	establi sh ed	source recorded	source established	general remarks	timeline of observations
Austria	No	No				
Belgium	No	No				
Bulgaria	No	No				
Croatia	No	No				
Cyprus	No	No				
Czech Republic	No	No				

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

country	reco ded	establi shed	source recorded	source established	general remarks	timeline of observations
Denmark	No	No				
Estonia	No	No				
Finland	No	No				
France	Yes	Yes			Present / localized; naturalized	
Germany	Yes	No				
Greece	No	No				
Hungary	No	No				
Ireland	No	No			Present; naturalized	
Italy	Yes	Yes			Present / localized; naturalized; invasive	
Latvia	No	No				
Lithuania	No	No				
Luxembourg	No	No				
Malta	No	No				
Netherlands	Yes	No				
Poland	No	No				
Portugal	No	No			Present / localized; naturalized; invasive	
Romania	Yes	No				
Slovakia	No	No				
Slovenia	No	No				
Spain	Yes	Yes			Present / localized; naturalized	
Sweden	No	No			Cultivated	

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response (8a): *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is recorded in 6 out of 27 Member States (France, Italy, Spain, Germany, Romania, Netherland).

Response (8b): Based upon the available data, *A. tenuifolia* can be assessed as established in 3 Member States (France, Italy and Spain).

Ambrosia tenuifolia (silver ragweed) is present only in France and Spain (Taramaracaz et al. 2005).

The South American *Ambrosia tenuifolia* has been found as an ephemeral casual in this area in the vicinity of Llinars del Vallès and Sant Celoni (Casasayas, La flora allòctona de Catalunya, Tesi doctoral (ined.), 880 pp., 1989). At present the species appears to be fully naturalized in the riu Besòs valley, often in abundance and always accompanied by *Ambrosia coronopifolia*. Apart from the above mentioned locality, *Ambrosia tenuifolia* also occurs in Sant Fost de Campsentelles (riu Besòs near Can Rovira), in Montmelo (riu el Congost) and doubtlessly elsewhere. Spain, Barcelona: Montmelo, riu Besòs (NE-Barcelona), UTM 31TDF39, ca. 50 m, gravelly riverbed, very common, 09.IX.2003, F. Verloove 5474 (priv. herb. author). (Verloove, 2005).

In this paper, *Ambrosia tenuifolia* (Asteraceae) is reported for the first time in the alien flora of Romania. Data resulting from the revision of herbarium specimens of the perennial ragweed previously collected from the locality of C. A. Rosetti (Danube Delta), as well as the results of our recent field work, revealed that *A. psilostachya* (a native species from North America) has been erroneously reported from Romania, and the correct identity of this plant is actually *A. tenuifolia*, which originates from South America. (Karrer et al., 2021).

Current status in Romania. In the locality of C. A. Rosetti (Danube Delta), the population of *A. tenuifolia* has conquered an area of approx. 100 sq.m, on sandy soil, near the crossroads of DC3 & DC4 (communal roads), just behind a local shop, north of the church (45,295127°N, 29,568970°E; ca. 2 m a.s.l.). Scattered individuals grew near the road and on the nearby ruderalized xerophilous grassland (which was dominated by *Cynodon dactylon*), but the population also expanded into a derelict neighbouring garden, where it was much denser, consisting of hundreds of shoots. From our preliminary data, it seems that the plants propagate locally slowly, only clonally, by root sprouting. Although it produces morphologically normal fruits and seeds, to date there is no evidence that the seeds germinate in that place or in the surroundings. However, we consider that the species is naturalized in the Danube Delta, where it persists and flourishes for over three decades. (Karrer et al., 2021).

Unlike the other *Ambrosia* species reported so far in Romania, which are native to North America (Strother, 2006), *A. tenuifolia* is of South American origin (Baker, 1882; Arechavalle, 1906; Thellung, 1912; Montagnani et al., 2017). In Europe, it was first identified in France, in 1839, on sea sands, possibly introduced with ships ballast (Planchon, 1864; Thellung, 1912), and subsequently it spread to other regions of the continent, being up to now reported from France (Cosson & Kralik, 1849-1850; Godron, 1852; Planchon, 1864; Thellung, 1912), Germany (Thellung, 1912), Spain (Montserrat, 1954), and Italy (Vignolo-Lutati, 1935). According to Montagnani et al. (2017), excepting Germany (casual), in other European countries this neophyte is fully naturalized, however, only locally invasive. This is also the case of the populations from the Danube Delta, Romania (Karrer et al., 2021).

The first observation of *Ambrosia* with small leaves mentioned in France dates from 1839, in Hérault (SIFlore). (GT IBMA. 2018).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

A. tenuifolia is also found, probably introduced, in South Africa, and was noted by first time in Europa, by Planchon (d. Thellung, Flore Adventice of Montpellier, 1912, p. 504), at Cette, probably introduced by ships from South America (1830-1840) and naturalized on the shores of the Thau Lagoon, where Serane later pointed it out; appeared on the shores of channel, near Cette, in 1841 (Girard) and in a nearby vineyard to the path of Cette a Salins (Touchy, 1843 and 1855; Blanc, 1851, and Cosson, 1859); in 1906, E. Mandon added the town of Palavas, while Daveau and Thellung found it abundant, like weeds difficult to exterminate, in the Botanical Garden of Montpellier. L. Verguin cites it as naturalized and abundant in the vicinity of La Seyne and Toulon (Bull. Soc. B. Fr., LVI, 1906, p. 581), and he found her in 1904 at Saint-Elme, near Sablettes. Jahandiez (Additions to the Flore du Var, Deuxieme partie. Adventive plants. Annales from the Soc. d'Hist. Nat. Toulon, 1928, p. 20) points to her at Cap Brun (Toulon), on the promontory of Ste. Marguerite (La Garde), islet of Porquerolles (since 1911), and collects the town of G. Hibon, 1915, on the beach of Cavalaire. It has also been naturalized in Algeria, and is reported as rarely adventitious in Germany (Monserrat, 1954).

Ambrosia tenuifolia Spreng: South American areas. It is naturalised in Southern France and in North east Spain. In Italy, the summer-autumn pollinosis are mainly due to *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* (*Ambrosia elatior*) and to *Ambrosia trifida*, whereas *Ambrosia tenuifolia* and *Ambrosia coronopifolia* have a comparatively limited distribution. In Ferrara, a town located in the Po Valley, *Ambrosia tenuifolia* has been detected all over the territory, on the beach, close to the shoreline, behind the coastal dunes and as a weed in the sandy wastelands; its frequency decreases from north to south, perhaps due to the competition with *Ambrosia coronopifolia* (Mandrioli et al., 1998).

In October 1950 we found this plant in Llinars del Valles (Barcelona), recently introduced and not reported to date in Spain; in this locality it grows abundantly in the gravel of the railway, not far from the railway station. The town of Llinars del Valles is located on the line railway that from Barcelona, by Maanes and Gerona, goes to France; as it has not yet been found in the vicinity of the port of Barcelona, it is presumable that, in Catalonia, the path of introduction is precisely said railway line and comes from France. It would be convenient to study carefully the flora of the intermediate localities, to clarify the problem of the path of introduction, and check if it is more extended by the Iberian Peninsula (Monserrat, 1954).

Was cited for the first time in Spain by Monserrat (1954), who he collected it in Llinars del Vallès (Barcelona), on the gravel roads near the railway. Subsequently he has been pointed out by other authors such as Gallego & Valdés (1984: 270), who found it in Andalusia, specifically in Puerto de Santa María (Cádiz). Masalles et al. (1996: 78) found the plant in the Catalan provinces of Lleida and Tarragona. Verloove (2005: 142) the quote from Montmeló (Barcelona) in the gravel bed of the Besós river. Sanz Elorza et al. (2001: 129) indicate it in the preliminary list of plants with incipient invasive behavior in Spain. The following herbarium references help to establish the area of the species in Spain: BARCELONA: Avinyonet del Penedès, 31TCF9979, 13-IX-1998, A. Sánchez Cuxart, MAF 158330. CÁDIZ: The Puerto de Santa María, 22-VI-1982, J. Devesa & S. Talavera, SEV 79654. CANTABRIA: Santoña, 30TVP6010, 15-IX-1987, S. Patino & J. Valencia, VIT 1541. VIZCAYA: Portugaleta, 30TVN9795, 1-XI-1995, J. Elorza & J. Valencia, VIT 35249. (Morales et al., 2012).

A9. In which EU Member States could the species establish in the future under current climate and under foreseeable climate change? The information needs be given separately for current climate and under foreseeable climate change conditions.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

A9a. Current climate: List Member States

A9b. Future climate: List Member States

With regard to EU Member States, see above.

With regard to climate change, provide information on
the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the risk assessment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response: Not evaluated.

A10. Is the organism known to be invasive (i.e. to threaten or adversely impact upon biodiversity and related ecosystem services) anywhere outside the risk assessment area?

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is invasive in South America (Chile) and Australia (New South Wales and South Australia) (CABI, 2023).

Ambrosia tenuifolia is an invasive herb that grows forming dense thickets that displace native vegetation. It can also invade semi-natural habitats. Additionally, because this species grows as pioneer species in disturbed sites and forest gaps, it has the potential to disrupt and outcompete early successional native plant communities (Parsons and Cuthbertson, 2001; Cunningham et al., 2011; Montagnani et al., 2017).

Related to invasiveness, the following characteristic of the *Ambrosia tenuifolia* must be taken into account: proved invasive outside its native range, abundant in its native range, highly adaptable to different environments, is a habitat generalist, tolerates, or benefits from, cultivation, browsing pressure, mutilation, fire, pioneering in disturbed areas, highly mobile locally, benefits from human association (i.e. it is a human commensal), long lived, fast growing, gregarious, has propagules that can remain viable for more than one year, reproduces asexually (CABI, 2023).

To date, *A. tenuifolia* appears not to be an invasive taxon in its non-native range, consisting of fewer than fifteen countries, but it is naturalized in over half of the range of introduction (64%) (Montagnani et al., 2017).

A11. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area has the species shown signs of invasiveness? Indicate the area endangered by the organism as

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

detailed as possible.

Freshwater / terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic

Marine regions:

Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea

Marine subregions:

Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel, Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast, Western Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Central Mediterranean Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* exhibits a distribution in parts of the Alpin, Atlantic and Mediterranean biogeographical regions.

A12. In which EU Member States has the species shown signs of invasiveness? Indicate the area endangered by the organism as detailed as possible.

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden

Response: There are documented signs of invasiveness in Spain and Italy.

In Ferrara (Italy), a town located in the Po Valley, *Ambrosia tenuifolia* has been detected all over the territory, on the beach, close to the shoreline, behind the coastal dunes and as a weed in the sandy wastelands; its frequency decreases from north to south, perhaps due to the competition with *Ambrosia coronopifolia* (Mandrioli et al., 1998).

Sanz Elorza et al. (2001) indicate it in the preliminary list of plants with incipient invasive behavior in Spain (Morales et al., 2012).

Unlike the other *Ambrosia* species reported so far in Romania, which are native to North America (Strother, 2006), *A. tenuifolia* is of South American origin (Baker, 1882; Arechavalleta, 1906; Thellung, 1912; Montagnani et al., 2017). In Europe, it was first identified in France, in 1839, on sea sands, possibly introduced with ships ballast (Planchon, 1864; Thellung, 1912), and subsequently it spread to other regions of the continent, being up to now reported from France (Cosson & Kralik, 1849-1850; Godron, 1852; Planchon, 1864; Thellung, 1912), Germany (Thellung, 1912), Spain (Montserrat, 1954), and Italy (Vignolo-Lutati, 1935). According to Montagnani et al. (2017), excepting Germany (casual), in other European countries this neophyte is fully naturalized, however, only locally invasive. This is also the case of the populations from the Danube Delta, Romania (Karrer et al., 2021).

Current status in Romania. In the locality of C. A. Rosetti (Danube Delta), the population of *A. tenuifolia* has conquered an area of approx. 100 sq.m, on sandy soil, near the crossroads of DC3 & DC4 (communal roads), just behind a local shop, north of the church (45,295127°N, 29,568970°E; ca. 2 m a.s.l.). Scattered individuals grew near the road and on the nearby ruderalized xerophilous

28

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APELOR ȘI PĂDURILOR

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MANAGEMENTUL
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DIN ROMÂNIA

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

grassland (which was dominated by *Cynodon dactylon*), but the population also expanded into a derelict neighbouring garden, where it was much denser, consisting of hundreds of shoots. From our preliminary data, it seems that the plants propagate locally slowly, only clonally, by root sprouting. Although it produces morphologically normal fruits and seeds, to date there is no evidence that the seeds germinate in that place or in the surroundings. However, we consider that the species is naturalized in the Danube Delta, where it persists and flourishes for over three decades (Karrer et al., 2021).

Ambrosia tenuifolia Sprengel Barcelona: Montmelo, riu Besòs (NE-Barcelona), UTM 31TDF39, ca. 50 m, gravelly riverbed, very common, 09.IX.2003, F. Verloove 5474 (priv. herb. author). The South American *Ambrosia tenuifolia* has been found as an ephemeral casual in this area in the vicinity of Llinars del Vallès and Sant Celoni (Casasayas, La flora al.lòctona de Catalunya, Tesi doctoral (ined.), 880 pp., 1989). At present the species appears to be fully naturalized in the riu Besòs valley, often in abundance and always accompanied by *Ambrosia coronopifolia*. Apart from the above mentioned locality, *Ambrosia tenuifolia* also occurs in Sant Fost de Campsentelles (riu Besòs near Can Rovira), in Montmelo (riu el Congost) and doubtlessly elsewhere. Contrary to many authors (including Casasayas l.c.), *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is a perennial species (Verloove, 2006).

In Ferrara, a town located in the Po Valley, *Ambrosia tenuifolia* has been detected all over the territory, on the beach, close to the shoreline, behind the coastal dunes and as a weed in the sandy wastelands; its frequency decreases from north to south, perhaps due to the competition with *Ambrosia coronopifolia*, which is present along the whole coast-line and in the ruderal areas of the villages. Its frequency increases from north to south (Mandrioli et al., 1998).

A13. Describe any known socio-economic benefits of the organism.

including the following elements:

Description of known uses for the species, including a list and description of known uses in the risk assessment area and third countries, if relevant.

Description of social and economic benefits deriving from those uses, including a description of the environmental, social and economic relevance of each of those uses and an indication of associated beneficiaries, quantitatively and/or qualitatively depending on what information is available.

If the information available is not sufficient to provide a description of those benefits for the entire risk assessment area, qualitative data or different case studies from across the risk assessment area or third countries shall be used, if available.

Response: In the Southern Cone of South America *A. tenuifolia* has been cultivated as a traditional medicinal herb (Montagnani et al., 2017, Mongelli et al., 1996; Del Vitto, 1997; Trillo et al., 2014). It is used in folk medicine and has been attributed pharmaceutical properties. Helps when lowering body temperature, digestive problems and is a stimulant (Grgić, S., 2014).

Plant used in ethnobotany to facilitate delivery of the placenta after childbirth. Roots used as a staple crop and stalks eaten as greens in the summer. Herb mixed with tobacco (<https://swbiodiversity.org>).

Repellent effect of chloroform-ethanolic and hexanic extracts from aerial parts of *Ambrosia tenuifolia*, *Baccharis articulata*, *Urtica urens*, *Clematis montevicensis* and *Euphorbia dentata* were evaluated

against *Tribolium castaneum* larvae and adults. The chloroform-ethanolic extract of *B. articulata* induced larvae repellency when the extracts were mixed in the diet followed by the hexanic extract of *A. tenuifolia*. A moderate repellent effect of *B. articulata* and *Urtica urens* extracts and hexane extract of *A. tenuifolia* on *T. castaneum* adults was observed (Memorian and Burgos, 2012).

Ambrosia tenuifolia has a significant trypanocidal activity against *Trypanosoma cruzi* epimastigotes. Besides, its essential oil showed antiplasmodial activity against chloroquine-sensitive and chloroquineresistant strains of *P. falciparum*. (Sülsen et al., 2008).

A. tenuifolia Sprengel (Asteraceae) is an Argentine medicinal species known as “ajenjo del campo,” “altamisa,” or “artemisia” which is traditionally used for the treatment of intermittent fevers. A bioguided assay fractionation of the CH₂Cl₂ : MeOH (1 : 1) extract of *A. tenuifolia* led to the isolation of two STLs, belonging to the pseudoguaianolide type, identified as psilostachyin and peruvín. Both compounds were active against *T. cruzi* and showed antileishmanial activity against *Leishmania mexicana* promastigotes (Sülsen et al., 2011).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

SECTION B – Detailed assessment

Important instructions:

In the case of lack of information the assessors are requested to use a standardized answer: “No information has been found.” In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

With regard to the scoring of the likelihood of events or the magnitude of impacts see Annexes I and II.

With regard to the confidence levels, see Annex III.

Highlight the selected response score and confidence level in bold but keep the other scores in normal text (so that the selected score is evident in the final document).

1 PROBABILITY OF INTRODUCTION AND ENTRY

Important instructions:

Introduction is the movement of the species into the risk assessment area (it may be either in captive conditions and/or in the environment, depending on the relevant pathways).

Entry is the release/escape/arrival in the environment, i.e. occurrence in the wild

Introduction and entry may coincide for species entering through pathways such as “corridor” or “unaided”, but it also may differ. If different, please consider all relevant pathways, both for the introduction into the risk assessment area and the entry in the environment.

The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD) should be used (see Annex IV). For detailed explanations of the CBD pathway classification scheme consult the IUCN/CEH guidance document² and the provided key to pathways³.

For organisms which are already present (recorded or established) in the risk assessment area, the likelihood of introduction and entry should be scored as “very likely” by default.

Repeated (independent) introductions and entries at separate locations in the risk assessment area should be considered here (see Qu. 1.7).

Qu. 1.1. List relevant pathways through which the organism could be introduced into the risk assessment area and/or enter into the environment. Where possible give details about the specific origins and end points of the pathways as well as a description of any associated commodities.

For each pathway answer questions 1.2 to 1.8 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than

² <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/7e5f0bd4-34e8-4719-a2f7-c0cd7ec6a86e/2020-CBD-pathways-interpretation.pdf>

³ <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/0aeba7f1-c8c2-45a1-9ba3-bcb91a9f039d/TSSR-2016-010%20CBD%20pathways%20key%20full%20only.pdf>

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

one pathway, e.g. 1.2a, 1.3a, etc. and then 1.2b, 1.3b etc. for the next pathway.

In this context a pathway is the route or mechanism of introduction and/or entry of the species.

The description of commodities with which the introduction of the species is generally associated shall include a list and description of commodities with an indication of associated risks (e.g. the volume of trade; the likelihood of a commodity being contaminated or acting as vector).

If there are no active pathways or potential future pathways this should be stated explicitly here, and there is no need to answer the questions 1.2-1.9.

Response:

(1): Horticulture (escape from confinement)...ne e cazul!

(2): Ornamental purpose other than horticulture (escape from confinement)...nu e cazul!

(3): Transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation) (transport – contaminant)

The mechanism of introduction into the invasive range of *A. psilostachya* and *A. tenuifolia* was likely the same as those mentioned previously (Makra et al., 2015). On the other hand, *A. tenuifolia*, was mentioned (Nelson, 1917) as a "ballast-plant", a species involuntary transported in solid sailing ballasts (currently replaced by water ballasts) and then released in new countries during the de-ballasting phase. This pathway was inferred by the author after the finding of *A. tenuifolia* and other non-native species in dumping areas near harbours in Oregon; nevertheless, this route is also plausible if past transoceanic travels to Europe are considered (Thellung, 1912). In any case, at present, the pathways of introduction of *A. psilostachya* and *A. tenuifolia* are of less certain than those of *A. artemisiifolia*, given the few studies available (Montagnani et al., 2017).

According to Randall (2017) a Major Pathway is: Contaminant, Herbal, Ornamental, but we did not find any evidence. Dispersed by: Humans, Animals, Vehicles, Water Weed of: Orchards & Plantations, Pastures, Pome Fruits References: Brazil-W-255, Brazil-W-361, Brazil-W-407, Argentina-W-237, Australia-W-269, Global-W-85, Global-A243, New Zealand-UW-280, Chile-N-241, South America-W-295, South America-W271, Australia-AX-147, Australia-N-198, Argentina-A-236, Australia-N-945, United Kingdom-U-314, Australia-E-327, EuropeNI-482, Spain-N-405, Europe-N-638, Spain-W-807, France-W-764, Palestine-N851, Australia-W-853, Australia-NX-855, Australia-W-869, Paraguay-NI-876, Argentina-A-913, New Zealand-U-919, Brazil-A-923, Uruguay-A-924, Peru-A930, Australia-N-354, France-N-1006, Italy-N-1006, Spain-N-1006, Australia-N1049, Europe-N-819, United States of America-N-101, Australia-Q-1134, Uruguay-A-1199, Chile-N-1229, Italy-N251, Spain-U-1270, La Reunion-W-1321, Australia-A-1331, Chile-N-1348, GlobalW-1349, Argentina-A-1363, Israel-NW1380, Australia-N-1450, Uruguay-A-1518, Argentina-A-87, Australia-A-87, Peru-A87, Uruguay-A-87, Brazil-A-1560, Uruguay-A-1562, Uruguay-A-1567, Australia-X-1693, Europe-UN-1740, Australia-N-1902, Chile-I-1872, New Zealand-Q-1879, Italy-N-1887, AustraliaWD-1934, Australia-N-1959, -I-, New Zealand-U-2048, Paraguay-A-2070, New Zealand-Q-2086, France-N-2091, Australia-W-1977, Chile-W-1977, FranceW-1977, Israel-W-1977, Italy-W-1977, Serbia-W-1977, South Africa-W-1977, Global—1324 (Randall, 2017).

Pathway name (3): Transport – Contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation))

Qu. 1.2c. Is introduction and/or entry along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

Response: Entry via this pathway is unintentional movement of the species via the contamination of habitat material (soil and vegetation).

Ambrosia tenuifolia had the 1-seeded fruits (cypselae=achenes), enclosed in lignified involucre, are not preadapted for being dispersed by a specific vector. Natural dispersion is done by wind, water and animals, starting at the end of summer (Insausti et al., 1995); they can also be accidentally dispersed by man over long distances, as contaminants of ship ballast (Planchon, 1864; Nelson, 1917) or of agricultural goods, machinery, etc. (Montagnani et al., 2017).

Qu. 1.3c. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced and/or enter into the environment through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.
- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction and/or entry based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in subsequent establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. The transport of topsoil, sand or other contaminated habitat material with shoot or root material could facilitate entry into the RA area. However, the pathway is mainly closed within the RA as there are prohibitions of the movement of soil into the EU from many countries.

Observations of *A. tenuifolia* seedling emergence were routinely carried out on an enclosure within a typical Salado river community. Total seedling emergence from October until December was nil in a year without flooding, whereas the next year, after a flood a density of 11 plus or minus 3 seedlings m² was recorded in the same place. The initial growth rate of *A. tenuifolia* seedlings is slow and their competitive ability is presumably reduced (Insausti and Soriano 1982). The responses of *A. tenuifolia* seeds to light and alternating temperature could, then, be important for successful seedling establishment (Insausti et al., 1995).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 1.4c. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

Response: Shoot and root material are likely to survive transport along the pathway, especially as it would be moved with habitat material that is likely to retain moisture. It is unlikely that plant material will reproduce or increase along the pathway.

Qu. 1.5c. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices before and during transport and storage along the pathway?

Response: The species is moderately likely to survive existing management practices along this pathway. However, there is no information available for this pathway.

Qu. 1.6c. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment undetected?

Response: Plants can regenerate from a small piece of ramet as long as a node is included. Shoots and root material can be buried in soil and other material, making them difficult to detect. Therefore, it is likely that the species could be introduced into the risk assessment area undetected.

In our study, the increased recruitment of *A. tenuifolia* seedlings in canopy gaps was initially a result of a permanent soil seed bank with a high availability of propagules, which can remain viable for many years (D'Angela et al., 1988).

Furthermore, we demonstrated that both the gaps generated by small and large disturbances constitute focal points where the recolonization of the grassland by *A. tenuifolia* originates from seedlings. When these seedlings survive, growth rapidly continues outside the original gaps by lateral clonal expansion. After seedlings became established in gaps, nearby patches of dense vegetation are effectively colonized in a relatively short time by ramets produced from root buds. Thus, lateral clonal growth of *A. tenuifolia* leads to the establishment of potentially independent ramets at some distance from the parent ramet. Grassland invasion begins following disturbance that increases resource availability (Davis et al. 2000), but continues by clonal growth inside the dense surrounding vegetation where resource availability is reduced (Insausti & Grimaldi, 2006).

Qu. 1.7c. How isolated or widespread are possible points of introduction and/or entry into the environment in the risk assessment area?

Response: There are no specific data on the points of introduction or entry.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Points of introduction can include road routes which join countries and other international transportation hubs. These are widespread throughout the risk assessment area.

We demonstrated that both the gaps generated by small and large disturbances constitute focal points where the recolonization of the grassland by *A. tenuifolia* originates from seedlings. When these seedlings survive, growth rapidly continues outside the original gaps by lateral clonal expansion (Insausti & Grimoldi, 2006).

Qu. 1.8c. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment based on this pathway?

Response: Root and shoot material may be able to move along this pathway, and the commodity is placed within the environment where the propagules have the opportunity to establish. However, there is no direct evidence that the species has moved along this pathway and therefore it is scored moderately likely with medium confidence.

Qu. 1.9. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment based on all pathways and specify if different in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions.

Provide a thorough assessment of the risk of introduction in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions: providing insight in to the risk of introduction into the risk assessment area.

Response: Not evaluated.

Qu. 1.10. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment based on all pathways in foreseeable climate change conditions?

Thorough assessment of the risk of introduction in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the likelihood of introduction (e.g. change in trade or user preferences)

The thorough assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment of likely introduction within a medium timeframe scenario (e.g. 30-50 years) with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied:

RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6 °C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0 °C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response: Not evaluated.

2 PROBABILITY OF ESTABLISHMENT

Important instructions:

For organisms which are already established in parts of the risk assessment area or have previously been eradicated, the likelihood of establishment should be scored as “very likely” by default.

Discuss the risk also for those parts of the risk assessment area, where the species is not yet established.

Qu. 2.1. How likely is it that the organism will be able to establish in the risk assessment area based on similarity of climatic and abiotic conditions in its distribution elsewhere in the world?

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is already established in the natural environment in the risk assessment area (France, Italy, Spain,). It is likely that further countries where the species could potentially establish are present within the risk assessment area.

Shoot biomass of the annual *A. artemisiifolia* was not affected by temperature, whereas the shoot biomass of *A. confertiflora* and *A. tenuifolia* was significantly reduced by the coldest temperature regime. For *A. confertiflora* and *A. tenuifolia* the temperature effect was more moderate: the ratio was 2-3 in the coldest temperature regime and decreased to 0.5 in the warmest temperature regime (Yair et al., 2020).

Qu. 2.2. How widespread are habitats or species necessary for the survival, development and multiplication of the organism in the risk assessment area? Consider if the organism specifically requires another species to complete its life cycle.

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is a pioneer herb native to temperate South America that has been introduced in Europe, North America, Southern Africa, Oceania and the Middle East. It competes well in highly disturbed sites where it can become dominant or co-dominant. *Ambrosia tenuifolia* can be found growing in grasslands, roadsides, forest gaps, secondary forests and sand dunes. It also grows as weed, primarily in degraded pastures, cultivated fields and ruderal or waste sites associated with frequent and extensive disturbance from human activities (Parsons and Cuthbertson, 2001; Cunningham et al., 2011; USDA-ARS, 2018).

Ambrosia tenuifolia grows best in open and disturbed sites where it often out competes other plant species for light, nutrients and water (CABI, 2023). It prefers warm areas with full sunlight and slightly acidic soils. It does not survive prolonged floods (Insausti et al., 1995; Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Lacy ragweed grows in thick patches and excludes desirable plant species in native environments, agricultural situations and orchards (<https://weeds.dpi.nsw.gov.au>).

It is a heliophilous species from warm (rather subtropical than temperate) climate, being drought tolerant, somewhat salt tolerant, and preferring well-aerated, \pm neutral soils, sometimes affected by floods (Insausti & Grimoldi, 2006; Karrer et al., 2021).

According to CABI (2023) the following types of climate are preferred: Am - Tropical monsoon climate - Tropical monsoon climate ($< 60\text{mm}$ precipitation driest month but $> (100 - [\text{total annual precipitation}(\text{mm})/25])$); As - Tropical savanna climate with dry summer - $< 60\text{mm}$ precipitation driest month (in summer) and $< (100 - [\text{total annual precipitation}(\text{mm})/25])$; Aw - Tropical wet and dry savanna climate - $< 60\text{mm}$ precipitation driest month (in winter) and $< (100 - [\text{total annual precipitation}(\text{mm})/25])$. *Ambrosia tenuifolia* can also tolerate the following climates: Cs - Warm temperate climate with dry summer - Warm average temp. $> 10^{\circ}\text{C}$, Cold average temp. $> 0^{\circ}\text{C}$, dry summers and Cf - Warm temperate climate, wet all year - Warm average temp. $> 10^{\circ}\text{C}$, Cold average temp. $> 0^{\circ}\text{C}$, wet all year. *Ambrosia tenuifolia* can tolerate temperatures between 12-25 degrees and a rainfall range between 350-1500 mm rainfall.

Qu. 2.3. How likely is it that establishment will occur despite competition from existing species in the risk assessment area?

Response: It competes well in highly disturbed sites where it can become dominant or co-dominant (Parsons and Cuthbertson, 2001; Cunningham et al., 2011; USDA-ARS, 2018).

In Flooding Pampa grasslands from Argentina, seeds of *Ambrosia tenuifolia* germinate after perceiving light with high R:FR reaching the soil in vegetation gaps created by plant death during previous waterlogged conditions (Insausti et al., 1995).

Along with alternating temperatures, light and in particular the R:FR ratio also promotes *A. tenuifolia* seed germination and plant growth, which benefits from vegetation gaps (Insausti et al., 1995; Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006).

However, allelopathy is known also on *A. psilostachya* and *A. tenuifolia* (Mongelli et al., 1997).

A. tenuifolia takes advantage of gaps in vegetation covers (caused by floods, grazing, etc.) which make light, nutrients and water more available for seed germination and recruitment (Insausti et al., 1995; Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006). As a result, this species is a good competitor in poorly evolved environments, although it usually persists in the following stage of vegetation succession where it can become co-dominant (see above). After disturbance, gaps constitute focal points where recolonization of the grassland by *A. tenuifolia* originates from seedlings, which initially have a slow growth phase. It then grows rapidly and continues outside the original gaps by lateral clonal expansion, thus allowing the species to occupy new areas. In any case, independent of the starting population's abundance, the species multiplies many times the surface of colonization in the quite short time of about 4 months (Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006).

Ambrosia tenuifolia is a pioneer species, typical of open habitats, which successfully colonizes vegetation gaps; however, taking advantage of clonal propagation (Insausti & Grimoldi, 2006), and allelopathic compounds (Mongelli et al. 1997), it also can persist in more evolved (yet disturbed) environments, where it can become co-dominant (Karrer et al., 2021).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 2.4. How likely is it that establishment will occur despite predators, parasites or pathogens already present in the risk assessment area?

Response: *Epiblema strenuana* was found in low quantities (2–3 galls per stem) in Israel in Western Hadera (1421/2046) on *A. tenuifolia* during summer 2008 (Yaacoby & Seplyarsky, 2011). *Epiblema strenuana*, the Ragweed Borer or Stem-Galling Moth, is the one of the most important natural enemy insects used as a biological control agent against hard-to-kill Asteraceae weeds in Australia. *Epiblema strenuana*, was introduced into Australia from Mexico to control major weeds of the Asteraceae family in 1982, and appeared to be an effective natural biological control agent against the introduced weeds *Ambrosia artemisifolia* L., *Ambrosia confertiflora* DC., *Ambrosia psilostachya* DC. and *Ambrosia tenuifolia* Sprengel, as well as *Parthenium hysterophorus* in Queensland, Australia (Dhileepan, 2001, 2003; Dhileepan & McFadyen, 2001, Anonymous 2004, Dhileepan, 2007, McFadyen, 2008).

Ambrosia tenuifolia is wild weed host for *Phenacoccus solenopsis*. The EFSA Panel on Plant Health performed a pest categorisation of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) for the European Union (EU) territory. This species is not included in EU Commission Implementing Regulation 2019/2072. *P. solenopsis* is native to North America and has spread to all continents except Antarctica. It has recently been reported from Cyprus, Greece and Italy. This mealybug is a polyphagous pest, feeding on about 300 plant species. It usually feeds on aerial plant parts, especially new growth, but also occurs on roots, and is often associated with ants (EFSA, 2021).

Qu. 2.5. How likely is the organism to establish despite existing management practices in the risk assessment area? Explain if existing management practices could facilitate establishment.

Response: The establishment of *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is suited to a number of different habitat types, including disturbed habitats. Management of habitats is likely to increase disturbance of the habitat, which can act to break the shoots of the plant and resprouting of these parts can occur if they have contact with the ground.

Qu. 2.6. How likely is it that biological properties of the organism would allow it to survive eradication campaigns in the risk assessment area?

Response: A viable soil seed bank also allows *A. tenuifolia* to be more resilient to critical phases such as floods. As reported above, the root system of this perennial species does not survive in anaerobic conditions due to prolonged water coverage, while seeds remain viable. According to Insausti and Grimoldi (2006), seeds are released in large quantities and they can remain viable for several years in soil seed banks. Unfortunately, information such as germination percentage and critical depth are not available for this species (Montagnani et al. 2017).

Vegetative reproduction through rhizomes is also relevant for *A. tenuifolia*, even though it produces a large number of seeds (Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006). Indeed, in this species both these strategies are important for its success in different stages of its life, as they react to dramatic environmental events, such as floods that are frequent on the Pampean Plains or human pressures such as agriculture and grazing (Insausti and Soriano, 1987; Insausti et al., 1995; Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006; Soriano, 1982).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 2.7. How likely are the biological characteristics of the organism to facilitate its establishment in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

a list and description of the reproduction mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area

an indication of the propagule pressure of the species (e.g. number of gametes, seeds, eggs or propagules, number of reproductive cycles per year) of each of those reproduction mechanisms in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

If relevant, comment on the likelihood of establishment based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

If relevant, comment on the adaptability of the organism to facilitate its establishment and if low genetic diversity in the founder population would have an influence on establishment.

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* have quite densely short-haired leaves that play a relatively protective role in avoiding desiccation (Montagnani et al. 2017).

The life strategy of *A. tenuifolia* is based not only on rhizome sprouting, but also on seeds as explained below. Although fewer investigations have been carried out on the *A. tenuifolia* rhizome, it is clear that resprouting from belowground buds permits the recolonization of vegetation gaps after disturbance (Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006), thus ensuring the persistence of the species (Semmartin et al., 2010). *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is a highly productive species, 1,330 g m² of total biomass according to Semmartin et al., (2010) and it can advance quite rapidly thanks to rhizomes, with an estimated rate of 1.72- 0.2 m² /month (Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006; Montagnani et al. 2017).

The small pieces of viable material required to produce a viable plant coupled with the ability of the plant to grow in a variety of soil types will promote establishment.

Qu. 2.8. If the organism does not establish, then how likely is it that casual populations will continue to occur?

Consider, for example, a species which cannot reproduce in the risk assessment area, because of unsuitable climatic conditions or host plants, but is present because of recurring introduction, entry and release events. This may also apply for long-living organisms.

Response: In areas, where *A. tenuifolia* is not present, casual populations may occur in proper/adequate habitats. Casual populations may occur in surrounding habitats. Casual populations are likely to occur in areas outside the optimum climatic conditions.

Qu. 2.9. Estimate the overall likelihood of establishment in the risk assessment area under current climatic conditions. In addition, details of the likelihood of establishment in relevant

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

biogeographical regions under current climatic conditions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the risk of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions: providing insight in the risk of establishment in (new areas in) the risk assessment area.

Response: The species is already established in the Alpin, Atlantic, Continental and Mediterranean biogeographical regions. Countries where the species is established include: France, Italy, Spain and Germany. The Alpin, Atlantic, Continental and Mediterranean biogeographical regions have a high proportion of area suitable for the establishment of the species.

Qu. 2.10. Estimate the overall likelihood of establishment in the risk assessment area under foreseeable climate change conditions. In addition, details of the likelihood of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions under foreseeable climate change conditions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the risk of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the likelihood of establishment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The thorough assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment of likely establishment within a medium timeframe scenario (e.g. 30-50 years) with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided.

However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response: Not evaluated.

3 PROBABILITY OF SPREAD

Important instructions:

Spread is defined as the expansion of the geographical distribution of an alien species within the risk assessment area.

Repeated releases at separate locations do not represent continuous spread and should be considered in the probability of introduction and entry section (Qu. 1.7).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.1. How important is the expected spread of this organism within the risk assessment area by natural means? (List and comment on each of the mechanisms for natural spread.)

including the following elements:

a list and description of the natural spread mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

an indication of the rate of spread discussed in relation to the species biology and the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

The description of spread patterns here refers to the CBD pathway category “Unaided (Natural Spread)”. It should include elements of the species life history and behavioural traits able to explain its ability to spread, including: reproduction or growth strategy, dispersal capacity, longevity, dietary requirements, environmental and climatic requirements, specialist or generalist characteristics.

Response: Lacy ragweed reproduces by seed and by shoots that develop along its creeping underground roots (runners). Infestations can quickly increase in size and density from new shoots that emerge from the extensive root network. Cultivation equipment contaminated with root fragments can cause spread. The seed of lacy ragweed can be spread large distances by attaching to the fur and wool of grazing stock and native animals. Seed may also be spread by flood waters, roadside slashers, attachment to clothing and contaminated mud stuck to vehicles and earth moving equipment. Seeds germinate in autumn. Seedlings develop a mass of creeping roots throughout winter and early spring. Flowering stems first appear in late spring, followed by flowering in mid-summer and continuing into autumn if favourable conditions persist. Plants die back in autumn, with new growth emerging from the root network (<https://weeds.dpi.nsw.gov.au/Weeds/LacyRagweed>).

Qu. 3.2a. List and describe relevant pathways of spread other than "unaided". For each pathway answer questions 3.3 to 3.9 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than one pathway, e.g. 3.3a, 3.4a, etc. and then 3.3b, 3.4b etc. for the next pathway.

including the following elements:

a list and description of pathways of spread with an indication of their importance and associated risks (e.g. the likelihood of spread in the risk assessment area, based on these pathways; likelihood of survival, or reproduction, or increase during transport and storage; ability and likelihood of transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host) in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

an indication of the rate of spread for each pathway discussed in relation to the species biology and the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

All relevant pathways of spread (except “Unaided (Natural Spread)”, which is assessed in Qu. 3.1) should be considered. The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity shall be used (see Annex IV).

Response: Pathway name: (2) Transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation) (Transport – Contaminant)

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.3b. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

Response: The spread of *A. tenuifolia* via transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation) is the unintentional spread of the species within the risk assessment area. Both seed material and plant fragments can be spread via this pathway, though seed is unlikely to be viable in the risk assessment area.

Qu. 3.4b. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway
- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. Shoot and root material can be present on/in the soil, in potentially large amounts if such material is taken from an area where the species is present.

Qu. 3.5b. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

Response: There is no quantitative evidence for *A. tenuifolia*, for the survival, reproduction or increase as a contaminant of habitat material. Viable shoot and root material can be small and therefore it could survive during transport along this spread pathway. Habitat material would be suitable for the survival of the species over short periods. Shoot and root material can remain viable within soil material.

Qu. 3.6b. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: Careful methodical management practices coupled with inspection would be needed to ensure that the species did not spread with contaminated soil and vegetation. This is often not feasible with such small shoot or root fragments.

Ambrosia tenuifolia may be spread as a contaminant in crops, soil, bird food, fodder, vehicles, agricultural machinery and commercial exchanges (Montagnani et al., 2017).

Cultivation equipment contaminated with root fragments can cause spread. The seed of lacy ragweed can be spread large distances by attaching to the fur and wool of grazing stock and native animals. Seed may also be spread by flood waters, roadside slashers, attachment to clothing and contaminated mud stuck to vehicles and earth moving equipment. Always use property hygiene practices when operating in areas infested with lacy ragweed (<https://weeds.dpi.nsw.gov.au/Weeds/LacyRagweed>).

Qu. 3.7b. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

Response: Soil and other habitat material can be moved throughout the risk assessment area and can be spread within such material. Shoot and root material may be small and buried in soil and other material, making them difficult to detect. Plants can regenerate from a small piece of stem, stolon or rhizome as long as a node is included which will aid spread along this pathway.

Qu. 3.8b. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

Response: It would be very likely that *A. tenuifolia* can transfer to a suitable habitat if shoot and root material of the species is incorporated in soil. Topsoil and habitat material is often physically transferred and deposited in suitable habitats.

Qu. 3.9b. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (provide quantitative data where possible).

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is a highly productive species, 1,330 g m² of total biomass according to Semmartin et al., (2010) and it can advance quite rapidly thanks to rhizomes, with an estimated rate of 1.72- 0.2 m² /month (Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006).

Pathway name: (3) Machinery / Equipment (Transport – stowaway)

Qu. 3.3c. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: This pathway details the potential spread of the species with contaminated machinery and equipment. There is no quantitative evidence / interceptions to support the movement of the species along this spread pathway.

Qu. 3.4c. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway
- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. However, any mechanisms involving equipment and vehicles could act to break shoot or root material into smaller fragments. This may aid spread as plants can regenerate from a small piece of stem, stolon or rhizome as long as a node is included which will aid spread along this pathway.

Qu. 3.5c. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

Response: Root and shoot material could survive during transport along this spread pathway.

Qu. 3.6c. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

Response: Root and shoot material can also remain hidden within crevices of machinery and equipment.

Ambrosia tenuifolia may be spread as a contaminant in crops, soil, bird food, fodder, vehicles, agricultural machinery and commercial exchanges (Montagnani et al., 2017).

Cultivation equipment contaminated with root fragments can cause spread. Seed may also be spread by flood waters, roadside slashers, attachment to clothing and contaminated mud stuck to vehicles and earth moving equipment. Always use property hygiene practices when operating in areas infested with lacy ragweed (<https://weeds.dpi.nsw.gov.au/Weeds/LacyRagweed>).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.7c. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

Response: Shoot and root fragments are relatively small, are easily broken from the main stem or root and potentially can remain hidden in soil in cracks and crevices in machinery and equipment. Such machinery can be moved within the RA area transporting the seed to new areas.

Qu. 3.8c. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

Response: It would be moderately likely that *A. tenuifolia* can transfer to a suitable habitat if the species is a stowaway on machinery/ equipment.

Qu. 3.9c. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (provide quantitative data where possible).

Response: Used machinery and equipment can be moved within the risk assessment area at a local and long distances scale. Any seed and root/shoot material attached could be spread at a fast rate. Inspections of used machinery and equipment coupled with cleaning will reduce the potential of spread of the species. There is no quantitative data.

Qu. 3.10. Within the risk assessment area, how difficult would it be to contain the organism in relation to these pathways of spread?

Response: As the species can spread as a contaminant of soil and habitat material, machinery and equipment and recreational equipment, biosecurity measures and inspections would need to be adopted where these spread pathways are active, and the species is present. This would involve multiple stakeholders and communication and awareness raising to reduce the spread pathways.

Preventing the spread from already established populations, will be difficult.

Qu. 3.11. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread in relevant biogeographical regions under current conditions for this organism in the risk assessment area (indicate any key issues and provide quantitative data where possible).

Thorough assessment of the risk of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions, providing insight in the risk of spread into (new areas in) the risk assessment area.

Response: In the risk assessment area, *A. tenuifolia* reproduces and spreads by vegetative reproduction. Therefore, spread by natural means can be assessed as moderately.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Human mediated spread includes intentional movement of the species through contamination of habitat material and used machinery and equipment. For human mediated spread, the rate of spread can be estimated as moderately. Spread would be highest in biogeographical regions where the species is already present, such as Alpine, Atlantic and Mediterranean biogeographical regions. A higher rate of spread may be seen in biogeographical regions where *A. tenuifolia* can be considered as established.

Qu. 3.12. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions (provide quantitative data where possible).

Thorough assessment of the risk of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk, specifically if rates of spread are likely slowed down or accelerated.

Response: Not evaluated.

4 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT

Important instructions:

Questions 4.1-4.5 relate to biodiversity and ecosystem impacts, 4.6-4.8 to impacts on ecosystem services, 4.9-4.13 to economic impact, 4.14-4.15 to social and human health impact, and 4.16-4.18 to other impacts. These impacts can be interlinked, for example, a disease may cause impacts on biodiversity and/or ecosystem functioning that leads to impacts on ecosystem services and finally economic impacts. In such cases the assessor should try to note the different impacts where most appropriate, cross-referencing between questions when needed.

Each set of questions starts with the impact elsewhere in the world, then considers impacts in the risk assessment area (=EU excluding outermost regions) separating known impacts to date (i.e. past and current impacts) from potential future impacts (including foreseeable climate change).

Only negative impacts are considered in this section (socio-economic benefits are considered in Qu. A.7)

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidence this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

Biodiversity and ecosystem impacts

Qu. 4.1. How important is the impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation caused by the organism in its non-native range excluding the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

Biodiversity means the variability among living organisms from all sources, including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems

impacted chemical, physical or structural characteristics and functioning of ecosystems

Response: *A. tenuifolia* is considered a harmful weed, mainly because it has a high production of allergenic pollen, that causes hay fever. It is also supposed (Montagnani et al., 2017; Rojas-Sandoval, 2018) to potentially disrupt and outcompete native plant communities, especially during early successional stages (Karrer et al., 2021).

Both the episodes of abrupt disappearance of a dense cover of *A. tenuifolia* and the subsequent reoccupation on the same sites play important roles in the vegetation changes recorded in this area (Insausti & Soriano 1987; Insausti et al. 1999).

Qu. 4.2. How important is the current known impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation (e.g. decline in native species, changes in native species communities, hybridisation) in the risk assessment area (include any past impact in your response)?

Discuss impacts that are currently occurring or are likely occurring or have occurred in the past in the risk assessment area. Where there is no direct evidence of impact in the risk assessment area (for example no studies have been conducted), evidence from outside of the risk assessment area can be used to infer impacts within the risk assessment area.

Response: In any case, independent of the starting population's abundance, the species multiplies many times the surface of colonization in the quite short time of about 4 months (Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006).

It produces a great number of seeds, with long viability (Insausti & Grimoldi, 2006); however, outside the native area (in Israel), according to Yair et al. (2020), the number of viable seeds under field conditions was very low (Karrer et al., 2021).

After the recession of the flood the density of *A. tenuifolia* seedlings was higher in flooded than in non-flooded plots and it was larger in wider gaps. Canopy removal in non-flooded plots increased field seedling emergence of *A. tenuifolia* up to the levels found in flooded. These disturbances have a significant impact on the vegetational pattern (Sala et al. 1986; Insausti and Soriano 1987; Chaneton et al. 1988). Both the occurrence of episodes of abrupt disappearance of a dense cover of *A. tenuifolia* and the subsequent reoccupation of the same sites play important roles in the vegetational changes recorded in this area (Insausti and Soriano 1987). As a consequence of these fluctuations, the biomass of this species may either represent 30% of the total biomass of the community (a proportion larger than the sum of the rest of the dicotyledons) or it may be nil (Fonseca et al. 1976). These strong fluctuations appear to be closely associated to flood episode (Insausti et al. 1995).

Grassland recolonization outside the gaps continued rapidly by clonal growth, from small gaps and large ones, even within the dense surrounding canopy. This provoked an intense competition with the other species. Gap opening by disturbances, seed germination in gaps and clonal growth were decisive for the recolonization of *A. tenuifolia* populations. This sequence of events triggered the recolonization of the plant community by this species, in sites where it had been eliminated by prolonged flooding. This process represents one of the most significant fluctuations in the vegetation dynamics of the Flooding Pampa Grasslands (Insausti and Grimoldi, 2006).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 4.3. How important is the potential future impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation likely to be in the risk assessment area?

See comment above. The potential future impact shall be assessed only for the risk assessment area. A potential increase in the distribution range due to climate change does not *per se* justify a higher impact score.

Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.4. How important is decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the organism currently in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

native species impacted, including red list species, endemic species and species listed in the Birds and Habitats directives

protected sites impacted, in particular Natura 2000

habitats impacted, in particular habitats listed in the Habitats Directive, or red list habitats

the ecological status of water bodies according to the Water Framework Directive and environmental status of the marine environment according to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive

Response: *A. tenuifolia* is certainly found in areas with high conservation value in Romania.

This species has been first found in Romania, in the village of C. A. Rosetti, from the Danube Delta, three decades ago, but up to now it has been known erroneously as *A. psilostachya* (*A. coronopifolia*) (Karrer et al., 2021).

The locality C. A. Rosetti is located on the territory of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve, which was recognized by its inclusion in the international network of biosphere reserves (1990), within the "MAN AND THE BIOSPHERE" (MAB) Program launched by UNESCO. The Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve was recognized in September 1991 as a Wetland of international importance, especially as a habitat for waterfowl - RAMSAR Convention. The universal natural heritage value of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve was recognized by its inclusion in the World Cultural and Natural Heritage List in December 1991 (<https://ddbtra.ro>).

Qu. 4.5. How important is decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.3. and 4.4.

Response: No information has been found on the issue

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Ecosystem Services impacts

Qu. 4.6. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services in its non-native range excluding the risk assessment area?

For a list of services use the CICES classification V5.1 provided in Annex V.

Impacts on ecosystem services build on the observed impacts on biodiversity (habitat, species, genetic, functional) but focus exclusively on reflecting these changes in relation to their links with socio-economic well-being.

Quantitative data should be provided whenever available and references duly reported.

Response: No information has been found on the issue

Qu. 4.7. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services currently in the different biogeographic regions or marine sub-regions where the species has established in the risk assessment area (include any past impact in your response)?

See guidance to Qu. 4.6.

Response: The presence of *A. tenuifolia* in vulnerable and/or protected sites and areas of eco-tourism interest across the risk assessment area (especially from Romania), coupled with its known behaviour allows us to conclude that it is likely to be having an effect on multiple ecosystem services but with no direct evidence of ecosystem service impacts in the risk assessment area.

Qu. 4.8. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services likely to be in the different biogeographic regions or marine sub-regions where the species can establish in the risk assessment area in the future?

See guidance to Qu. 4.6.

Response: No information has been found on the issue

Economic impacts

Qu. 4.9. How great is the overall economic cost caused by the organism within its current area of distribution (excluding the risk assessment area), including both costs of / loss due to damage and the cost of current management.

Where economic costs of / loss due to the organism have been quantified for a species anywhere in the world these should be reported here. The assessment of the potential costs of / loss due to damage shall describe those costs quantitatively and/or qualitatively depending on what information is available. Cost of / loss due to damage within different economic sectors can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage. As far as possible, it would be useful to separate costs of / loss due to

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

the organism from costs of current management.

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* may be spread as a contaminant in crops, soil, bird food, fodder, vehicles, agricultural machinery and commercial exchanges ([Montagnani et al., 2017](#)).

Qu. 4.10. How great is the economic cost of / loss due to damage (excluding costs of management) of the organism currently in the risk assessment area (include any past costs in your response)?

Where economic costs of / loss due to the organism have been quantified for a species anywhere in the EU these should be reported here. Assessment of the potential costs of damage on human health, safety, and the economy, including the cost of non-action. A full economic assessment at EU scale might not be possible, but qualitative data or different case studies from across the EU (or third countries if relevant) may provide useful information to inform decision making. In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable). Cost of / loss due to damage within different economic sectors can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.11. How great is the economic cost of / loss due to damage (excluding costs of management) of the organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.10.

Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.12. How great are the economic costs / losses associated with managing this organism currently in the risk assessment area (include any past costs in your response)?

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.13. How great are the economic costs / losses associated with managing this organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.12.

Response: In the absence of evidence for current annual costs associated with the management of the species it is difficult to estimate future costs.

Social and human health impacts

Qu. 4.14. How important is social, human health or other impact (not directly included in any earlier categories) caused by the organism for the risk assessment area and for third countries, if relevant (e.g. with similar eco-climatic conditions).

The description of the known impact and the assessment of potential future impact on human health, safety and the economy, shall, if relevant, include information on

illnesses, allergies or other affections to humans that may derive directly or indirectly from a species;

damages provoked directly or indirectly by a species with consequences for the safety of people, property or infrastructure;

direct or indirect disruption of, or other consequences for, an economic or social activity due to the presence of a species.

Social and human health impacts can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

Response: Since becoming aware of the widespread nature of *Ambrosia tenuifolia* in the Newcastle area three years ago, ten patients have been recognized as suffering from allergic contact dermatitis to ragweed (Watt, 1987).

If the animals that give it eat it milk, as a result, an unpleasant smell and taste of milk occurs (Grgić, 2014).

A. tenuifolia is reported to be severely allergenic in its native range and produces a huge amount of pollen (Giscafre and Ragonese, 1942; Vaz Ferreira, 1946; Tejera and Beri, 2005; Del Vitto et al., 2015; pollenlibrary.com). The allergenicity of *A. tenuifolia* is still poorly known (no allergens are reported in allergen databases), but it shows little cross-reactivity with the other *Ambrosia* species (Girodet, 2013).

Qu. 4.15. How important is social, human health or other impact (not directly included in any earlier categories) caused by the organism in the future for the risk assessment area.

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

Response: It is not anticipated that any significant change in the importance is caused in the future.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Other impacts

Qu. 4.16. How important is the organism in facilitating other damaging organisms (e.g. diseases) as food source, a host, a symbiont or a vector etc.?

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is wild weed host for *Phenacoccus solenopsis*. The EFSA Panel on Plant Health performed a pest categorisation of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) for the European Union (EU) territory. This species is not included in EU Commission Implementing Regulation 2019/2072. *P. solenopsis* is native to North America and has spread to all continents except Antarctica. It has recently been reported from Cyprus, Greece and Italy. This mealybug is a polyphagous pest, feeding on about 300 plant species. It usually feeds on aerial plant parts, especially new growth, but also occurs on roots, and is often associated with ants (EFSA, 2021).

Qu. 4.17. How important might other impacts not already covered by previous questions be resulting from introduction of the organism?

Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.18. How important are the expected impacts of the organism despite any natural control by other organisms, such as predators, parasites or pathogens that may already be present in the risk assessment area?

Response: *Ambrosia tenuifolia* is wild weed host for *Phenacoccus solenopsis*. The EFSA Panel on Plant Health performed a pest categorisation of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) for the European Union (EU) territory. This species is not included in EU Commission Implementing Regulation 2019/2072. *P. solenopsis* is native to North America and has spread to all continents except Antarctica. It has recently been reported from Cyprus, Greece and Italy. This mealybug is a polyphagous pest, feeding on about 300 plant species. It usually feeds on aerial plant parts, especially new growth, but also occurs on roots, and is often associated with ants (EFSA, 2021).

Qu. 4.19. Estimate the overall impact in the risk assessment area under current climate conditions. In addition, details of overall impact in relevant biogeographical regions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the overall impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, with impacts on economy as well as social and human health as aggravating factors, in current conditions.

Response: Not evaluated.

Qu. 4.20. Estimate the overall impact in the risk assessment area in foreseeable climate change conditions. In addition, details of overall impact in relevant biogeographical regions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the overall impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, with impacts on

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2014-2020

economy as well as social and human health as aggravating factors, under future conditions.

See also guidance to Qu. 4.3.

Response: Not evaluated.

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UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

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MANAGEMENTUL
SPECIILOR INVAZIVE
DIN ROMÂNIA

Commelina communis

Risk assessment template developed under the project POIM/178/4/1/120008 “Managementul adecvat al speciilor invazive din Romania, în conformitate cu Regulamentul UE 1143/2014 referitor la prevenirea și gestionarea introducerii și răspandirii speciilor alogene invazive”

Name of organism: *Commelina communis* L.

Author(s) of the assessment: Petronela Camen-Comănescu

Risk Assessment Area: The risk assessment area is the territory of the European Union 27, excluding the EU-outermost regions.

Date of completion: 20.06.2023

Contents

SECTION A – Organism Information and Screening	62
SECTION B – Detailed assessment	79
1 PROBABILITY OF INTRODUCTION AND ENTRY	79
2 PROBABILITY OF ESTABLISHMENT	95
3 PROBABILITY OF SPREAD	103
4 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT	117
RISK SUMMARIES	126
REFERENCES	127
Distribution Summary	136
ANNEX I Scoring of Likelihoods of Events	138
ANNEX II Scoring of Magnitude of Impacts	139
ANNEX III Scoring of Confidence Levels	140
ANNEX IV CBD pathway categorisation scheme	141
ANNEX V Ecosystem services classification (CICES V5.1, simplified) and examples	143
ANNEX VI EU Biogeographic Regions and MSFD Subregions	147
ANNEX VII Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/968 of 30 April 2018	148
ANNEX VIII Species Distribution Model	Eroare! Marcaj în document nedefinit.

SECTION A – Organism Information and Screening

A1. Identify the organism. Is it clearly a single taxonomic entity and can it be adequately distinguished from other entities of the same rank?

including the following elements:

the taxonomic family, order and class to which the species belongs;

the scientific name and author of the species, as well as a list of the most common synonym names;

names used in commerce (if any)

a list of the most common subspecies, lower taxa, varieties, breeds or hybrids

As a general rule, one risk assessment should be developed for a single species. However, there may be cases where it may be justified to develop one risk assessment covering more than one species (e.g. species belonging to the same genus with comparable or identical features and impact). It shall be clearly stated if the risk assessment covers more than one species, or if it excludes or only includes certain subspecies, lower taxa, hybrids, varieties or breeds (and if so, which subspecies, lower taxa, hybrids, varieties or breeds). Any such choice must be properly justified.

Response: The risk assessment covers one species, *Commelina communis* L. (CoL 2022a, Euro+Med 2006+).

Taxonomy (Euro+Med 2006+)

Kingdom	<i>Plantae</i>
Phylum	<i>Tracheophyta</i>
Class	<i>Magnoliopsida</i>
Order	<i>Commelinales</i>
Family	<i>Commelinaceae</i>
Genus	<i>Commelina</i> L.
Species	<i>Commelina communis</i> L.

Commelina L. is the largest genus of Commelinaceae, comprising 201 herbaceous species (CoL 2022b; PoWo 2023), distributed worldwide, mainly in tropical and subtropical regions (Faden 1998, 2000; Burns et al. 2011)

Commelina spp. are easily differentiated from the others genera by its inflorescences which are subtended by spathaceous basal bracts and reduced to (1–)2 fasciculate cincinni, zygomorphic flowers, petals clawed, unequal and mostly blue (but sometimes white or lilac, rarely yellow, apricot or orange), three posterior staminodes with 6-lobed cruciform antherodes, three anterior stamens, and 2-locular or unequally 3-locular and 2-valved capsules (Faden 1998, Pellegrini & Forzza 2017). Members of the genus are known by many common names, including dayflower.

Commelina is named for Dutch botanists Jan Commelijjn (Johannus Commelinus, 1629–1692), founder of the hortus botanicus in Amsterdam, and his nephew Caspar Commelijjn (1667–1734), who

62

followed in his uncle's footsteps. Linnaeus named the genus for the two botanists in the family because of the two well-developed petals of some species of *Commelina*, leaving its reduced petal to refer to Jan's brother Casparus Commelinus senior, who was a successful bookseller and newspaper publisher but did not botanise (Christenhusz et al. 2017).

Commelina communis L. is the accepted name of the species (Euro+Med 2006-; PoWo 2023; IPNI 2023). The species was described in 1753 by Linne in the first edition of his *Species Plantarum* with type locality: "America" (Pennell 1937). By 1807 the species has been already in European botanical gardens (Pennell 1938).

Synonyms

According to PoWo (2023) and WFO (2023), *Commelina communis* L. includes two accepted varieties: *Commelina communis* var. *communis* and *Commelina communis* var. *ludens* (Miq.) C.B. Clarke (first published in A.L.P.de Candolle & A.C.P.de Candolle, Monogr. Phan. 3: 171 (1881)).

For *Commelina communis* var. *communis* are listed 30 synonyms, including one subspecies, 5 varieties and 16 forms:

- Commelina barbata* Bojer, in Hortus Maurit.: 359 (1837)
- Commelina communis* f. *alba* Ti Chen, in Bull. Bot. Res., Harbin 14(1): 80 (1994)
- Commelina communis* f. *albiflora* Makino, in Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 24: 33 (1910)
- Commelina communis* f. *albomaculata* Sugim., in Keys Herb. Pl. Jap. Monoc.: 565 (1973)
- Commelina communis* f. *albomarginata* Tuyama, in Misc. Rep. Res. Inst. Nat. Resources 11: 6 (1948)
- Commelina communis* f. *alboradiata* Tuyama, in Misc. Rep. Res. Inst. Nat. Resources 11: 6 (1948)
- Commelina communis* var. *angustifolia* Nakai, in Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 23: 191 (1909)
- Commelina communis* f. *aureostriata* Tuyama, in Misc. Rep. Res. Inst. Nat. Resources 11: 6 (1948)
- Commelina communis* f. *caeruleopurpurascens* Makino in J. Jap. Bot. 7: 4 (1931)
- Commelina communis* f. *candida* Hiyama in J. Jap. Bot. 28: 95 (1953)
- Commelina communis* var. *ciliata* Masam. in J. Geobot. 8: 71 (1960), nom. illeg.
- Commelina communis* f. *ciliata* Pennell in Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philadelphia 90: 38 (1939)
- Commelina communis* f. *ciliata* (Masam.) Murata in Acta Phytotax. Geobot. 44: 80 (1993), nom. illeg.
- Commelina communis* f. *diabolica* (Koidz.) Sugim. in Keys Herb. Pl. Jap. Monoc.: 565 (1973)
- Commelina communis* subsp. *exserta* Pennell in Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philadelphia 90: 36 (1938)
- Commelina communis* var. *exserta* (Pennell) F.G. Bernard in Naturaliste Canad. 95: 599 (1968)
- Commelina communis* var. *hebespatha* H. Hara in Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 52: 401 (1938)
- Commelina communis* f. *hebespatha* (H. Hara) Sugim. Shizuoka-ken Shokubutsu-shi: 490 (1967)
- Commelina communis* var. *hortensis* Makino in Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 15: 64 (1901)
- Commelina communis* f. *leucantha* Nakai in Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 49: 421 (1935)
- Commelina communis* f. *minor* (Y.N. Lee & Y.C. Oh) M. Kim in Korean Endemic Pl.: 565 (2017)
- Commelina communis* f. *miranda* Hiyama in J. Jap. Bot. 28: 95 (1953)
- Commelina coreana* H. Lév. in Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 8: 284 (1910)
- Commelina diabolica* Koidz. in Acta Phytotax. Geobot. 8: 189 (1939)
- Commelina minor* Y.N. Lee & Y.C. Oh in Korean J. Bot. 24: 28 (1981)
- Commelina nipponica* Koidz. in Acta Phytotax. Geobot. 8: 188 (1939)
- Commelina polygama* Roth in Bot. Mag. (Römer & Usteri) 4(10): 14 (1790)
- Commelina vulgaris* Redouté in Liliac. 4: t. 206 (1808), not validly publ.
- Commelina willdenowii* Kunth in Enum. Pl. 4: 37 (1843)

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Disecocarpus polygamus (Roth) Hassk. in Commelin. Ind.: 9 (1870)

For *Commelina communis* var. *ludens* (Miq.) C.B. Clarke, two taxa are listed as synonyms:

Commelina ludens Miq.

Commelina debilis Ledeb.

Common names

According to EPPO (2023), common names in the European region are:

Czech: křížatka obecná

Croatian: komelina

Danish: Fattigjøde

Dutch: Gewone commelina

English: day-flower Asian dayflower, Asiatic dayflower, mouse flower, common dayflower, Mouse Ears

Estonian: harilik kommeliiin

Finnish: rikkasoljo

French: Comméline commune, commeline vulgaire, misère asiatique

German: gemeine Commeline, Kommeline

Hungarian: Azúrkék kommelina

Italian: Erba miseria asiatica

Netherlands: kruipende Tradescanti

Norwegian: dagblom

Polish: Komelina pospolita

Portuguese: tradescância

Russian: Коммелина обыкновенная

Slovak: križatka obyčajná, podenka obyčajná

Slovene: navadna comelina

Spanish: Hierba asiática del pollo

Swedish: liten himmelsblomma

Turkish: Mahmuza

Ukrainian: комеліна звичайна

Most common subspecies, lower taxa, varieties, breeds or hybrids

Two varieties are recognized (PoWo 2022, Euro+Med (2006-), WFO): *Commelina communis* var. *communis* and *Commelina communis* var. *ludens* (Miq.). *Commelina communis* var. *hortensis* Makino is recognized just by WFO (2023).

Commelina communis var. *ludens* (Miquel) C. B. Clarke was created by C.B. Clarke after demoting it from the full species status in which it was placed by Friedrich Anton Wilhelm Miquel (*Commelina ludens* Miq.) in 1861. The native range of this variety is SE. China, Japan to Nansei-shoto. The species is distinguished by its darker flowers, antherodes with maroon centers (instead of entirely yellow), distalmost cyme less well developed and usually not producing a flower, and spathes proportionally broader.

C. communis var. *hortensis*, which was named by Tomitaro Makino was first published in *Bot. Mag. (Tokyo)* 15: 64. 1901. Apparently is a cultivated variety which originated from *C. communis* var. *ludens* in Japan. It is accepted by some botanists. It differs in having larger showy flowers which are used to produce a dye. A variegated form called *C. communis* var. *ludens* f. *aureostriata* named by Frank C. MacKeever in 1961 is known to occur randomly throughout much of the species' range.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

A2. Provide information on the existence of other species that look very similar [that may be detected in the risk assessment area, either in the environment, in confinement or associated with a pathway of introduction]

Include both native and non-native species that could be confused with the species being assessed, including the following elements:

other alien species with similar invasive characteristics, to be avoided as substitute species (in this case preparing a risk assessment for more than one species together may be considered);

other alien species without similar invasive characteristics, potential substitute species;

native species, potential misidentification and mis-targeting

Response: *Commelina communis* L. is an herbaceous annual plant with erect to decumbent stems. The diffusely branched stems tend to root at the basal nodes. Shoots are erect at first, becoming prostrate and spreading out due to later profuse branching, longer inter-nodes vary from 60 mm. on some plants to 160 mm. on others (Brashier 1966) Leaves are sessile, or subpetiolate with leaf sheaths cylindrical, glabrous (Sajedi 2019). Leaf blades are lanceolate to ovate-elliptic, glabrous to pubescent, acute to acuminate. The flowers are arranged on cincinni who are subtended by a a folded, heart shaped spathe. The spathe can be glabrous to very slightly pubescent, if pubescent, long white hairs are very sparsely scattered over spathe. A flower consists of 3 membranous sepals, 2 large blue petals, 1 small white petal, 5-6 stamens and a long white style. The calyx consists of three unequal sepals that are, except for glandular microhairs, glabrous. The lower two sepals are connate basally by one-half to two-thirds of their length, and together their outer and upper margins are sheathed by the upper sepal. The corolla consists of three strongly unequal, clawed, and glabrous petals. The upper two petals are blue (typically sky-blue), spatulate, and relatively large, whereas the lower petal is white, lanceolate, smaller, and inconspicuous. This size discrepancy between the upper and lower petals is not as pronounced in bud, when the petals are imbricate, with the lateral margins of the lower petal completely outside and the lateral margins of one of the upper petals completely inside the others (Ushimaru et al. 2007).

C. communis has three types of stamens: two long stamens, one medium length stamen, and three short stamens (staminoides). The anthers of the long stamens (L-anther) and medium length stamen (M-anther) produce fertile pollen; the anthers of the short stamens (S-anther) produce only a small amount of sterile pollen and function only in display (Morita and Nigorikawa, 1999; see also Hrycan and Davis, 2005).

To the human eye, the M- and S-anthers are bright yellow and more conspicuous than the brown L-anthers (Faden, 1992). In *C. communis*, the filaments of long stamens typically become elongate and appear to function as a landing platform equivalent to the floral lowerlips of the Orchidaceae. The two types of yellow anthers are considered to function as floral (pollen) guides to floral visitors in *Commelina* (Hrycan and Davis 2005).

C. communis flowers do not produce nectar, and pollen is the only floral reward for floral visitors such another Commelinaceae species (Faden, 1992). It has been noted that pollen from the L-anthers contributes to outcrossing, whereas pollen from the M-anthers functions mainly as

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

areward for insects visiting *Commelina* species (Vogel 1978; Faden 1992; Morita & Nigorikawa, 1999; Hrycan & Davis, 2005).

The gynoecium consists of three connate carpels, although the upper carpel is underdeveloped and sterile, resulting in an essentially bilocular, bisymmetric -appearing ovary that will develop into a bilocular, bivalved capsule. The style in hermaphroditic flowers curves downward and then more distally upward and is capped by a triangular, papillate stigma. The surface of the gynoecium is essentially glabrous, with the exception of glandular microhairs on the ovary (Ushimaru et al. 2007).

Asiatic dayflower produces bi-locular fruits with dimorphic seeds with each fruit bearing 2 elliptic, or 1 elliptic and 2 semi-elliptic, or 4 semi-elliptic seeds (Hollinshead 1938). The two seeds in each valve are brown-yellow, irregularly pitted, flat-sided, and truncate at one end.

Asiatic dayflower is native to temperate northeast Asia (Ushimaru 2003). However, is cosmopolitan and widely distributed around the world, principally in the northern hemisphere (USDA 2023).

In its native range, it grows on rocky places, on mountain slopes, on the banks of rivers, but it is also a weed on agricultural land and in gardens (Sîrbu & Oprea 2011).

Existence of other non-native species that look very similar

Non-native similar-looking species can be distinguished by the following differences (Verloove 2023):

Commelina erecta - its spathe is fused at the top for most of its length, has narrower leaves, the yellow stamens lack the maroon spot, and is variously covered in stiff hairs on spathes, leaves, sheaths and stem, where Asiatic Dayflower is mostly hairless.

Commelina obliqua - much more hairy (stem, leaf sheaths). Spathe margins connate basally. Lower petal blue. Capsule always 3-locular. Plant always perennial.

Commelina coelestis - plant usually erect, tall. Roots tuberous. Leaf sheaths and spathe distinctly hairy. Flowers showy, ca. 20 mm across, petals concolourous (all blue, exceptionally all white), all equally large.

Commelina diffusa - are hardly distinguishable in the absence of flowers (although the former usually has slightly shorter and narrower leaves). Lower petal blue. Capsule 3-locular. Plant often slender

Existence of other native species that look very similar

There are no native species looking very similar in the risk assessment area.

A3. Does a relevant earlier risk assessment exist? Give details of any previous risk assessment, including the final scores and its validity in relation to the risk assessment area.

Response:

Inside of the risk assessment area

Portugal

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Risk Assessment score 20: Value obtained according to a protocol adapted from the Australian Weed Risk Assessment (P-WRA). The study evaluated 172 plant species: 49 considered as invasive and 123 as non-invasive species. The results showed that the P-WRA correctly identified all invasive species. As for non-invasive species, 17% were accepted, 78% rejected and 5% required further evaluation. According to the score, *Commelina communis* has been rejected (Morais et al. 2017)

Outside of the risk assessment area

Pacific Islands

According to the Pacific Island Ecosystem at Risk project (HEAR 2023), *Commelina communis* is assessed as High Risk by a score of 21.

The relevant answers are:

Is the species highly domesticated?	no
Broad climate suitability (environmental versatility)	yes
Native or naturalized in regions with tropical or subtropical climates	yes
Does the species have a history of repeated introductions outside its natural range?	yes
Naturalized beyond native range	yes
Garden/amenity/disturbance weed	yes
Agricultural/forestry/horticultural weed	yes
Environmental weed	no
Congeneric weed	yes
Produces spines, thorns or burrs	no
Parasitic	no
Unpalatable to grazing animals	no
Toxic to animals	no
Causes allergies or is otherwise toxic to humans	no
Creates a fire hazard in natural ecosystems	no
Tolerates a wide range of soil conditions (or limestone conditions if not a volcanic island)	yes
Climbing or smothering growth habit	yes
Forms dense thickets	no
Aquatic	no
Grass	no
Nitrogen fixing woody plant	no
Produces viable seed	yes
Self-compatible or apomictic	yes
Reproduction by vegetative fragmentation	yes
Propagules likely to be dispersed unintentionally (plants growing in heavily trafficked areas)	yes
Propagules dispersed intentionally by people	yes
Propagules likely to disperse as a produce contaminant	yes
Propagules adapted to wind dispersal	no

Propagules water dispersed	yes
Evidence that a persistent propagule bank is formed (>1 yr)	yes
Well controlled by herbicides	no

The Pacific Islands have different climatic conditions than regions in the EU, though basic information on e.g. biology and habitat preferences of the species, can be taken into account. The assessment of e.g. invasiveness has to be reviewed accordingly to the different conditions in the risk assessment area.

A4. Where is the organism native?

including the following elements:

an indication of the continent or part of a continent, climatic zone and habitat where the species is naturally occurring

if applicable, indicate whether the species could naturally spread into the risk assessment area

Response: According PoWo 2023, Sajedi 2019 and Euro+Med 2006-, the native range of this species is East Europe (East European Russia, Central European Rus), North Caucasus, Transcaucasia (Azerbaijan, Armenia, and Georgia) to East and Southeast Asia, ranging from China, Taiwan, Japan, Korea, eastern Russia, Cambodia, Laos, Malaysia, Thailand, and Vietnam to India.

Commelina communis is native to temperate biome (PoWo, 2023) and has been broadly distributed all over the world, especially in the Northern Hemisphere (Santiago & Micheal 2009). *C. communis* prefers moist, shady forest edges. It is common in wet areas of crop fields, orchards, ditches, and roadsides (Maslo 2016).

Kutbay and Uçkan (1998) demonstrated that *Commelina communis* has relatively high ecological tolerance with respect to climatic and soil factors.. Thus, *C. communis* is found in both slightly arid and completely humid regions and can occur on both slightly acidic and alkaline soils and calcareous and non-calcareous soils. From this it may be suggested that high plasticity may allow plant species to maintain dominance in various environments by increasing the number of tolerable habitats.

In its native range, the species grows in rocky places, on mountain slopes, on the banks of rivers, as well as as a cultural weed in gardens (Sîrbu & Oprea 2011).

A5. What is the global non-native distribution of the organism outside the risk assessment area?

Response:

Table 1 countries with *Commelina communis* occurrences mentioned in references and databases

Continent/ region	country	general remarks	source
Asia	Iran	Present	Sajedi (2019)

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Continent/ region	country	general remarks	source
	Türkiye	Naturalized/Invasive	GBIF (2023); Brundu et al. (2011); Uludag et al. (2017); Terzioğlu & Bozkurt (2020); Randall (2017); Atasoy & Çorbacı (2018)
Africa	Algeria	Present	EPPO (2023)
	Tanzania	Present	GBIF (2023)
	South Africa	Present	GBIF (2023)
Europe	Albania	Present	GBIF (2023); Barina et al. (2014); CoL (2023); Randall (2017)
	Belarus	Present	GBIF (2023); Randall (2017)
	Bosnia and Herzgovina	Naturalized	GBIF (2023); Maslo (2014); Maslo (2016); UkrBIN (2017); Randall (2017)
	Norway	Present	Lye (2011); Randall (2017)
	Moldova	Present	GBIF (2023); Randall (2017)
	Montenegro	Present	GBIF (2023); Randall (2017)
	Macedonia	Present	GBIF (2023); Randall (2017)
	Serbia	Present	GBIF (2023); UkrBIN (2017); Vrbničanin & Božić (2014); Randall (2017)
	Switzerland	Naturalised	GBIF (2023); Randall (2017)
	Ukraine	Naturalised	Randall (2017); Burda (2018)

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Continent/ region	country	general remarks	source
North and Middle America (incl. Caribbean)	United States of America	Present; (Carolina, Dakota , Florida, Georgia, Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Kansas, Kentucky, Louisiana, Maine, Maryland, Massachusetts, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi, Missouri, Nebraska, New Hampshire, New Jersey, New York, Ohio, Oklahoma, Ontario, Oregon, Pennsylvania, Tennessee, Texas, Vermont, Virginia, West Virginia, Wisconsin) invasive in some of states	PoWo 2023, EPPO 2023; CoL (2023); Randall (2017)
	Canada	Status unknown (Ontario, Québec)	PoWo 2023, EPPO 2023; CoL (2023); Randall (2017)
South America	Argentina	Weed	Randall (2017)
	Bolivia	Present	GBIF (2023); Randall (2017)
	Brazil	Present	GBIF (2023)
	Ecuador	Present	GBIF (2023)
	Venezuela	Present	GBIF (2023)
Oceania	New Zealand	Casual	Randall (2017)

A6. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area has the species been recorded and where is it established? The information needs be given separately for recorded (including casual or transient occurrences) and established occurrences. “Established” means the process of an alien species successfully producing viable offspring with the likelihood of

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

continued survival⁴.

A6a. Recorded: List regions

A6b. Established: List regions

Freshwater / terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic

Marine regions:

Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea

Marine subregions:

Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel, Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast, Western Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Central Mediterranean Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea.

Comment on the sources of information on which the response is based and discuss any uncertainty in the response.

For delimitation of EU biogeographical regions please refer to <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2> (see also Annex VI).

For delimitation of EU marine regions and subregions consider the Marine Strategy Framework Directive areas; please refer to <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/msfd-regions-and-subregions/technical-document/pdf> (see also Annex VI).

Response: The Arctic, Anatolian and Macaronesian biogeographical regions are not part of the risk assessment area, but included for completeness. Table 2 give an overview about occurrences of the species in the biogeographical regions. In the Steppic region, no occurrence data is available.

Source of information are human observation data by GBIF (2022), European wide overviews like Euro+Med PlantBase (providing an on-line database and information system for the vascular plants of Europe and the Mediterranean region, against an up-to-date and critically evaluated consensus taxonomic core of the species concerned) as well as national floristic or invasive species references.

Response (6a): *C. communis* is recorded in the Alpine, Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Mediterranean and Black Sea biogeographical regions. No recorded occurrence data is available for Steppic biogeographical regions.

Response (6b): According to the available information, *C. communis* can be considered as “established” in the Continental, Pannonian and Mediterranean biogeographical regions.

“Established” means the process of an alien species successfully producing viable offspring with the likelihood of continued survival. In the available references (mainly Euro+Med PlantBase), the term “naturalized” is used. In order to answer question 6b, “naturalized” is used as a synonym for “established”. The assessment of established occurrences in biogeographical regions is mainly deduced from the data available on national level (compare Table 5).

⁴ Convention on Biological Diversity, Decision VI/23

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Table 2 biogeographical regions with recorded/established *Commelina communis* occurrences (grey cell – biogeographical region not covered by the risk assessment area)

biogeographical region	recorded	established	source of recorded occurrences	source of established occurrences
Alpine	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)	
Anatolian	No	No		
Arctic	No	No		
Atlantic	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	
Black Sea	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)	
Boreal	Yes	No	GBIF (2023);	
Continental	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	
Macaronesian	No	No		
Mediterranean	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	
Pannonian	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)	
Steppic	No	No	GBIF (2023)	

A7. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area could the species establish in the future under current climate and under foreseeable climate change? The information needs to be given separately for current climate and under foreseeable climate change conditions.

A7a. Current climate: List regions

A7b. Future climate: List regions

With regard to EU biogeographic and marine (sub)regions, see above.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the risk assessment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of

the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response (7a): Not evaluated.

Response (7b): Not evaluated

A8. In which EU Member States has the species been recorded and in which EU Member States has it established? List them with an indication of the timeline of observations. The information needs to be given separately for recorded and established occurrences.

A8a. Recorded: List Member States

A8b. Established: List Member States

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden

The description of the invasion history of the species shall include information on countries invaded and an indication of the timeline of the first observations, establishment and spread.

Response (8a): *Commelina communis* is recorded in 20 out of 27 Member States (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden).

Response (8b): Based upon the available data, *Commelina communis* can be assessed as established in 6 Member States (Croatia, France, Italy, Portugal, Spain).

Table 5 EU member states with recorded/established *Commelina communis* occurrences

country	recorded	established	source recorded	source established	general remarks	timeline of observations
Austria	Yes	No	GBIF (2023); PoWo (2023); Van Valkenburg (2014); CoL (2023); Randall (2017)		Casual	no data available
Belgium	Yes	No	GBIF (2023); Verloove (2006); Verloove (2023); Randall (2017)		Casual	first collected in Malonne in 1947
Bulgaria	Yes	No	Milanova & Gushev 2002; GBIF (2023); Delipavlov (1980); CoL (2023); PoWo (2023); Delipavlov (1980)		Casual	1980
Croatia	Yes	No	Hulina(2010); Milović & Mitić (2012); GBIF (2023); Tafra et al. (2013); Milović et al. (2010); Randall (2017)		Casual	no data available

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

country	recorded	established	source recorded	source established	general remarks	timeline of observations
Cyprus	No	No				
Czech Republic	Yes	No	Pyšek et al. (2012); GBIF (2023); Williamson et al. (2005); CoL (2023); PoWo (2023); Randall (2017)		Casual	1940
Denmark	Yes	No	Randall (2017)		weed	no data available
Estonia	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023);	Randall (2017)	Naturalised	no data available
Finland	Yes	No	GBIF (2023);			no data available
France (France, Corse)	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023); EPPO (2023); Van Valkenburg et al. (2014);	Randall (2017);	Naturalised	first record in the 1960s in Alsace
Germany	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	Randall (2017);	Naturalised	no data available
Greece	Yes	No	GBIF (2023); Krigas & Kokkini (2004); Randall (2017)		Casual	no data available
Hungary	Yes	No	GBIF (2023); Randall (2017)		Casual	no data available
Ireland	No	No				
Italy	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023); Puddu et al. (2016); Andreatta et al. (2021); Campisi et al. (2019)	EPPO (2023); PoWo (2023); Van Valkenburg (2014); Randall (2017); Celesti-Grapow (2009); Celesti- Grapow & Accogli (2010); Banfi & Galasso (2010)	Invasive, weed of rice field embankment s in NW Italy	1977, first report in Verona
Latvia	Yes	No	Randall (2017)		weed	no data available

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

country	recorded	established	source recorded	source established	general remarks	timeline of observations
Lithuania	Yes	Yes	EPPO (2023); Gudžinskas (1993)	Randall (2017)	invasive	no data available
Luxembourg	No	No				
Malta	No	No				no data available
Netherlands	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)			no data available
Poland	Yes	No	Tokarska-Guzik et al.(2014).		casual	1936
Portugal	Yes	Yes	Verloove & Alves (2016); UkrBIN (2017); Randall (2017)		weed	2015?
Romania	Yes	Yes	Oprea (2005); Oprea et al. (2011); Randall (2017); GBIF (2023); CoL (2023); PoWo (2023)	Anastasiu et al. (2005) Anastasiu et al. (2011)	Cultivated Naturalised	no data available
Slovakia	Yes	Yes	Ditě & Feráková (2019); GBIF (2023); Ditě et al. (2019)	Medvecka et al. (2012); Randall (2017)	Naturalised	1965
Slovenia	Yes	Yes	GBIF (2023)	Zelnik (2012); Randall (2017)	invasive	no data available
Spain	Yes	Yes	Aymerich & Sáez (2019); GBIF (2023); CoL (2023).	Verloove & Alves (2016); Romero & Amigo Vázquez (2010)	Cultivated Invasive in some regions	no data available
Sweden	Yes	No	GBIF (2023)			no data available

A9. In which EU Member States could the species establish in the future under current climate and under foreseeable climate change? The information needs be given separately for current climate and under foreseeable climate change conditions.

A9a. Current climate: List Member States

A9b. Future climate: List Member States

MINISTERUL MEDIULUI,
APELOR ȘI PĂDURILORUNIVERSITATEA DIN
BUCUREȘTI
ȘTIINȚE ȘI ARTĂMANAGEMENTUL
SPECIILOR INVAZIVE
DIN ROMÂNIA

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

With regard to EU Member States, see above.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the risk assessment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response (9a): Not evaluated

Response (9b): Not evaluated

A10. Is the organism known to be invasive (i.e. to threaten or adversely impact upon biodiversity and related ecosystem services) anywhere outside the risk assessment area?

Response: *Commelina communis* has become an aggressive invader of natural ecosystems and crop fields in North America and it is reported as invasive in some states of United States (Zheng 2004, Swearingen & Barger 2016). Thus, in Virginia and Kentucky this species appear on their invasive species list. (Invasive.org 2023).

Asiatic dayflower (*Commelina communis* L.) became increasingly invasive in Christmas tree plantations in the U.S. Northeast, significantly reducing the growth of newly transplanted trees and disfiguring the shape of established trees. The studies have shown that this weed is a highly competitive and difficult to control, and few herbicides have provided consistent control (Aulakh 2022)

In Europe, outside the risk assessment area, it is listed as an invasive alien plant in Montenegro (EPPO 2023).

A11. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area has the species shown signs of invasiveness? Indicate the area endangered by the organism as detailed as possible.

Freshwater / terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic

Marine regions:

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea

Marine subregions:

Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel, Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast, Western Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Central Mediterranean Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea

Response: *Commelina communis* exhibits a widespread distribution in parts of the Continental (Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Slovenia) and Mediterranean biogeographical regions (Croatia, Greece, Italy, France, Portugal, Spain) (Figure 2).

Nevertheless, there are documented signs of invasiveness especially in Mediterranean region: Italy, France, Portugal and Spain where *Commelina communis* is already established. In Spain, is now classified as an invasive species in Galicia (Romero & Amigo, 2009) and naturalized in Catalonia (Verloove 2020). This species occurs in *Bidentetiae tripartitae* communities, on damp sandy substrates and looks perfectly established in this area (Verloove & Alves 2016). In Italy, the species is established in many mediterranean regions: Calabria, Liguria, Toscana, Umbria (Portale della Flora d'Italia/ Portal to the Flora of Italy 2023)

A12. In which EU Member States has the species shown signs of invasiveness? Indicate the area endangered by the organism as detailed as possible.

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden

Response: There are documented signs of invasiveness in Italy – Lombardia, Piemonte (Portale della Flora d'Italia/ Portal to the Flora of Italy 2023), Lithuania (EPPO 2023), Spain (Verloove & Alves 2016; Romero & Amigo 2010) and Slovenia (Zelnik 2012).

It was classified as a non-established escape from cultivation at river Miño near the city of Ourense in northwestern Spain. In few years, this species has spread in Galicia and is now classified as an invasive species in Ourense and Pontevedra (Romero & Amigo, 2009)

A13. Describe any known socio-economic benefits of the organism.

including the following elements:

Description of known uses for the species, including a list and description of known uses in the risk assessment area and third countries, if relevant.

Description of social and economic benefits deriving from those uses, including a description of the environmental, social and economic relevance of each of those uses and an indication of associated beneficiaries, quantitatively and/or qualitatively depending on what information is available.

If the information available is not sufficient to provide a description of those benefits for the entire risk assessment area, qualitative data or different case studies from across the risk assessment area

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

or third countries shall be used, if available.

Response: *Commelina communis* had been used in traditional Chinese medicine as a medicinal herb with febrifugal, antipyretic, anti-inflammatory and diuretic effects. Leaf tea from *C. communis* has been in use in gargle for sore throat, diuretic, acute tonsillitis, urinary infections, dysentery, acute intestinal enteritis, obesity, and diabetes mellitus (Youn et al. 2004; eFloras 2008; PFAF 2017).

Recent pharmacological studies have revealed that *C. communis* contains and other active compounds: p-hydroxycinnamic acid, with antibacterial activity (Liu et al. 2023); D-mannitol, with an antitussive effect; a flavonoid orientin who decrease the lipid accumulation in mouse adipocytes (Nagai et al. 2018), antioxidants (11 flavonoid glycosides, isoquercitrin, isorhamnetin-3-O-rutinoside, isorhamnetin-3-O-b-D-glucoside, glucoluteolin, chrysoeriol-7-O-b-D-glucoside, orientin, vitexin, isoorientin, isovitexin, swertisin, and flavocommelin) (Shibano et al. 2008; Zhang et al. 2018); alkaloids with antiviral activity (Bing et al. 2009). Also, some studies show an anti-diabetic effect through α -glucosidase inhibitory action as a regulator of post-prandial blood glucose (Kim et al. 1999; Youn et al. 2004)

The petals of flowers have also been used in Japan to produce a dye and a pigment (PFAF 2017). *Commelina communis* var. *hortensis*, with its larger petals which yield a blue juice is used in manufacturing a paper called *boshigami* or *aigami*, which is the famous product of the Yamada village in the Shiga prefecture. The paper is usually resoaked, allowing the pigment to be reabsorbed in water for use as a dye. The dye, also referred to as *aigami*, *aobanagami* or *tsuyukusairo* is composed primarily of malonyl awobanin and was used extensively as a colorant in 18th and 19th century woodblock prints in Japan, especially during the early Ukiyo-e era (Japanese Architecture and Art Net Users System 2001, Shimoyama et al. 2006).

Commelinin, the pigment from the flowers of *C. communis*, is known to be a stable blue complex pigment even in acidic condition. The results of a study demonstrate that commelinin is a tetranuclear (4 Mg^{2+}) metal complex, in which two Mg^{2+} ions chelate to six anthocyanin molecules, while the other two Mg^{2+} ions bind to six flavone molecules, stabilizing the commelinin complex, a new type of supramolecular complex (Shiono et al. 2008).

In China and India the plant is used as a vegetable and fodder crop (Purdue University 2003). Leaves, flowers, young shoots and seeds are used raw or cooked (PFAF 2017).

In the last decades, *Commelina communis* started to be used as a model organism in the field of plant physiology due to its complex pigment chemistry (Hondo et al. 1992; Oyama & Kondo 2004; Shiono et al 2008; Misawa et al. 2013) and the ease of viewing its stomata (Lee & Bowling 1992; Joon-Sang 1998; Wilkinson et al. 2001). Also, *C. communis* can serve as pioneer species for reclamation of copper mined land and can be used as model plants for investigation of plant tolerance mechanisms, and geochemical prospecting (Tang et al. 1999).

Recent research has also revealed that the Asiatic dayflower can bioaccumulate a number of heavy metals (Cu, Cd, Cr, Zn), making it a candidate for revegetating and essentially cleaning spoiled copper mines (Tang & Xi 2002; Xiao et al. 2008; Wang 2013; Ge & Zhang 2015; Pan et al. 2021). Several animals and fungi use the plant as a food source, with a few species feeding upon it exclusively.

Commelina communis is grown also as an ornamental garden plant and groundcover plant - beds and side borders (Hulina 2010; Randall 2017; Von Karl-Georg et al. 2017).

SECTION B – Detailed assessment

Important instructions:

In the case of lack of information the assessors are requested to use a standardized answer: “No information has been found.” In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

With regard to the scoring of the likelihood of events or the magnitude of impacts see Annexes I and II.

With regard to the confidence levels, see Annex III.

Highlight the selected response score and confidence level in bold but keep the other scores in normal text (so that the selected score is evident in the final document).

1 PROBABILITY OF INTRODUCTION AND ENTRY

Important instructions:

Introduction is the movement of the species into the risk assessment area (it may be either in captive conditions and/or in the environment, depending on the relevant pathways).

Entry is the release/escape/arrival in the environment, i.e. occurrence in the wild

Introduction and entry may coincide for species entering through pathways such as “corridor” or “unaided”, but it also may differ. If different, please consider all relevant pathways, both for the introduction into the risk assessment area and the entry in the environment.

For each described pathway, in each of the questions below, ensure that there are separate comments explicitly addressing both the “introduction” and “entry” where applicable and as appropriate. The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD) should be used (see Annex IV). For detailed explanations of the CBD pathway classification scheme consult the IUCN/CEH guidance document⁵ and the provided key to pathways⁶.

For organisms which are already present (recorded or established) in the risk assessment area, the likelihood of introduction and entry should be scored as “very likely” by default.

Repeated (independent) introductions and entries at separate locations in the risk assessment area should be considered here (see Qu. 1.7).

Qu. 1.1. List relevant pathways through which the organism could be introduced into the risk assessment area and/or enter into the environment. Where possible give details about the

⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f8627bbc-1f15-11eb-b57e-01aa75ed71a1>

⁶ <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/0aeba7f1-c8c2-45a1-9ba3-bcb91a9f039d/TSSR-2016-010%20CBD%20pathways%20key%20full%20only.pdf>

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

specific origins and end points of the pathways as well as a description of any associated commodities.

For each pathway answer questions 1.2 to 1.8 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than one pathway, e.g. 1.2a, 1.3a, etc. and then 1.2b, 1.3b etc. for the next pathway.

In this context a pathway is the route or mechanism of introduction and/or entry of the species.

The description of commodities with which the introduction of the species is generally associated shall include a list and description of commodities with an indication of associated risks (e.g. the volume of trade; the likelihood of a commodity being contaminated or acting as vector).

If there are no active pathways or potential future pathways this should be stated explicitly here, and there is no need to answer the questions 1.2-1.9.

Response: “The Global Compendium of Weeds” (2017) mentioned 5 pathways for introduction of *Commelina communis*, one accidental and 4 intentional:

contaminant (accidental contaminants in produce, seed, livestock, possessions, vehicle or equipment);

crop (edible plants);

herbal (plants used as herbal medicine, natural therapies and other related uses);

ornamental (grown by people for all sorts of reasons);

pasture (includes fodder, forage, silage, hay, straw).

These pathways can be assimilated to the following CBD pathways (Annex IV):

(a) Transport – seed contaminant

On March 23, 2023, a report of the specialists of the Federal State Budget Institution Primorskaya MVL (Russia), who checked 293.7 thousand tons of grain products intended for export was done. According to the results of the research, 11.5 thousand tons of grain contaminated with quarantine and non-quarantine weeds were identified. Of the non-quarantine objects in the same lots of grain, 22 species of weed seeds were identified. Among these is also mentioned *Commelina communis* (Russian federation 2023)

Also, Lye (2011) declared that seeds of the Asiatic dayflower reached Norway as pollution in rice sacs imported by asian shops. In Oslo there are many shops who import large quantities rice, vegetables and fruit from East Asia.

In Poland, seeds of *Commelina communis* are introduced with oil plants seeds (Tokarska-Guzik 2005).

(b): Horticulture (escape from confinement)

Horticulture is the intentional introduction of the species into the risk assessment area. *Commelina communis* has been used as a garden ornamental species planted in summer flower beds and borders in Austria (Von Bernhardt et al. 2017).

(c): Ornamental purpose other than horticulture (escape from confinement)

This pathway involves the intentional introduction of the species for ornamental purposes, though entry into the natural environment would be unintentional. This pathway includes the movement of all potential plant parts into the risk assessment area.

(d) Agriculture (escape from confinement)

In China and India the plant is used as a vegetable and fodder crop (Purdue University 2003). It had been used in traditional Chinese medicine as a medicinal herb and the last studies discovered new active compounds with antiviral, antioxidant activity and hypoglycemic effect.

Pathway name (a): Transport – seed contaminant

Qu. 1.2a. Is introduction and/or entry along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Entry via this pathway is unintentional movement of the species via the contamination of imported grains.

Qu. 1.3a. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced and/or enter into the environment through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.
- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction and/or entry based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in subsequent establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. The transport of imported grains could facilitate entry into the RA area. There is the potential for numerous seeds to be transported along this pathway.

Each *Commelina communis* plant can produce 500–1 000 seeds (Mandák et al. 2012).

Qu. 1.4a. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There are evidences that grains exported from countries where *Commelina communis* is native are contaminated with seeds of various plant species including *Commelina communis*, indicating that it is very likely the species can survive along this pathway. The germination rate of the seeds of *Commelina communis* is 80-90% (Takabayashi & Nakayama 1978, 1979; Watanabe & Hirokawa 1969). Most seeds stay dormant and more than 80% among them could germinate even after four and a half years (Takabayashi & Nakayama 1979).

It is unlikely that plant material will reproduce or increase along the pathway.

Qu. 1.5a. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices before and during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species is likely to survive existing management practices along this pathway. However, there is no information available for this pathway.

Qu. 1.6a. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment undetected?

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is information regarding the existence of these seeds as contaminants of grains (Lye 2011; Russian federation 2023) Therefore, it is likely that the species could be introduced into the risk assessment area undetected.

Qu. 1.7c. How isolated or widespread are possible points of introduction and/or entry into the environment in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	isolated widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There are no specific data on the points of introduction or entry.

Points of introduction can include road routes which join countries and other international transportation hubs. These are widespread throughout the risk assessment area. Urbanization and the management of land is increasing through the risk assessment area.

Qu. 1.8c. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is evidence that the species has moved along this pathway and therefore it is scored likely with medium confidence.

Pathway name (b): Horticulture (escape from confinement)

Qu. 1.2b. Is introduction and/or entry along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: Horticulture is the intentional introduction of the species into the risk assessment area for the commercial culturing. As an ornamental plant it was introduced from East-Asia (Hulina 2010). *Commelina communis* var. *hortensis*, was developed by cultivation by Makino in Japan. Also, *C. communis* var. *ludens* f. *aureostriata* was created for ornamental purpose.

The pathway includes the movement of plant material via e-commerce. Just the seeds of the species are available via the large retail suppliers (e.g. eBay).

Qu. 1.3b. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced and/or enter into the environment through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction and/or entry based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in subsequent establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species is an ornamental species and grown in the risk assessment area. Although seeds are available on the internet (ebay.com, hayefield.com), no sites in the risk assessment area have been identified that sell seeds of this species. No information was found on the sale as a living plant.

No information has been found about volumes of the species imported into the risk assessment area.

As this route of introduction is deliberate, and the planting of the species in gardens would be the end result of the movement of the species, a low number of propagules could lead to the introduction of the species. Therefore, it is only moderately likely that large numbers of the organism will travel along this pathway.

It is moderately likely that the species will enter the natural environment via this pathway. Potentially, if planted in nurseries and garden centers, plant material or seeds may escape from confined areas into the natural environment.

Dumping of material to the natural environment may occur, although it is unlikely with good practice in the horticulture industry. Dumped waste, containing seeds and stem pieces, was not reported.

If eradication measures are taken, there is the potential that the species can re-establish if it is dumped again or if some small shoot or root material is left behind. Plants can regenerate from a small piece of stem.

Qu. 1.4b. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The pathway ‘Horticulture’ is the deliberate movement of plant material into the risk assessment area and as such plant material would be maintained and moved to ensure survival.

Commelina communis it was used as an ornamental plant (Banfi & Galasso (2010) but at present just seeds are sold. No information was found on the sale as a living plant in or out of risk assesment area.

However, three types of material can potentially enter the risk assessment area via this pathway: living plants, seeds and cuttings.

Living plants

It is unlikely the plants will reproduce or increase during their transport along this pathway. For transport they are packed and kept in dry conditions, which allows survival but not growth or reproduction. It is unlikely the plants will reproduce or increase during their transport along this pathway.

Stem/Shoot material

Shoots can be moved along the path. There is no data on the commercial use of this type of material, but it is likely that it will survive transport as the industry will ensure that they are properly packaged to ensure survival. *C. communis* it has stems that crawl along the ground and rooting adventitiously at the nodes, thus growing survival potential (Huang et al. 2000; Santiago and Michael 2009) If the shoots detach from the plant and fall on moist soil, there may be a greater chance that they will root and survive in these habitats.

Seed

Because e-commerce of seeds has been observed, it is likely that seeds of this species are part of the horticulture pathway of the species.

C. communis mainly a self-pollinated plant; however, cross-pollination by insects has also been reported. A single plant can produce 5–80 bisexual flowers in each life cycle (Li et al. 2016). Each *C. communis* plant can produce 500–1 000 seeds (Mandák et al. 2012).

C. communis is known for its opportunistic germination throughout the growing season (Prostko and Webster 2007; GómezVargas 2012).

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Scientific studies have shown that *C. communis* growth and production increases with high water content, whereas water stress significantly decreases its growth and seed production (Haroon et al. 2019).

Seeds may survive along the pathway. It would not be possible for the species to reproduce or increase during transport and storage along this pathway. There is no detailed analysis on the viability of seed when are transported. The seeds are resilient and relative long-lived (Von Bernhardt et al. 2017). More than 80% of the seeds can germinate even after a few years in the soil seed bank (Takabayashi and Nakayama 1978).

Qu. 1.5b. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices before and during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Seeds are the commodity itself and it deliberately enters the risk assessment area. The seeds are sold through some internet sites and sent by parcel to the countries where they are requested. They are probably transported in envelopes and kept in low humidity conditions. However, the species is very likely to survive.

Qu. 1.6b. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment undetected?

Please note that “detection” here is considered as any system or event that may actively contribute to record the presence of a species in a way that appropriate management measures could be potentially undertaken by relevant authorities.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is unlikely that the organism will enter the risk assessment area undetected via this pathway as this concerns the intentional movement of plant material into the risk assessment area.

The species could enter the environment undetected as the species may escape from garden centers or botanic gardens via seed or the dumping of plant material. If the species escapes, it would be difficult to quickly detect the seeds or plant, as only small fragments of the stem are enough to form a viable plant.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 1.7b. How isolated or widespread are possible points of introduction and/or entry into the environment in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	isolated widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: For the introduction of seeds, the entry points are widespread as anyone with an internet connection and a postal address can obtain seeds of the species from outside the risk assessment area. Therefore, introduction points are widespread within the risk assessment area.

Qu. 1.8b. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: This pathway is active, and it is moderately likely that the species is being moved along the pathway from outside the risk assessment area into the risk assessment area.

The seed material can be purchased online. We can say that horticulture is more of a historical way, because the species is likely to be propagated in the risk assessment area, because the species can be easily grown from stem fragments and by seeds.

Pathway name (c): Ornamental purpose other than horticulture (escape from confinement)

Qu. 1.2c. Is introduction and/or entry along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: This pathway involves the intentional introduction of the species for ornamental purposes, though entry into the natural environment would be unintentional. This pathway includes the movement of all potential plant parts into the risk assessment area.

For escape/entry into the environment, this pathway includes the dumping of plant material (both intentionally and unintentionally) into the natural environment. Many studies have classified the

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ornamental species *Commelina communis* as escaped from cultivation (Webb 1980; Tafra et al. 2013; Verloove & Alves2016; Von Bernhardt et al.2017; Randall 2017; Andreatta et al. 2021).

Qu. 1.3c. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced and/or enter into the environment through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.
- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction and/or entry based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in subsequent establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Studies about this species indicate ornamental cultivation as one of the main pathways (Webb 1980; Tafra et al. 2013; Verloove & Alves2016; Von Bernhardt et al.2017; Randall 2017; Andreatta et al. 2021). There is no information on frequency or volumes entering the risk assessment area or the environment.

There is no additional information related to this pathway. It is possible that the spread of the species is mainly due to the dumping of garden waste. This is probably the main factor driving the species towards the environment in the risk assessment area.

If eradication measures are taken following planting, there is the potential that the species can re-establish if replanted. The number of potential areas, where the species can escape from, increases the difficulty of eradication at a large scale.

Qu. 1.4c. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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2014-2020

	very likely		
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Response: Plant material is the commodity itself and it is deliberately moved for sale within the risk assessment area. Therefore, plant parts or whole parts are likely to survive along the pathway to the end point where it is planted in a garden.

The following section lists the plant parts of concern:

Live plants (low concern)

Live plants may be dumped as garden waste into the natural environment, and it is likely that these can survive in some conditions.

Stem/shoot material (high concern)

C. communis has an aggressive growth habit, creeping along the soil and rooting adventitiously at the nodes, thus increasing the potential for survival. Stem material may spread outside the confines of a garden where it is deliberately planted. Additionally, if garden waste is placed on a suitable substrate, it will be able to survive.

Seeds (high concern)

Plants with seeds or contaminated soil seed can be dumped as garden waste into the natural environment. Each *C. communis* plant can produce 500–1 000 seeds in accordance with laboratory statistics. Mature *C. communis* seeds easily fall on the ground and buried into the soil. These seeds form a massive seed bank, maintaining genotypes over time and containing significantly large genetic diversity information. More than 80% of the seeds can germinate even after a few years in the soil seed bank (Takabayashi and Nakayama 1978).

C. communis is known also for its opportunistic germination throughout the growing season (Prostko and Webster 2007; GómezVargas 2012). These seeds are very likely to germinate or form a massive seed bank with a very high chance of germinating in the coming years.

Qu. 1.5c. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices before and during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Management practices such as physical removal or cutting may lead to fragmentation of plant material. Dumping as garden waste may increase the propagule pressure of the species in the environment.

Other management practices (e.g. chemical control in gardens) may have a minimal impact on the survival and reproduction of the species by reducing the vigour of the plant or killing it directly. *C. communis* is tolerant to most herbicides popularly used in maize and soybean field such as imazethapyr, acetochlor, fluroxypyr, glyphosate, etc. (Ma et al. 2009; Santiago and Micheal 2009).

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

The control efficacy of a herbicide varied on *C. communis* populations in different locations, causing this species escaping from herbicide treatments in some areas (Juan et al. 2018)

Qu. 1.6c. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment undetected?

Please note that “detection” here is considered as any system or event that may actively contribute to record the presence of a species in a way that appropriate management measures could be potentially undertaken by relevant authorities.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: As the pathway is intended for ornamental use in gardens and parks, it is very unlikely that the organism introduction into the risk assessment area is undetected.

It is moderately likely that *C. communis* can enter the environment undetected because the species is planted in gardens, sometimes in close proximity to natural habitats, where there is potential for escape.

Qu. 1.7c. How isolated or widespread are possible points of introduction and/or entry into the environment in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	isolated widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. commelina* is already present in many gardens from risk assessment area where has an invasive behaviour (Krigas & Kokkini 2004; Oprea et al. 2011; Urbisz 2011; Tafra et al 2013;

Qu. 1.8c. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: This introduction pathway is the most active and there is evidence that the species is being moved along the pathway into the risk assessment area. Based on this, a score of likely with a moderate confidence has been given.

Pathway name(d): Agriculture (escape from confinement)

Qu. 1.2d. Is introduction and/or entry along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is a medicinal and edible plant. Also, is used as pasture. Global Compendium of Weeds (2017) mentioned among amain major pathways also use as crop, herbal and pasture.

No information has been found about this.

Qu. 1.3d. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced and/or enter into the environment through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.
- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals/ propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction and/or entry based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in subsequent establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found.

Qu. 1.4d. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

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2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found.

Qu. 1.5d. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices before and during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found.

Qu. 1.6d. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found.

Qu. 1.7a. How isolated or widespread are possible points of introduction and/or entry into the environment in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	isolated widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found.

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2014-2020

Qu. 1.8a. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found.

Qu. 1.9. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment based on all pathways and specify if different in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions.

Provide a thorough assessment of the risk of introduction in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions: providing insight in to the risk of introduction into the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Commelina communis* is very likely to be introduced and enter the risk assessment area with a high confidence. The species is already present in the risk assessment area.

The species is recorded in the Alpine, Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Mediterranean and Black Sea biogeographical regions.

Qu. 1.10. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment based on all pathways in foreseeable climate change conditions?

Thorough assessment of the risk of introduction in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

- the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)
- the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)
- what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the likelihood of introduction (e.g. change in trade or user preferences)

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

The thorough assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment of likely introduction within a medium timeframe scenario (e.g. 30-50 years) with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Not available

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2 PROBABILITY OF ESTABLISHMENT

Important instructions:

- For organisms which are already established in parts of the risk assessment area or have previously been eradicated, the likelihood of establishment should be scored as “very likely” by default.
- Discuss the risk also for those parts of the risk assessment area, where the species is not yet established.

Qu. 2.1. How likely is it that the organism will be able to establish in the risk assessment area based on similarity of climatic and abiotic conditions in its distribution elsewhere in the world?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Commelina communis* is already established in the natural environment in the risk assessment area (Estonia, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain) (see Qu. A8b). It is very likely that the species can establish in other countries within the RA area where the habitats and climate is suitable to establishment (see Qu. A9).

Commelina species are C-3, monocotyledonous plants and therefore have a high efficiency of CO₂ uptake at low irradiance; therefore, they tolerate shade very well and could become persistent. They are both annuals and perennials and therefore dominate the fallow vegetation because they are most competitive due to their growth and regeneration characteristics (Van Rijn 2000)

Within its native distribution, *Commelina communis* is most typical of moist, open places, including shady forest edges and wet areas of crop fields, orchards, ditches, and roadsides (Hsu 1978; Hong et al. 2000). Within its native range in China it is also sometimes considered a pest, especially in the northeast of the country where it has caused economically significant agricultural damage in orchards.

Kutbay and Ucan (1998) reported that Asiatic dayflower has broad ecological tolerance to climatic and soil factors; this phenotypic plasticity allows this species to maintain dominance in several environments. *C. communis* prefers humid areas receiving partial sunlight, light textured (sandy or loam) and nutrient rich soils for its growth and development. The plant is found to be distributed and established throughout the Black Sea region especially in the areas receiving high amount of rainfall. (Farooq & Akyol 2015).

It prefers moist, fertile soil but also grows well on roadsides and in non-crop areas. It can occur on both slightly acidic and alkaline soils and calcareous and non-calcareous soils. Also is found in both slightly arid and completely humid regions (Kutbay & Ucan. 1998).

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

The plant species is doing well in very short periods of time cold winter tracts, and that she thrives best in areas with hot summers, preferably where the average temperature for the three hottest months reaches over 20° C (Lye 2011).

C. communis is already established in the risk assessment area and further establishment is very likely as there are climatically suitable areas and habitats available.

Qu. 2.2. How widespread are habitats or species necessary for the survival, development and multiplication of the organism in the risk assessment area? Consider if the organism specifically requires another species to complete its life cycle.

RESPONSE	very isolated isolated moderately widespread widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Within its native distribution, the plant is most typical of moist, open places, including shady forest edges and wet areas of crop fields, orchards, ditches, and roadsides (Hong & DeFillipps, 2000; Hsu 1978). *C. communis* has become an aggressive weed of crop fields within its native range in China and Japan and could cause serious damage in orchards, onion fields, tobacco fields and tree plantations (Oiyama & Shibayama 2000; Gómez-Vargas J M. 2012; Chen et al. 2019; Dai et al. 2021). Wherever it goes, it extrudes the crop and form a dense community (Haroon et al. 2023).

In Zagreb and surroundings (Croatia), it is widely distributed and it can be found in ruderal places, in pavement crevices etc., where it can persist for several years and to expand in an area owing to rooting at the nodes. Its thriving is mostly connected to shaded and humid habitats and its localities are scattered particularly in urban environment (Hulina 2010).

Studies made in town of Omiš (Dalmatia, Croatia) (Tafra et al. 2013) reported the species from ruderal habitats (trash dumps, heaps of soil and construction waste etc.) and cultivated surfaces (gardens, olive groves, vineyards).

In Belgium, it was found on dumps and as an impurity in soybeans, especially in the port of Gent, sometimes abundantly so (Verloove 2023).

In France, it was often recorded as naturalized in different habitats: forest borders (Schirrhoffen), wastelands and gardens (Barr, Obernai) and on very urbanized places such as pavements (Strasbourg) (EPPO 2023).

In Romania it was reported as a sub-spontaneous species in the wild in many localities, spread along the roads and dishes, or as a weed in maize crops, preferably in shady places as well as in ruderal places (Oprea et al. 2011)

In Southeast Norway plants of *C. communis* were discovered in a wasteland field at 95 m a.s.l. (Lye 2011).

The first indication of this species for Bosnia and Herzegovina was in the city of Mostar, on the left bank of the River Neretva, on periodical lood deposits with an abundance of organic material (Maslo, 2014).

In Turkey, the plant has created extensive populations especially in the Eastern Black Sea region and can create significant problems in agricultural areas. The extensively invaded habitats were found in the agricultural areas such as tea plantations, hazelnut and kiwi orchards, mixed fruits and vegetables fields as well as non-agricultural areas such as stream and forest sides, vacant lands, roadsides etc. The plant is found to be distributed and established throughout the Black Sea region especially in the areas receiving high amount of rainfall (Farooq & Akyol 2015)

In North America, the species is present in "weedy and waste places; edges of fields, woods, and marshes, often in thick herbaceous vegetation; occasionally in woods" (eFloras 2008).

C. communis does not require another organism to complete its life cycle.

C. communis has relatively high ecological tolerance. From this it may be suggested that high plasticity may allow plant species to maintain dominance in various environments by increasing the number of tolerable habitats (Kutbay & Uçkan 1998).

When taking into consideration all of the habitats detailed above, within the EU, habitats that can facilitate the survival, development and multiplication of the *C. communis* are widespread.

Qu. 2.3. How likely is it that establishment will occur despite competition from existing species in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In Spain, *C. communis* was recorded participating in nitrophilous riparian grasslands, on sandy and humid soils, in the Baixo Natural Area as well as in the community of *Bidentetea tripartitae* on sand substrate, on the banks of the Miño (Romero & Amigo 2009; Verloove & Alves 2016).

In Lombardia (Italy), *C. communis* lowers the biodiversity of the plant communities in which it settles, taking space away from native species; it also infests edges of the rice fields (Banfi & Galasso 2010).

There is no scientific information on competition with native species.

Qu. 2.4. How likely is it that establishment will occur despite predators, parasites or pathogens already present in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely	CONFIDENCE	low
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	unlikely moderately likely likely very likely		medium high
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Response: Fungi from Kordyana, Brachybasidiaceae (Exobasidiales, Basidiomycota), are leaf pathogens causing a white smut-like disease, typically on members of Commelinaceae. Several species of Kordyana, in particular *K. brasiliensis*, *K. tradescantiae*, and *K. celebensis*, are considered promising candidates for biocontrol of invasive weeds, such as *Tradescantia fluminensis* in Australia, New Zealand, and China and *C. benghalensis* in the United States and China. In Korea, it was identified and described the species *K. commelinae* found on *C. communis* and *C. minor*. (Park et al. 2021).

There are no reports of promising insect candidates for biological control reported on *Commelina* spp. in the risk assessment area. In Korea and China there have been reports of *Lema concinnipennis* and *Lema scutellaris* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) two leaf-feeding species on *C. communis* [86]. *Noelema sexpunctata* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) another leaf-feeding species was also reported on *C. communis*. In Central Virginia, USA, *Pycnodees medius* (Hemiptera: Miridae) was found to cause tissue necrosis on *C. communis*. Various insects were also screened for their potential as bio-control agents of weeds in rice and it was found that *Necrobis ruficollis* (blue beetle), *Rhaphidopalpa africana* (yellow beetle), *Conocephalus* sp., *Tetragnathidae* spp. and *Paracrinema tricolor* (grasshopper) were promising (Isaac et al. 2013).

Larvae of *Xenapates gaullei* were detected on *Commelina communis* plants in West Africa and might be a candidate for biological control of invasive *Commelina* spp. (Liston et al. 2015).

U2- tobacco mosaic virus has also been found infecting *C. communis* (Isaac et al. 2013). Brome mosaic virus isolates have been identified infecting *C. diffusa* and *C. communis* in Fayetteville, Arkansas, USA. (Valverde 1983).

These species are not present in the EU.

It is very likely that establishment will occur despite predators, parasites or pathogens already present in the risk assessment area. *C. communis* does not have any host specific natural enemies in the risk assessment area and there is no evidence that native organisms feed or infect the species in substantial levels to inflict any damage on the species.

Qu. 2.5. How likely is the organism to establish despite existing management practices in the risk assessment area? Explain if existing management practices could facilitate establishment.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* occurs both in crops and sub-spontaneously in most parts of Europe (WEBB, 1980), being present in different types of habitats, especially in disturbed ones.

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2014-2020

The establishment of *C. communis* is possible for a number of different habitat types, mainly for disturbed habitats.

The species is reported to be challenging to control in glyphosate tolerant crop systems. *C. communis* is tolerant to most herbicides popularly used in maize and soybean field such as imazethapyr, acetochlor, fluroxypyr, glyphosate, etc. (Ma et al. 2009; Santiago and Micheal 2009)

C. communis has an aggressive growth habit, creeping along the soil and rooting adventitiously at the nodes, thus increasing the potential for survival (Huang et al. 2000; Pyšek 2001; Li et al. 2008; Santiago and Micheal 2009). The shoots of the plant can break and resprouting if they have contact with the ground. The seeds are resilient and relative long-lived (Von Bernhardt et al. 2017).

Qu. 2.6. How likely is it that biological properties of the organism would allow it to survive eradication campaigns in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In the risk assessment area, sexual reproduction is the main method of reproduction of this species. These seeds of *C. communis* form a massive seed bank in soil, maintaining genotypes over time and containing significantly large genetic diversity information. More than 80% of the seeds can germinate even after a few years in the soil seed bank (Takabayashi and Nakayama 1978).

A study revealed that growth, biomass partitioning and chlorophyll fluorescence of *C. communis* biotypes is severely affect by drought stress. As the duration of water stress were reduced, the plant height, number of leaves, biomass and seed production were increased. This proves that *C. communis* growth and production increases with high water content, whereas water stress significantly decreases its growth and seed production. (Haroon et al 2023)

Therefore, unless eradication campaigns are thorough and remove all reproductive material, it is likely that the species can survive during eradication campaigns. A medium confidence is given as there is no published information for the risk assessment area on eradication campaigns.

Qu. 2.7. How likely are the biological characteristics of the organism to facilitate its establishment in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

- a list and description of the reproduction mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area
- an indication of the propagule pressure of the species (e.g. number of gametes, seeds, eggs or propagules, number of reproductive cycles per year) of each of those reproduction mechanisms in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

- If relevant, comment on the likelihood of establishment based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.
- If relevant, comment on the adaptability of the organism to facilitate its establishment and if low genetic diversity in the founder population would have an influence on establishment.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Commelina communis* reproduces by seed and vegetatively through stem cuttings. It is mainly a self-pollinated plant; however, cross-pollination by insects has also been reported. That is, a single plant can produce 5–80 bisexual flowers in each life cycle (Li et al. 2016). Each *C. communis* plant can produce 500–1 000 seeds.

In the risk assessment area, sexual reproduction is the main method of reproduction of this species. These seeds of *C. communis* form a massive seed bank in soil, maintaining genotypes over time and containing significantly large genetic diversity information. More than 80% of the seeds can germinate even after a few years in the soil seed bank (Takabayashi and Nakayama 1978).

Also, the plant can root at the leaf nodes on moist ground, forming new plants vegetatively. Asiatic dayflower has an aggressive growth habit, creeping along the soil and rooting adventitiously at the nodes, thus increasing the potential for survival (Kuhns and Harpster 2005).

Qu. 2.8. If the organism does not establish, then how likely is it that casual populations will continue to occur?

Consider, for example, a species which cannot reproduce in the risk assessment area, because of unsuitable climatic conditions or host plants, but is present because of recurring introduction, entry and release events. This may also apply for long-living organisms.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In areas, where *C. communis* is not established, casual populations may occur in ruderal places and cultivated surfaces. The species is mostly connected to shaded and humid habitats and its localities are scattered particularly in urban environment. Casual populations are likely to occur in areas outside the optimum climatic conditions.

Qu. 2.9. Estimate the overall likelihood of establishment in the risk assessment area under current climatic conditions. In addition, details of the likelihood of establishment in relevant

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2014-2020

biogeographical regions under current climatic conditions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the risk of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions: providing insight in the risk of establishment in (new areas in) the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The overall likelihood of *C. communis* establishing in the risk assessment area is very likely with high confidence. The species is already established in the Continental, Pannonian and Mediterranean biogeographical regions. Countries where the species is established include: Estonia, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain.

The Alpine, Atlantic, Boreal and Black Sea biogeographical regions have a high proportion of area suitable for the establishment of the species and thus further establishment is likely in these areas under the current climatic conditions.

Qu. 2.10. Estimate the overall likelihood of establishment in the risk assessment area under foreseeable climate change conditions. In addition, details of the likelihood of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions under foreseeable climate change conditions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the risk of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

- the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)
- the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)
- what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the likelihood of establishment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The thorough assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment of likely establishment within a medium timeframe scenario (e.g. 30-50 years) with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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	very likely		
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Response: NA

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2014-2020

3 PROBABILITY OF SPREAD

Important instructions:

- Spread is defined as the expansion of the geographical distribution of an alien species within the risk assessment area.
- Repeated releases at separate locations do not represent continuous spread and should be considered in the probability of introduction and entry section (Qu. 1.7).

Qu. 3.1. How important is the expected spread of this organism within the risk assessment area by natural means? (List and comment on each of the mechanisms for natural spread.)

including the following elements:

- a list and description of the natural spread mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.
- an indication of the rate of spread discussed in relation to the species biology and the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

The description of spread patterns here refers to the CBD pathway category “Unaided (Natural Spread)”. It should include elements of the species life history and behavioural traits able to explain its ability to spread, including: reproduction or growth strategy, dispersal capacity, longevity, dietary requirements, environmental and climatic requirements, specialist or generalist characteristics.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Commelina communis* reproduces by seed and vegetatively through stem cuttings. It is mainly a self-pollinated plant; however, cross-pollination by insects has also been reported. That is, a single plant can produce 5–80 bisexual flowers in each life cycle (Li et al. 2016). Each *C. communis* plant can produce 500–1 000 seeds.

In the risk assessment area, sexual reproduction is the main method of reproduction of this species. These seeds of *C. communis* form a massive seed bank in soil, maintaining genotypes over time and containing significantly large genetic diversity information. More than 80% of the seeds can germinate even after a few years in the soil seed bank (Takabayashi and Nakayama 1978).

Birds are reported as a spread way of the seeds (Von Bernhardt et al. 2017).

Also, *C. communis* can reproduce vegetatively, rooting adventitiously at the nodes.

Qu. 3.2a. List and describe relevant pathways of spread other than "unaided". For each pathway answer questions 3.3 to 3.9 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than one pathway, e.g. 3.3a, 3.4a, etc. and then 3.3b, 3.4b etc. for the next pathway.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

including the following elements:

- a list and description of pathways of spread with an indication of their importance and associated risks (e.g. the likelihood of spread in the risk assessment area, based on these pathways; likelihood of survival, or reproduction, or increase during transport and storage; ability and likelihood of transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host) in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.
- an indication of the rate of spread for each pathway discussed in relation to the species biology and the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.
- All relevant pathways of spread (except “Unaided (Natural Spread)”, which is assessed in Qu. 3.1) should be considered. The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity shall be used (see Annex IV).

Spread pathways are detailed in order of importance

- (a) Transport – seed contaminant
- (b): Horticulture (escape from confinement)
- (c): Ornamental purpose other than horticulture (escape from confinement)
- (d) Agriculture (escape from confinement)

Pathway name: (a) Transport – seed contaminant

Qu. 3.3a. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	Unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: This pathway of spread is unintentional as contaminant of grains.

Qu. 3.4a. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway

- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* was found as contaminant of grain that can also be used for sowing for agricultural purposes. It is known that in some grain exporting countries outside and inside of risk assessment there, *C. communis* is a weed in soybean, rice, wheat and corn crops (Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic).

Jehlík (1998) proposes 40 plant species to be put into quarantine for the area of the Czech Republic including *C. communis*. The proposal was not accepted (Soukup et al. 2004)

Qu. 3.5a. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is very likely that *C. communis* seeds will survive during transport and storage along this pathway. Being transported with other seeds used for sowing or for food use, they are kept in favorable conditions (low humidity) who promote their survival.

Qu. 3.6a. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is likely to survive existing management practises during spread. The occurrence of *C. communis* is attributable to the adoption of glyphosate-resistant crops and the

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

concomitant use of glyphosate as the primary or sole strategy for weed control. Apparent natural tolerance to glyphosate and other biological characteristics contribute to the inability of growers to manage this weed effectively. Other herbicides used for weed control in soybean do not demonstrate high levels of efficacy against this weed. The best Asiatic dayflower control was provided by three timely applications of glyphosate, but sufficient escapes occurred, thus suggesting that the weed would increase in future prominence (Nandula 2005). Although there is no data on the effect of urbanisation on the spread of the species, small fragments of the plant may be moved through dumping which can facilitate spread.

Qu. 3.7a. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Being an unintentional way of spreading, is likely that the seeds of *C. communis* spread if the contaminated grains are used in agriculture.

Qu. 3.8a. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Transfer of the species into a suitable habitat is moderately likely. The species has been shown to occur in ruderal habitats and natural habitats. *C. communis* has become an weed of crop fields in some countries inside of the risk assesment area.

Qu. 3.9a. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (please provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no quantitative analysis on the spread of the species in the risk assessment area on this pathway.

Pathway name: (b): Horticulture (escape from confinement)

Qu. 3.3b. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	Unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Commelina communis* it was introduced in the risk assessment area as an ornamental species. There is no information about the current commercialization of the species as a living plant. Only a few internet sites that sell the seeds of this species have been identified.

Qu. 3.4b. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway
- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no quantitative information on the number of sales of the seeds in the risk assessment area or the numbers of sites where the species has been planted.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.5b. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is likely that *C. communis* seed will survive during transport and storage along this pathway. Seeds will be moved along the pathway and packaged to promote their survival.

It would not be possible for the species to reproduce or increase during transport and storage along this pathway. There is no detailed analysis on the viability of seed when are transported. The seeds are resilient and relative long-lived (Von Bernhardt et al. 2017). More than 80% of the seeds can germinate even after a few years in the soil seed bank (Takabayashi and Nakayama 1978).

Qu. 3.6b. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is likely to survive existing management practises during spread. Seeds or small fragments of the plant may be moved through dumping which can facilitate spread.

Qu. 3.7b. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Seeds or stem fragments may be spread via dumping waste and therefore may be spread in the risk assessment area undetected.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.8b. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Transfer of the species into a suitable habitat is likely. The species has been shown to occur in ruderal habitats. The presence of the species in urban and semi-urban habitats in the risk assessment area, including waste/abandoned lands highlights the species can transfer to a suitable habitat.

Dumping of plant material can increase the likelihood of transfer to a suitable habitat as material would be directly transferred.

Qu. 3.9b. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (please provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is a garden ornamental species which is not sold as living plant in the risk assessment area. Only seeds were detected as being sold on internet.

There is no quantitative analysis on the spread of the species in the risk assessment area. Via this pathway the species could be spread throughout the risk assessment area.

Pathway name: (c): Ornamental purpose other than horticulture (escape from confinement)

Qu. 3.3c. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

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RESPONSE	Unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is present in the risk assessment area as an ornamental species escape from cultivation. It is present in ruderal habitats (trash dumps, heaps of soil and construction waste etc.) and cultivated surfaces (gardens, olive groves, vineyards) (Tafra, et al. 2013; Maslo 2016; EPPO 2023)

Qu. 3.4c. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway
- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no quantitative information in the risk assessment area or the numbers of sites where the species has been planted. However, *C. communis* is not a popular ornamental species. The species may be dumped from waste garden material into the natural environment, though again, there are no details and the volume of movement or frequency.

Qu. 3.5c. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Plants can regenerate from a small piece of stem as long as a node is included, reproducing vegetatively through stem cuttings. Mature *C. communis* seeds easily fall on the ground and buried into the soil. These seeds form a massive seed bank. More than 80% of the seeds can germinate even after a few years in the soil seed bank (Takabayashi and Nakayama 1978, Mandák et al. 2012).

It is unlikely the plants will reproduce during their transport along this pathway.

Qu. 3.6c. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is likely to survive existing management practises during spread. Management of urban and semi-urban habitats is likely to increase disturbance of the habitat which the species prefers. Management practices may be minimal and the native vegetation sparse, this may make the survival of the species in these areas more likely.

Although there is no data on the effect of urbanisation on the spread of the species.

Qu. 3.7c. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Small stem fragments can produce a viable plant rooting adventitiously at the nodes. These fragments and seeds may be spread via dumping of garden waste and therefore may be spread in the risk assessment area undetected.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.8c. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* spread in ruderal habitats (train stations, cemeteries, pavements, wastelands, shady forest edges, crop fields, orchards, tree plantations ditches, and roadsides) and natural habitats (woods, marshes) within the risk assessment area. The presence of the species in urban and semi-urban habitats in the risk assessment area, including waste/abandoned lands highlights the species spread.

Qu. 3.9c. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (please provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no quantitative analysis on the spread of the species in the risk assessment area.

Pathway name: (d) Agriculture (escape from confinement)

Qu. 3.3d. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In its native area, *C. communis* is used as medicinal plant, vegetable and fodder crop. Recent studies have discovered the existence of numerous active compounds, *C. communis* becoming

more and more known as a medicinal plant. There is no information about its use in the risk assessment area.

Qu. 3.4d. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway
- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway.

Qu. 3.5b. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available about this subject.

Qu. 3.6d. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available

Qu. 3.7d. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available.

Qu. 3.8d. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available

Qu. 3.9d. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (provide quantitative data where possible).

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available

Qu. 3.10. Within the risk assessment area, how difficult would it be to contain the organism in relation to these pathways of spread?

RESPONSE	very easy easy with some difficulty difficult very difficult	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Natural spread would be difficult to control within the risk assessment area. The plant is propagated mainly by seeds. *C. communis* is known for its opportunistic germination throughout the growing season (Prostko and Webster 2007; GómezVargas 2012).

Also, Asiatic dayflower (*Commelina communis* L.) is a weed difficult to control with glyphosate and to most herbicides popularly used in maize and soybean field such as imazethapyr, acetochlor, fluroxypyr, glyphosate (Ma et al. 2009; Santiago and Micheal 2009).

Containing the spread via the following pathways will be difficult: Transport – seed contaminant and Ornamental purpose other than horticulture (escape from confinement).

The difficulty is associated with the large number of seeds that a plant can produce. Each *C. communis* plant can produce 500–1 000 seeds and can germinate even after a few years.

As the species can spread as a seed contaminant biosecurity measures and inspections would need to be adopted . This would involve multiple stakeholders and communication and awareness raising to reduce the spread pathways.

Preventing the spread from already established populations, including those in private gardens will be difficult.

Qu. 3.11. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread in relevant biogeographical regions under current conditions for this organism in the risk assessment area (indicate any key issues and provide quantitative data where possible).

Thorough assessment of the risk of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions, providing insight in the risk of spread into (new areas in) the risk assessment area.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In the risk assessment area, *C. communis* reproduces and spreads both by seeds and by vegetative reproduction. Therefore, spread by natural means can be assessed as rapidly.

Human mediated spread includes intentional movement of the species through Horticulture, Ornamental purposes other than horticulture (escape from confinement), Transport – seed contaminant, Agriculture. For human mediated spread, the rate of spread can be estimated as moderately. Spread would be highest in biogeographical regions where the species is already present, such as Alpine, Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Mediterranean and Black Sea biogeographical regions. A higher rate of spread may be seen in biogeographical regions where *C. communis* can be considered as established, e.g. Atlantic, Continental and Mediterranean biogeographical regions.

Qu. 3.12. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions (provide quantitative data where possible).

Thorough assessment of the risk of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk, specifically if rates of spread are likely slowed down or accelerated.

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: NA

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

4 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT

Important instructions:

- Questions 4.1-4.5 relate to biodiversity and ecosystem impacts, 4.6-4.8 to impacts on ecosystem services, 4.9-4.13 to economic impact, 4.14-4.15 to social and human health impact, and 4.16-4.18 to other impacts. These impacts can be interlinked, for example, a disease may cause impacts on biodiversity and/or ecosystem functioning that leads to impacts on ecosystem services and finally economic impacts. In such cases the assessor should try to note the different impacts where most appropriate, cross-referencing between questions when needed.
- Each set of questions starts with the impact elsewhere in the world, then considers impacts in the risk assessment area (=EU excluding outermost regions) separating known impacts to date (i.e. past and current impacts) from potential future impacts (including foreseeable climate change).
- Only negative impacts are considered in this section (socio-economic benefits are considered in Qu. A.7)
- In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable). Note that in principle, even if no information is available for the risk assessment area, this does not apply to Qu. 4.2 and 4.3, because the information on impact can be inferred from regions outside the risk assessment area. If no information is available from regions outside the risk assessment area either, then this should be discussed explicitly.

Biodiversity and ecosystem impacts

Qu. 4.1. How important is the impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation caused by the organism in its non-native range excluding the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

- Biodiversity means the variability among living organisms from all sources, including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems
- impacted chemical, physical or structural characteristics and functioning of ecosystems

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is recognized as an invasive alien plant in various parts of the world including North America (SUA) and Europe (Georgia, Italy, Lithuania, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey).

In Georgia, *C. communis* is an invasive species detected in areas of high conservation value (AHCV) (Slodowicz et al. 2018). Distribution models assessed species presence and showed predictions of the future distribution of 27 invasive plants. The actual filling area of *C. communis* in the AHCV is 28.8

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

% and varies up to 57.4 % in the predicted potential distribution of the species. The potential distribution of invasive plant species in Georgia varies widely among species, with the highest being 85.4%.

A major score is given due to the scale and importance of the impacts detailed above and a high confidence score is given because of the depth of literature in the invaded range.

Qu. 4.2. How important is the current known impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation (e.g. decline in native species, changes in native species communities, hybridisation) in the risk assessment area (include any past impact in your response)?

Discuss impacts that are currently occurring or are likely occurring or have occurred in the past in the risk assessment area. Where there is no direct evidence of impact in the risk assessment area (for example no studies have been conducted), evidence from outside of the risk assessment area can be used to infer impacts within the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The plant is invasive in some countries in the risk assessment area (Italy, Lithuania, Slovenia, Spain), but there is no published evidence that significant damage is occurring in areas that have already been invaded in the risk assessment area. Nonetheless a score of minimal with low confidence is given.

It lowers the biodiversity of the plant communities in which it settles, taking space away from native species; it also infests i edges of the rice fields (Banfi & Galasso 2010).

Qu. 4.3. How important is the potential future impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation likely to be in the risk assessment area?

See comment above. The potential future impact shall be assessed only for the risk assessment area. A potential increase in the distribution range due to climate change does not *per se* justify a higher impact score.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: NA

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 4.4. How important is decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the organism currently in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

- native species impacted, including red list species, endemic species and species listed in the Birds and Habitats directives
- protected sites impacted, in particular Natura 2000
- habitats impacted, in particular habitats listed in the Habitats Directive, or red list habitats
- the ecological status of water bodies according to the Water Framework Directive and environmental status of the marine environment according to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: NA

Qu. 4.5. How important is decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.3. and 4.4.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Decline in conservation values would be exhibited in the areas where the species is already established. In the absence of specific and detailed studies, the score is assessed as moderate with a low confidence.

Ecosystem Services impacts

Qu. 4.6. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services in its non-native range excluding the risk assessment area?

For a list of services use the CICES classification V5.1 provided in Annex V.

Impacts on ecosystem services build on the observed impacts on biodiversity (habitat, species, genetic, functional) but focus exclusively on reflecting these changes in relation to their links with

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

socio-economic well-being.

Quantitative data should be provided whenever available and references duly reported.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is an invasive and noxious weed found in gardens and crop fields in USA (corn, soybean, peanut and cotton fields) and Europe (Turkey). The plant has created extensive populations especially in the Eastern Black Sea region and can create significant problems in agricultural areas. The extensively invaded habitats were found in the agricultural areas such as tea plantations, hazelnut and kiwi orchards, mixed fruits and vegetables fields (Farooq & Akyol 2015).

The ecosystem services impact are significant and measurable and a moderate score is given with medium confidence.

Qu. 4.7. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services currently in the different biogeographic regions or marine sub-regions where the species has established in the risk assessment area (include any past impact in your response)?

See guidance to Qu. 4.6.

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue

Qu. 4.8. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services likely to be in the different biogeographic regions or marine sub-regions where the species can establish in the risk assessment area in the future?

See guidance to Qu. 4.6.

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	moderate major massive		
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Economic impacts

Qu. 4.9. How great is the overall economic cost caused by the organism within its current area of distribution (excluding the risk assessment area), including both costs of / loss due to damage and the cost of current management.

Where economic costs of / loss due to the organism have been quantified for a species anywhere in the world these should be reported here. The assessment of the potential costs of / loss due to damage shall describe those costs quantitatively and/or qualitatively depending on what information is available. Cost of / loss due to damage within different economic sectors can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage. As far as possible, it would be useful to separate costs of / loss due to the organism from costs of current management.

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.10. How great is the economic cost of / loss due to damage (excluding costs of management) of the organism currently in the risk assessment area (include any past costs in your response)?

Where economic costs of / loss due to the organism have been quantified for a species anywhere in the EU these should be reported here. Assessment of the potential costs of damage on human health, safety, and the economy, including the cost of non-action. A full economic assessment at EU scale might not be possible, but qualitative data or different case studies from across the EU (or third countries if relevant) may provide useful information to inform decision making. In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable). Cost of / loss due to damage within different economic sectors can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.11. How great is the economic cost of / loss due to damage (excluding costs of management) of the organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.10.

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.12. How great are the economic costs / losses associated with managing this organism currently in the risk assessment area (include any past costs in your response)?

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.13. How great are the economic costs / losses associated with managing this organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.12.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Social and human health impacts

Qu. 4.14. How important is social, human health or other impact (not directly included in any earlier categories) caused by the organism for the risk assessment area and for third countries, if relevant (e.g. with similar eco-climatic conditions).

The description of the known impact and the assessment of potential future impact on human health, safety and the economy, shall, if relevant, include information on

illnesses, allergies or other affections to humans that may derive directly or indirectly from a species;

damages provoked directly or indirectly by a species with consequences for the safety of people, property or infrastructure;

direct or indirect disruption of, or other consequences for, an economic or social activity due to the presence of a species.

Social and human health impacts can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.15. How important is social, human health or other impact (not directly included in any earlier categories) caused by the organism in the future for the risk assessment area.

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

GUVERNUL ROMÂNIEI

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No impacts are recorded in other more heavily invaded countries. There is no reason to assume that the social and human health impacts would increase significantly in the timescale under consideration.

Other impacts

Qu. 4.16. How important is the organism in facilitating other damaging organisms (e.g. diseases) as food source, a host, a symbiont or a vector etc.?

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* is host to U2- tobacco mosaic virus (Isaac et al. 2013) and brome mosaic virus (Valverde 1983) but none have been recorded in the risk assessment area so a minimal score is given.

Qu. 4.17. How important might other impacts not already covered by previous questions be resulting from introduction of the organism?

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.18. How important are the expected impacts of the organism despite any natural control by other organisms, such as predators, parasites or pathogens that may already be present in

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2014-2020

the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *C. communis* does not have any host specific natural enemies in the risk assessment area and there is no evidence that native organisms feed or infect the species in substantial levels to inflict any damage on the species.

Qu. 4.19. Estimate the overall impact in the risk assessment area under current climate conditions. In addition, details of overall impact in relevant biogeographical regions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the overall impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, with impacts on economy as well as social and human health as aggravating factors, in current conditions.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The overall current impact in the risk assessment area can only be scored as minimal due to the limited amount of reliable evidence but confidence in this score is low.

Qu. 4.20. Estimate the overall impact in the risk assessment area in foreseeable climate change conditions. In addition, details of overall impact in relevant biogeographical regions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the overall impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, with impacts on economy as well as social and human health as aggravating factors, under future conditions.

See also guidance to Qu. 4.3.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: NA

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RISK SUMMARIES			
	RESPONSE	CONFIDENCE	COMMENT
Summarise Introduction and Entry*	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	low medium high	
Summarise Establishment*	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	low medium high	
Summarise Spread*	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	low medium high	
Summarise Impact*	minimal minor moderate major massive	low medium high	
Conclusion of the risk assessment (overall risk)	low moderate high	low medium high	

*in current climate conditions and in foreseeable future climate conditions

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Distribution Summary

Please answer as follows:

- Yes if recorded, established or invasive
- if not recorded, established or invasive
- ? Unknown; data deficient

The columns refer to the answers to Questions A5 to A12 under Section A.

For data on marine species at the Member State level, delete Member States that have no marine borders. In all other cases, provide answers for all columns.

Member States

	Recorded	Established (currently)	Possible establishment (under current climate)	Possible establishment (under foreseeable climate)	Invasive (currently)
Austria	Yes	-			-
Belgium	Yes	-			-
Bulgaria	Yes	-			-
Croatia	Yes	-			-
Cyprus	-	-	-	-	-
Czech Republic	Yes	-			-
Denmark	Yes	-			-
Estonia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	-
Finland	Yes	-			-
France	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	-
Germany	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	-
Greece	Yes	-			-
Hungary	Yes	-			-
Ireland	-	-	-	-	-
Italy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Latvia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Lithuania	-	-	-	-	-
Luxembourg	-	-			-
Malta	-	-			-
Netherlands	Yes	-			-
Poland	Yes	-			-
Portugal	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Romania	Yes	Yes			-
Slovakia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Slovenia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Spain	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Sweden	-				-

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2014-2020

Biogeographical regions of the risk assessment area

	Recorded	Established (currently)	Possible establishment (under current climate)	Possible establishment (under foreseeable climate)	Invasive (currently)
Alpine	Yes	-			-
Atlantic	Yes	Yes			-
Black Sea	Yes	-			-
Boreal	Yes	-			-
Continental	Yes	Yes			-
Mediterranean	Yes	Yes			-
Pannonian	Yes	-			-
Steppic	-	-	-	-	-

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DIN ROMÂNIA

ANNEX I Scoring of Likelihoods of Events

(taken from UK Non-native Organism Risk Assessment Scheme User Manual, Version 3.3, 28.02.2005)

Score	Description	Frequency
Very unlikely	This sort of event is theoretically possible, but is never known to have occurred and is not expected to occur	1 in 10,000 years
Unlikely	This sort of event has occurred somewhere at least once in the last millenium	1 in 1,000 years
Moderately likely	This sort of event has occurred somewhere at least once in the last century	1 in 100 years
Likely	This sort of event has happened on several occasions elsewhere, or on at least once in the last decade	1 in 10 years
Very likely	This sort of event happens continually and would be expected to occur	Once a year

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ANNEX II Scoring of Magnitude of Impacts

(modified from UK Non-native Organism Risk Assessment Scheme User Manual, Version 3.3, 28.02.2005)

Score	Biodiversity and ecosystem impact	Ecosystem Services impact	Economic impact (Monetary loss and response costs per year)	Social and human health impact, and other impacts
	<i>Question 4.1-5</i>	<i>Question 4.6-8</i>	<i>Question 4.9-13</i>	<i>Question 4.14-18</i>
Minimal	Local, short-term population decline, no significant ecosystem impact	No services affected ⁷	Up to 10,000 Euro	No social disruption. Local, mild, short-term reversible effects to individuals.
Minor	Local, short-term population loss, Localized reversible ecosystem impact	Local and temporary, reversible effects to one or few services	10,000-100,000 Euro	Significant concern expressed at local level. Mild short-term reversible effects to identifiable groups, localised.
Moderate	Local to regional long-term population decline/loss, Measureable reversible long-term damage to ecosystem, little spread, no extinction	Measureable, temporary, local and reversible effects on one or several services	100,000-1,000,000 Euro	Temporary changes to normal activities at local level. Minor irreversible effects and/or larger numbers covered by reversible effects, localised.
Major	Long-term irreversible ecosystem change, spreading beyond local area, population loss or extinction of single species	Local and irreversible or widespread and reversible effects on one / several services	1,000,000-10,000,000 Euro	Some permanent change of activity locally, concern expressed over wider area. Significant irreversible effects locally or reversible effects over large area.
Massive	Long-term irreversible ecosystem change, widespread, population loss or extinction of several species	Widespread and irreversible effects on one / several services	Above 10,000,000 Euro	Long-term social change, significant loss of employment, migration from affected area. Widespread, severe, long-term, irreversible health effects.

⁷ Not to be confused with “no impact”.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ANNEX III Scoring of Confidence Levels

(modified from Bacher et al. 2017)

Each answer provided in the risk assessment must include an assessment of the level of confidence attached to that answer, reflecting the possibility that information needed for the answer is not available or is insufficient or available but conflicting.

The responses in the risk assessment should clearly support the choice of the confidence level.

Confidence level	Description
Low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g. only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence <i>and/or</i> Impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the assessment area <i>and/or</i> Evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g. because it is strongly ambiguous <i>and/or</i> The information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.
Medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred <i>and/or</i> Impacts are recorded at a small spatial scale, but rescaling of the data to relevant scales of the assessment area is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty <i>and/or</i> The interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.
High	There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment (including causality) <i>and</i> Impacts are recorded at a comparable scale <i>and/or</i> There are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa <i>and</i> The interpretation of data/information is straightforward <i>and/or</i> Data/information are not controversial or contradictory.

ANNEX IV CBD pathway categorisation scheme

Overview of CBD pathway categorisation scheme showing how the 44 pathways relate to the six main pathway categories. All of the pathways can be broadly classified into 1) those that involve intentional transport (blue), 2) those in which the taxa are unintentionally transported (green) and 3) those where taxa moved between regions without direct transportation by humans and/or via artificial corridors (orange and yellow). Note that the pathways in the category “Escape from confinement” can be considered intentional for the introduction into the risk assessment area and

unintentional for the entry into the environment.

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2014-2020

ANNEX V Ecosystem services classification (CICES V5.1, simplified) and examples

For the purposes of this risk assessment, please feel free to use what seems as the most appropriate category / level / combination of impact (Section – Division – Group), reflecting information available.

Section	Division	Group	Examples (i.e. relevant CICES “classes”)
Provisioning	Biomass	Cultivated <i>terrestrial</i> plants	Cultivated terrestrial plants (including fungi, algae) grown for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from cultivated plants, fungi, algae and bacteria for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Cultivated plants (including fungi, algae) grown as a <u>source of energy</u> <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to crops, orchards, timber etc.</i>
		Cultivated <i>aquatic</i> plants	Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown as an <u>energy source</u> . <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to aquatic plants cultivated for nutrition, gardening etc. purposes.</i>
		Reared animals	Animals reared for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from reared animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Animals reared to provide <u>energy</u> (including mechanical) <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to livestock</i>
		Reared <i>aquatic</i> animals	Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from animals grown by in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture as an <u>energy source</u> <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to fish farming</i>
		Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic)	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used for <u>nutrition</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used as a <u>source of energy</u> <i>Example: reduction in the availability of wild plants (e.g. wild berries, ornamentals) due to non-native organisms (competition, spread of disease etc.)</i>
		Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic)	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from wild animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used as a <u>source of</u>

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2014-2020

			<p><u>energy</u></p> <p><i>Example: reduction in the availability of wild animals (e.g. fish stocks, game) due to non-native organisms (competition, predations, spread of disease etc.)</i></p>
	Genetic material from all biota	Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi	<p><u>Seeds, spores and other plant materials</u> collected for maintaining or establishing a population;</p> <p>Higher and lower plants (whole organisms) used to <u>breed new strains or varieties</u>;</p> <p>Individual genes extracted from higher and lower plants for the <u>design and construction of new biological entities</u></p> <p><i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms due to interbreeding</i></p>
		Genetic material from animals	<p>Animal material collected for the purposes of maintaining or establishing a population;</p> <p>Wild animals (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties;</p> <p>Individual genes extracted from organisms for the design and construction of new biological entities</p> <p><i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms due to interbreeding</i></p>
	Water ⁸	Surface water used for nutrition, materials or energy	<p>Surface water for <u>drinking</u>;</p> <p>Surface water used as a material (<u>non-drinking purposes</u>);</p> <p>Freshwater surface water, coastal and marine water used as an <u>energy source</u></p> <p><i>Example: loss of access to surface water due to spread of non-native organisms</i></p>
		Ground water for used for nutrition, materials or energy	<p>Ground (and subsurface) water for <u>drinking</u>;</p> <p>Ground water (and subsurface) used as a material (<u>non-drinking purposes</u>);</p> <p>Ground water (and subsurface) used as an <u>energy source</u></p> <p><i>Example: reduced availability of ground water due to spread of non-native organisms and associated increase of ground water consumption by vegetation.</i></p>
Regulation & Maintenance	Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	<p><u>Bio-remediation</u> by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals; <u>Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation</u> by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals</p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem functioning and ability to filtrate etc. waste or toxics</i></p>
		Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	<p><u>Smell reduction; noise attenuation; visual screening</u> (e.g. by means of green infrastructure)</p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem structure, leading to reduced ability to mediate nuisances.</i></p>
	Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Baseline flows and extreme event regulation	<p>Control of <u>erosion</u> rates;</p> <p>Buffering and attenuation of <u>mass movement</u>;</p> <p><u>Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation</u> (Including flood control, and coastal protection);</p> <p><u>Wind</u> protection;</p> <p><u>Fire</u> protection</p>

⁸ Note: in the CICES classification provisioning of water is considered as an abiotic service whereas the rest of ecosystem services listed here are considered biotic.

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2014-2020

			<p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem functioning or structure leading to, for example, destabilisation of soil, increased risk or intensity of wild fires etc.</i></p>
		Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	<p><u>Pollination</u> (or 'gamete' dispersal in a marine context); <u>Seed dispersal</u>; Maintaining <u>nursery populations and habitats</u> (Including gene pool protection)</p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the abundance and/or distribution of wild pollinators; changes to the availability / quality of nursery habitats for fisheries</i></p>
		Pest and disease control	<p>Pest control; Disease control</p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the abundance and/or distribution of pests</i></p>
		Soil quality regulation	<p><u>Weathering processes</u> and their effect on soil quality; <u>Decomposition and fixing processes</u> and their effect on soil quality</p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to vegetation structure and/or soil fauna leading to reduced soil quality</i></p>
		Water conditions	<p>Regulation of the <u>chemical condition</u> of freshwaters by living processes; Regulation of the chemical condition of salt waters by living processes</p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to buffer strips along water courses that remove nutrients in runoff and/or fish communities that regulate the resilience and resistance of water bodies to eutrophication</i></p>
		Atmospheric composition and conditions	<p>Regulation of <u>chemical composition</u> of atmosphere and oceans; Regulation of <u>temperature and humidity</u>, including ventilation and transpiration</p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystems' ability to sequester carbon and/or evaporative cooling (e.g. by urban trees)</i></p>
Cultural	Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting	Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment	<p>Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through <u>active or immersive interactions</u>;</p> <p>Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through <u>passive or observational interactions</u></p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.) that make it attractive for recreation, wild life watching etc.</i></p>
		Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	<p>Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>scientific investigation</u> or the creation of traditional ecological knowledge;</p> <p>Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>education and training</u>;</p> <p>Characteristics of living systems that are resonant in terms of <u>culture or heritage</u>;</p> <p>Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>aesthetic experiences</u></p>

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2014-2020

			<i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.) that have cultural importance</i>
	Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	<p>Elements of living systems that have <u>symbolic meaning</u>;</p> <p>Elements of living systems that have <u>sacred or religious meaning</u>;</p> <p>Elements of living systems used for <u>entertainment or representation</u></p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.) that have sacred or religious meaning</i></p>
		Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	<p>Characteristics or features of living systems that have an <u>existence value</u>;</p> <p>Characteristics or features of living systems that have an <u>option or bequest value</u></p> <p><i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystems designated as wilderness areas, habitats of endangered species etc.</i></p>

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DIN ROMÂNIA

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ANNEX VI EU Biogeographic Regions and MSFD Subregions

See <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2> ,
http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/biogeog_regions/

and

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/msfd-regions-and-subregions-1/technical-document/pdf>

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DIN ROMÂNIA

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ANNEX VII Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/968 of 30 April 2018

see <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32018R0968>

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Phytolacca americana

**Risk assessment template developed under the the project POIM/178/4/1/120008
“Managementul adecvat al speciilor invazive din Romania, în conformitate cu Regulamentul UE
1143/2014 referitor la prevenirea și gestionarea introducerii și răspandirii speciilor alogene
invazive”**

Name of organism: *Phytolacca americana* L.

Author(s) of the assessment: *Paulina Anastasiu*

Risk Assessment Area: The risk assessment area is the territory of the European Union, excluding the outermost regions.

Date of completion: 20 iunie 2023

Date of revision:

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UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Contents

<u>SECTION A – Organism Information and Screening</u>	151
<u>SECTION B – Detailed assessment</u>	162
<u>1 PROBABILITY OF INTRODUCTION</u>	162
<u>2 PROBABILITY OF ENTRY</u>	177
<u>3 PROBABILITY OF ESTABLISHMENT</u>	188
<u>4 PROBABILITY OF SPREAD</u>	196
<u>Pathway name: Transport – stowaway: Machinery/ equipment</u>	198
<u>Pathway name: UNAIDED (natural spread)</u>	201
<u>Pathway name: Transport – contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation)</u>	203
<u>Pathway name: People and their luggage/ equipment (in particular tourism)</u>	206
<u>5 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT</u>	210
<u>Biodiversity and ecosystem impacts</u>	210
<u>Ecosystem Services impacts</u>	213
<u>Economic impacts</u>	215
<u>Social and human health impacts</u>	218
<u>Other impacts</u>	219
<u>RISK SUMMARIES</u>	222
<u>REFERENCES</u>	223
<u>Distribution Summary</u>	230
<u>ANNEX I Scoring of Likelihoods of Events</u>	232
<u>ANNEX II Scoring of Magnitude of Impacts</u>	233
<u>ANNEX III Scoring of Confidence Levels</u>	234
<u>ANNEX IV Ecosystem services classification (CICES V5.1, simplified) and examples</u>	234
<u>ANNEX V EU Biogeographic Regions and MSFD Subregions</u>	238
<u>ANNEX VI Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/968 of 30 April 2018</u>	239
<u>ANNEX VII Projection of climatic suitability for <i>Phytolacca americana</i> establishment</u>	240

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

SECTION A – Organism Information and Screening

A1. Identify the organism. Is it clearly a single taxonomic entity and can it be adequately distinguished from other entities of the same rank?

including the following elements:

the taxonomic family, order and class to which the species belongs;

the scientific name and author of the species, as well as a list of the most common synonym names;

names used in commerce (if any)

a list of the most common subspecies, lower taxa, varieties, breeds or hybrids

As a general rule, one risk assessment should be developed for a single species. However, there may be cases where it may be justified to develop one risk assessment covering more than one species (e.g. species belonging to the same genus with comparable or identical features and impact). It shall be clearly stated if the risk assessment covers more than one species, or if it excludes or only includes certain subspecies, lower taxa, hybrids, varieties or breeds (and if so, which subspecies, lower taxa, hybrids, varieties or breeds). Any such choice must be properly justified.

Response: It should be noted that the Flora of North America (http://www.efloras.org/florataxon.aspx?flora_id=1&taxon_id=220010427) detail that the “The infraspecific taxonomy of *Phytolacca americana* has been disputed since J. K. Small (1905) recognized *P. rigida* [*Phytolacca americana* var. *rigida* (Small) Caulkins & R.E. Wyatt, Bull. Torrey Bot. Club 117(4): 366 1990. basonym: *Phytolacca rigida* Small, Bull. New York Bot. Gard. 3(11): 422–423 1905] as distinct from *P. americana* on the basis of its "permanently erect panicles" [sic] and "pedicels...much shorter than the diameter of the berries." J. W. Hardin (1964b) separated *P. rigida* from *P. americana* by the length of the raceme (2-12 cm in *P. rigida*, 5-30 cm in *P. americana*) and the thickness and diameter of the xylem center of the peduncle (70% greater thickness in *P. rigida*, 17% greater diameter in *P. americana*), but he found no discontinuities in any feature. J. W. Nowicke (1968) and J. D. Sauer (1952), among others, treated *P. rigida* as a synonym of *P. americana*. Most recently, D. B. Caulkins and R. Wyatt (1990) recognized *P. rigida* as a variety of *P. americana*.”

Taxonomy:

Scientific name: *Phytolacca americana* L., Sp. Pl.: 441 (1753)

For this risk assessment (RA), *P. americana* s.l. (in the broad sense) is considered especially in view of a lack of distinguishing character states and such a distinction not being made in Europe.

Kingdom: Plantae; Phylum: Magnoliophyta; Class: Angiospermae; Order: Caryophyllales; Family: Phytolaccaceae Genus: *Phytolacca*

Synonyms:

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Phytolacca americana var. *americana* L. (autonym)

Phytolacca decandra L., Sp. Pl. ed. 2: 631 (1762)

Note: Other checklist databases detail other synonyms for *P. americana* such as *Phytolacca vulgaris* Bubani, *Phytolacca vulgaris* Crantz (Bock *et al.*, 2018).

English common names: American cancer, American nightshade, American pokeweed, American spinach, bears grape, cancer root, garget, inkberry, pigeonberry, poke, pokeberry, pokeroot, pokeweed, red-ink plant, stoke berry, Virginia poke.

Other languages: Albanian çapezë; Bulgarian американски лаконос, лаконос; Croatian američki kermes; Czech líčidlo americké; Danish asiatisk kermesbær; Dutc karmozijnbes, westerse karmozijnbes h; laque, French: phytolacca américain, phytolaque américaine, phytolaque d'Amérique, phytolaque à dix étamines, raisin d'Amérique; amerikanische Kermesbeere, Scharlachbeere, Schminkbeere German; Greek αγριοσταφίδα ή μαυροστάφυλο ; Hebrew fitolakah amerikanit; Hungarian amerikai alkörmös; Italian cremesina uva-turca, erba carmesina, fitolacca, uva d'America, uva da colorare; Polish szkarłatka amerykańska; Portuguese бага-ноива; erva-dos-cachos-de-índia, erva-dos-cancros, gaia-moça, tintureira, uva-da-américa, uva-dos-tintureiros, vermelhão, caruru-de-cacho, fruto-de-pombo, uva-de-tinta; Romanian cîrmîz; Russian лаконос американский; Serbian америчка винобоја, гроздасти кермес; Slovakian líčidlo americké;; Slovenian navadna barvilnica; Spanish carmesín de oblea, espinacas de América, fitolaca, grana encarnada, granilla, hierba carmín, tintilla, uvas de América, uvas de Indiasombú; Swedish amerikanskt kermesbär; Turkish şekerçiboyası Ukrainian лаконос американський

See also Euro+Med (2006).

Description of the species: *Phytolacca americana* is a polycarpic perennial herb (Armesto *et al.*, 1983) with a large white taproot which can reach 12 – 15 cm in diameter at ground level (Balogh & Juhász, 2008). The Flora of North America detail: 3 (-7) m in height. Leaves: petiole 1-6 cm; blade lanceolate to ovate, to 35 × 18 cm, base rounded to cordate, apex acuminate. Racemes open, proximal most pedicels sometimes bearing 2-few flowers, erect to drooping, 6-30 cm; peduncle to 15 cm; pedicel 3-13 mm. Flowers: sepals 5, white or greenish white to pinkish or purplish, ovate to suborbiculate, equal to subequal, 2.5-3.3 mm; stamens (9-)10(-12) in 1 whorl; carpels 6-12, connate at least in proximal 1/2; ovary 6-12-loculed. Berries purple-black, 6-11 mm diam. Seeds black, lenticular, 3 mm, shiny. $2n = 36$. Seeds can weigh 6.1 – 7.5 g/1000 seeds (Balogh & Juhász, 2008).

A2. Provide information on the existence of other species that look very similar [that may be detected in the risk assessment area, either in the environment, in confinement or associated

with a pathway of introduction]

Include both native and non-native species that could be confused with the species being assessed, including the following elements:

other alien species with similar invasive characteristics, to be avoided as substitute species (in this case preparing a risk assessment for more than one species together may be considered);

other alien species without similar invasive characteristics, potential substitute species;

native species, potential misidentification and mis-targeting

Response: The Manual of the Alien Plants of Belgium (2020) states: ‘*Phytolacca acinosa* (an emerging invasive species in the EU) is often confused with *P. americana* in Belgium. In fact many records of the latter doubtlessly belong to *Phytolacca acinosa*, by far the commonest representative of the genus in Belgium. *Phytolacca acinosa* always is a much smaller plant (rarely exceeding 100 cm) with an erect inflorescence and broader leaves. Moreover, at least in Belgium, it starts flowering much earlier: *Phytolacca acinosa* starts flowering from May onwards whereas *Phytolacca americana* does not flower before July’.

Verloove (2019) details that *P. acinosa* is an increasingly locally naturalised garden escape in Belgium. The species was first recorded in 1960 on a talus slope of the Albertkanaal in Kanne. From 1990 it has been recorded as an urban weed in many cities: Antwerpen, Brugge, Brussel, Gent, Izegem, Kortrijk, Leuven, Liège, Menen, Tielt, Tongeren occurring in gardens or parks in cemeteries or in urban wasteland. *P. acinosa* also occurs in Hungary as a non-native species (Balogh and Juhasz, 2008; Borak and Šoštarić, 2016). In Slovenia, *P. acinosa* has been recorded in 70 locations (LIFE Artemis Project, 2020). It is also present in Denmark (Hartvig, 2015). *P. polyandra* is locally naturalised in the British Isles (Clement & Foster 1994). *P. esculenta* is recorded as a casual alien plant in France (Tison & de Foucault, 2014).

In the horticultural trade within the risk assessment area plants traded as *Phytolacca rivinoides* and *Phytolacca latbenia* can be confused with *P. americana* especially the morphological similarity and the colour of the inflorescence. In addition, *Phytolacca acinosa* Roxb., and *Phytolacca polyandra* Batalin can be confused with *P. americana*.

Phytolacca americana may also be confused with the native species *Atropa belladonna* in the forest cuttings.

A3. Does a relevant earlier risk assessment exist? Give details of any previous risk assessment, including the final scores and its validity in relation to the risk assessment area.

Response: In Belgium, the species was evaluated in 2010 using the impact assessment protocol ISEIA <http://ias.biodiversity.be/species/show/111>. The species was scored 9, which means moderate impact. In Germany, the species was risk assessed and the species was included in the Grey List which means the species is classified as potentially invasive (Nehring et al., 2013).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

A4. Where is the organism native?

including the following elements:

an indication of the continent or part of a continent, climatic zone and habitat where the species is naturally occurring

if applicable, indicate whether the species could naturally spread into the risk assessment area

Response: *Phytolacca americana* is native to North America (including southeastern Canada, eastern the US and the northeast of Mexico) (Sauer, 1952; Rzedowski and Rzedowski, 2000). Its native range includes a little of southeastern Canada and almost the entire eastern half of the USA (Sauer, 1952). The species has however, spread westwards into other States and USDA (2019) detail the species present in: Alabama, Arkansas, Arizona, California, Connecticut, District of Columbia, Delaware, Florida, Georgia, Iowa, Illinois, Indiana, Kansas, Kentucky, Louisiana, Massachusetts, Maryland, Maine, Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, North Carolina, Nebraska, New Hampshire, New Jersey, New York, Ohio, Oklahoma, Pennsylvania, Rhode island, South Carolina, Tennessee, Texas, Virginia, Vermont, Wisconsin, and West Virginia (USDA, 2019; US NPGS, 2019). In Canada, the species is present in the Provinces: Brunswick, Ontario and Quebec. The spread of the species in North America is regarded as being greatly influenced by humans over the last few centuries (Sauer, 1952).

It is not possible for *P. americana* to naturally spread into the risk assessment area from its native range.

The species is native within a number of Köppen-Geiger climate zones including, the main zones of Hot-summer humid continental climate (Dfa), Warm-summer humid continental climate (Dfb), humid subtropical climate (Cfa), Hot-summer Mediterranean climate (Csa).

Regarding the habitat preference of the species in its native range, it is often abundant in open, disturbed habitats, as well as in forest edges and light gaps (Sauer 1952, cited by Armesto et al (1983)). Balogh & Juhasz (2008) describe in more details that “*In its native range Ph. americana primarily grows as a pioneer plant of disturbed and open surfaces of damp soiled forests (for example around badger’s burrows), on the fringe of forests and on riverbanks. Of the antropogeneous habitats it can be found on cuttings, waysides, fields and fallows. They prefer the eutrophic, flimsy, damp soils. It occurs rarely on sites where the temperature goes under –15 °C permanently in the winter, propagation is favourable if the average temperature is around 20 °C in July. In its native range it occurs at 1400 m of elevation.*”

A5. What is the global non-native distribution of the organism outside the risk assessment area?

Response: *Phytolacca americana* has been introduced into many regions of the world. In Asia it is common from Turkey to Iran, and present in India, China, Taiwan, Japan, and Indonesia (on Sumatra it was found on 1500 m a.s.l.) (Balogh and Juhasz, 2008). The species is cultivated in China and recorded in the following provinces (Anhui, Fujian, Guangdong, Guizhou, Hebei, Henan, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Shaanxi, Shandong, Sichuan, Taiwan, Yunnan, Zhejiang) (Flora of China, 2019). It has also been reported as invasive in China where it can become out of control in urban garden environments (Li *et al.*, 2016). The species is widely recorded in South Korea and considered

an invasive alien species (Kim *et al.*, 2008). In Japan, the species is reportedly present throughout the country and it is estimated that the species was originally introduced into the country around 1970 (NIES, 2019). In Israel the species was first recorded in 1898 (Dufour-Dror 2012). In Turkey, the species is present around the Black Sea region from Samsun to Sarp/Artvin where invaded habitats included forests, river banks, waste land, coastal regions, urban and along the edges of agricultural areas (Akyol *et al.*, 2015).

In the Oceania region, the species is non-native in Australia, where it is found in New South Wales and Queensland (Hewson, 1984). It is also present in New Zealand (Webb *et al.*, 1988).

In Africa, *P. americana* is an invasive non-native species in South Africa (Invasive species South Africa, 2019), where it is listed as a NEMBA Category 1b species (i.e. “invasive species that may not be owned, imported into South Africa, grown, moved, sold, given as a gift or dumped in a waterway”). It is recorded as being problematic in Mpumalanga (Invasive species South Africa, 2019). Q bank (2019) also list the species as present in Cape Verde, Democratic People's Republic of Congo, Liberia, Mauritius, Reunion and Swaziland. Interestingly, the species is listed on the A1 list since 2001 for East Africa (EPPO, 2019).

Q bank (2019) lists central and South American countries where *P. americana* is present including: Costa Rica. Bolivia, Ecuador and Uruguay. There are some reports that the species is present in the Galapagos Islands (Charles Darwin Foundation, 2019).

The species is present in Switzerland where it is listed on the Observation list of Invasive Alien Plants since 2013 (EPPO, 2019). The species is reported to have been introduced into Switzerland in the 1700s as an ornamental plant (FOEN, 2006). It is mostly distributed south of the Alps, but some occurrences are recorded in northern Switzerland. It is reportedly a ruderal species growing in waste ground, disturbed habitats, open woods, pastures and along roadsides and railways (FOEN, 2006).

The species is present in Serbia where it has been recorded in woodland habitats in Vojvodina (Krtivojević *et al.*, 2012). It has been recorded in Ukraine (Balogh and Juhasz, 2008). The species is recorded as being non-native in Albania (Balogh and Juhasz, 2008). Maslo (2016) details *P. americana* is present in Bosnia and Herzegovina where it was first recorded in 1908.

The species is recorded as naturalised in Georgia with 107 recorded occurrences (Slodowicz *et al.*, 2018).

The species occurs as a non-native species in Macaronesia (Invasoras, 2019). It is present in the Azores archipelago (all islands) and the Madeira archipelago (Madeira island) (Invasoras, 2019).

A6. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area has the species been recorded and where is it established? The information needs to be given separately for recorded and established occurrences.

A6a. Recorded: List regions

A6b. Established: List regions

Freshwater / terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic

Marine regions:

Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea

Marine subregions:

Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel, Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast, Western Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Central Mediterranean Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea.

Comment on the sources of information on which the response is based and discuss any uncertainty in the response.

For delimitation of EU biogeographical regions please refer to <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2> (see also Annex V).

For delimitation of EU marine regions and subregions consider the Marine Strategy Framework Directive areas; please refer to <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/msfd-regions-and-subregions/technical-document/pdf> (see also Annex V).

Response (6a):

terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic (based on GBIF data, 2019; Euro+Med, 2011).

Response (6b):

terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic (based on Euro+Med, 2011).

A7. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area could the species establish in the future under current climate and under foreseeable climate change?

The information needs to be given separately for current climate and under foreseeable climate change conditions.

A7a. Current climate: List regions

A7b. Future climate: List regions

With regard to EU biogeographic and marine (sub)regions, see above.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the risk assessment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response (7a): Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic (see Figure 8, species modelling Annex VII).

Response (7b): Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic. With climate change there is the potential that areas of the boreal biogeographical regions may become suitable for the establishment of the species. Areas of the Mediterranean may become more limited for the establishment of the species (see Figure 8, species modelling Annex VII).

It should however be noted that the SDM may over represent the potential establishment of the species in the natural environment within the RA area as the data taken from GBIF to perform the models would also include localities where the species has been planted.

A8. In which EU Member States has the species been recorded and in which EU Member States has it established? List them with an indication of the timeline of observations. The information needs be given separately for recorded and established occurrences.

A8a. Recorded: List Member States

A8b. Established: List Member States

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom

The description of the invasion history of the species shall include information on countries invaded and an indication of the timeline of the first observations, establishment and spread.

Response (8a): Recorded: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, United Kingdom (Euro+Med, 2011; and references below)

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response (8b): Established: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain (Euro+Med, 2011; and references below)

Further information on occurrence in EU Member States (where available):

Phytolacca americana was first recorded in Europe in the 17th century where its cultivation began around the Mediterranean Sea (South Europe and North Africa), due to planting of the species as a dye-plant since 1650 (Balogh and Juhasz, 2008). From 1770 it started to spread out from Bordeaux (France). In Europe, the species has been introduced into Austria, Belgium (not established, Verloove, 2019), Bulgaria (Petrova *et al.*, 2013), Cyprus, Croatia (Boršić *et al.*, 2008; Nikolić *et al.*, 2014; Nikolić, 2020), Czech Republic, France (Le Neindre, 2002; Chabrol *et al.*, 2007), including Corsica (Jeanmonod *et al.*, 2011), Germany (Nehring *et al.*, 2013), Greece (Arianoutsou *et al.*, 2010) including Crete, Hungary (Botta-Dukát and Mihály, 2006), Italy (Galasso *et al.*, 2008; Celesti-Grappo *et al.*, 2009) including Sardinia and Sicily, Netherlands (J. van Valkenburg, pers comm. 2019), Poland (Chmura 2016), Portugal (Invasive Plants in Portugal, 2019), Romania, Slovenia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Spain, UK (Stace, 2019). It should be noted, that in Belgium, there are increasing observations of the species, along with other *Phytolacca* species (e.g. *P. acinosa*) (Adriaens *et al.*, 2019). *P. americana* has been recorded in 841 locations in Slovenia (Source - Information system Invazivke (Life Artemis projects): <https://www.invazivke.si/> (May 29, 2020)). In Germany, the species was first introduced for horticulture between 1630-1651 (Nehring *et al.*, 2013).

Borbás mentioned in 1879 that it started to escape around gardens and hedges in Budapest (Hungary). Domokos (1937) writes about it as a frequent plant in the Mecsek-alja and along the Lower Danube already in the first half of the 20th century. Recent distribution in Hungary is South Transdanubia (mostly Belső-Somogy, West-Baranya), Duna-Tisza Interfluve (Budapest–Csévharaszt, to the south from Kecskemét) and Hajdúság (Téglás–Hajdúhadház). Balogh & Juhasz (2008) detail that recently its presence has been noticed in South-Mezőföld, but its smaller or bigger stands can be found in many other areas (for example eastern Vas County, Bakonyalja, Balaton-uplands, Gerecse, Külső-Somogy, Zselic).

A9. In which EU Member States could the species establish in the future under current climate and under foreseeable climate change? The information needs to be given separately for current climate and under foreseeable climate change conditions.

A9a. Current climate: List Member States

A9b. Future climate: List Member States

With regard to EU Member States, see above.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the risk assessment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response (9a): At present *P. americana* is established in Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, , France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain. It is envisaged that further establishment would be seen in these countries and other countries where the biogeographical regions are the same. Additional countries to the aforementioned would be Belgium, Estonia, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania and Luxembourg.

Response (9b): Under a climate change scenario of (RCP 4.5, over the next 30/50 years), countries in northern Europe may be suitable for the establishment of *P. americana* due to the increased temperature and the length of the growing season. Both increased summer and winter temperatures would benefit the species. Increased precipitation and CO2 levels as a result of climate change may also favor the species. These countries would include Denmark, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Finland, Sweden and the UK. See Annex VII for more details.

A10. Is the organism known to be invasive (i.e. to threaten or adversely impact upon biodiversity and related ecosystem services) anywhere outside the risk assessment area?

Response: In the USA, in Pennsylvania, which is outside of its native range, *P. americana* is reported as a frequent weed (i.e. invasive in cultivated areas) in corn and soybean crops (Patches *et al.*, 2017; Steckel, 2006)). The species is also reported as a common pasture weed in the USA (Kinningham, nd). Sellers *et al* (2006) highlights that the species can be poisonous to animals and can impact on hogs, sheep, cattle, horses and poultry.

It has also been reported as invasive in China where it can become out of control in urban garden environments (Li *et al.*, 2016) In China, in natural reserves in Jiangsu, *P. americana* threatens the survival of native plants such as *Emilia sonchifolia* and *Taraxacum mongolicum* (Dong *et al.*, 2011). The species is widely recorded in South Korea where it can invade coastal dune systems and has been designated as a harmful species because of its adverse effects on the ecosystem (Min 2014).

P. americana is an invasive non-native species in South Africa (Invasive species South Africa, 2019), where it is listed as a NEMBA Category 1b⁹ species. It is recorded as being problematic in Mpumalanga where it spreads into natural habitats (Invasive species South Africa, 2019).

A11. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area has the species shown signs of invasiveness? Indicate the area endangered by the organism as detailed

⁹ **Category 1b:** Invasive species requiring compulsory control as part of an invasive species control programme. Remove and destroy. These plants are deemed to have such a high invasive potential that infestations can qualify to be placed under a government sponsored invasive species management programme.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

as possible.

Freshwater / terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic

Marine regions:

Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea

Marine subregions:

Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel, Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast, Western Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Central Mediterranean Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea

Response: Alpine, Atlantic, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian.

The endangered area includes areas of forests, river banks, waste land, coastal regions, urban habitats and along the edges of agricultural areas within the aforementioned biogeographical regions

A12. In which EU Member States has the species shown signs of invasiveness? Indicate the area endangered by the organism as detailed as possible.

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom

Response: Croatia (Boršić *et al.*, 2008; Nikolić *et al.*, 2014), France (Dumas, 2011a), Germany (Schirmel, 2019), Hungary (Balogh and Juhasz, 2008), Italy (Acta plantarum, 2019), Poland (Chmura, 2016), Portugal (Invasoras, 2019), Romania (Szatmari, 2012), Spain (Sanz-Elorza *et al.*, 2001; Dana *et al.*, 2001), Slovenia (Kus Veenvliet *et al.* 2017).

The endangered area includes areas of forests, river banks, waste land, coastal regions, urban habitats and along the edges of agricultural areas within the aforementioned countries.

A13. Describe any known socio-economic benefits of the organism.

including the following elements:

Description of known uses for the species, including a list and description of known uses in the Union and third countries, if relevant.

Description of social and economic benefits deriving from those uses, including a description of the environmental, social and economic relevance of each of those uses and an indication of associated beneficiaries, quantitatively and/or qualitatively depending on what information is available.

If the information available is not sufficient to provide a description of those benefits for the entire risk assessment area, qualitative data or different case studies from across the Union or third countries shall be used, if available.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: *Phytolacca americana* has numerous medicinal uses, these include achy muscles and joints (rheumatism); swelling of the nose, throat, and chest; tonsillitis; hoarse throat (laryngitis); swelling of lymph glands (adenitis); swollen and tender breasts (mastitis); mumps; skin infections including scabies, tinea, sycosis, ringworm, and acne; fluid retention (edema), skin cancers, menstrual cramps (dysmenorrhea), and syphilis. See Paly *et al.*, (1994), Patra *et al* 2014 for examples of chemical compounds.

Research is undertaken on the properties of natural compounds produced by *Phytolacca americana* e.g. Cho *et al.* (2003), Getiya *et al.* (2011).

The leaves of *P. americana* can be eaten – though they must be cooked, and apparently, it is used like spinach. The root is also reported as edible, though it is the most toxic part of the plant.

A dye can be obtained from the fruit, which can be used as ink and a dye for clothes (Balogh & Juhasz (2008). The ink can be used as body paint which American native Indians used. There are reports that the dye has been used as a food coloring and as a wine coloring agent.

It is reported that the roots are rich in saponins, which can be used as a substitute for soap.

Such an array of uses may be the reason why the species has expanded from its native range in the USA to cover most of the United States (Sauer, 1952).

Balogh & Juhasz (2008) detail that *P. americana* can also be used for the coloration of foods such as preserved fruit and sweets.

RHS reports the species being available in the horticulture industry in 16 nurseries in UK, see: <https://www.rhs.org.uk/Plants/12895/i-Phytolacca-americana-i/Details>. The species is widely sold in the EU as a horticulture plant and this is historically the main entry pathway for the species. In Germany, the species is marketed as being attractive for ‘bees, bumblebees and other insects. (e.g. : <https://www.pflanzen-fuer-dich.de/de-de/artikel/3176/phytolacca-americana>).

In addition, Min *et al.* 2006 find that *P. americana* hyperaccumulate metal and may be used for phytoremediation

SECTION B – Detailed assessment

Important instructions:

In the case of lack of information the assessors are requested to use a standardized answer: “No information has been found.”

With regard to the scoring of the likelihood of events or the magnitude of impacts see Annexes I and II.

With regard to the confidence levels, see Annex III.

Highlight the selected response score and confidence level in bold but keep the other scores in normal text (so that the selected score is evident in the final document).

1 PROBABILITY OF INTRODUCTION

Important instructions:

Introduction is the movement of the species into the risk assessment area (it may be either in captive conditions and/or in the environment, depending on the relevant pathways).

Entry is the release/escape/arrival in the environment, i.e. occurrence in the wild and is treated in the next section (N.B. introduction and entry may coincide for species entering through pathways such as “corridor” or “unaided”).

The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD) should be used. For detailed explanations of the CBD pathway classification scheme consult the IUCN/CEH guidance document¹⁰ and the provided key to pathways¹¹.

For organisms which are already present in the risk assessment area, only complete this section for current active pathways and, if relevant, potential future pathways.

Qu. 1.1. List relevant pathways through which the organism could be introduced. Where possible give details about the specific origins and end points of the pathways as well as a description of any associated commodities.

For each pathway answer questions 1.2 to 1.7 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than one pathway, e.g. 1.2a, 1.3a, etc. and then 1.2b, 1.3b etc. for the next pathway.

In this context a pathway is the route or mechanism of introduction of the species.

The description of commodities with which the introduction of the species is generally associated

¹⁰ <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/738e82a8-f0a6-47c6-8f3b-aeddb535b83b/TSSR-2016-010%20CBD%20categories%20on%20pathways%20Final.pdf>

¹¹ <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/0aeba7f1-c8c2-45a1-9ba3-bcb91a9f039d/TSSR-2016-010%20CBD%20pathways%20key%20full%20only.pdf>

shall include a list and description of commodities with an indication of associated risks (e.g. the volume of trade; the likelihood of a commodity being contaminated or acting as vector).

If there are no active pathways or potential future pathways this should be stated explicitly here, and there is no need to answer the questions 1.2-1.9

Introduction pathways considered in this section are:

- Horticulture
- Transport – Contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation))
- Transport – stowaway (machinery/equipment)
- Pathway name: unaided
- People and their luggage/equipment (in particular tourism)

Pathway name: (1) Horticulture

Qu. 1.2a. Is introduction along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	Low medium high
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Response: Introduction via this pathway is deliberate, and planting of the species would be the end result of the movement of the species. *Phytolacca americana* is grown as a garden ornamental species within the RA area. The species is traded within the RA area.. The species is on sale on eBay and Amazon and suppliers can send seeds from Russia, USA, and Mexico. It is likely that the species is sold throughout the RA area as an ornamental species.

Qu. 1.3a. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in introduction whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely	CONFIDENCE	low
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	unlikely moderately likely likely very likely		medium high
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Response: *Phytolacca americana* is available through the horticultural trade both within the RA area and outside. The species is available via internet suppliers (e.g. Amazon.com and ebay.com) but it remains unclear if the species can be sent to buyers within the EU from outside.

By definition, both seeds and whole plants could enter the RA area via plants for planting.

As entry via this pathway is deliberate, and planting of the species would be the end result of the movement of the species low numbers of propagules could result in the entry of the species.

A medium confidence is given which reflects the known introduction of the species but there are still gaps in the knowledge, i.e. if the species is continually introduced into the RA area for horticulture.

Qu. 1.4a. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The pathway 'Horticulture' is the deliberate movement of plant material into the risk assessment area and as such plant material would be maintained and moved to ensure survival. No management practices would be carried out along this pathway.

It is unlikely that the species will reproduce or increase along the pathway. Both seed and live plants could be moved along this pathway.

Qu. 1.5a. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low medium high
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Response: No management practices would be carried out along this pathway.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 1.6a. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is unlikely that the organism will enter the risk assessment area undetected via the pathway ‘Horticulture (escape from confinement)’ is the deliberate movement of plant material into the risk assessment area. Any plant material imported into the EU should be accompanied with a Phytosanitary Certificate. Therefore, a high confidence is given.

Qu. 1.7a. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Phytolacca americana* is available through the horticultural trade both within the PRA area and outside. The species is available via internet suppliers (e.g. Amazon.com and ebay.com) but it remains unclear if the species can be sent to buyers within the EU from outside, hence a medium confidence score. Therefore, based on the latter, a medium rating of uncertainty has been given.

(2) Pathway name: Transport – Contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation))

Qu. 1.2b. Is introduction along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Entry via this pathway is unintentional movement of the species via the contamination of habitat material (soil and vegetation).

Qu. 1.3b. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced through this

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in introduction whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The transport of topsoil and or other contaminated material with seed of the species can facilitate entry into the RA area. However, the pathway is mainly closed within the RA as there are prohibitions of the movement of soil into the EU from many countries. The lack of data associated with this pathway is reflected by a low confidence.

Qu. 1.4b. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The pathway Transport – Contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation) is the unintentional movement of plant material into the risk assessment area. As the seed would be moved with soil it is likely that they would survive during passage.

It is unlikely that the plant will multiply along the pathway

Seeds would be the most likely plant parts for transport, rather than whole plant parts. Seeds can remain dormant within a seed bank for a number of years. Therefore, habitat material collected from the natural environment may potentially contain viable seeds. For example, Michigan State University (2020) report seeds can remain viable in the seedbank for up to 50 years and Sellers et al (2019) detail 40 years). However, the aforementioned figures are likely to be the extreme. Hyatt and Casper (2000) showed in a forest gap in the USA, 46 % of *P. americana* seeds were viable in the soil for at least a year.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Seed viability under controlled (artificial) conditions may be significantly lower compared to the seedbank. USDA Forest Service (1970) showed that after 5 months of storage under different conditions, germination was 8 % (at room temperature), 0 % at 42 °F (5 °C) (in air), 54 % in wet sand and 68 % in sphagnum moss at 5 °C.

Qu. 1.5b. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Soil is unlikely to be treated as it is moved through the pathway and as such plant material would survive. Thus, a low rating of confidence has been given.

Qu. 1.6b. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is likely that the organism will enter the risk assessment area undetected as seeds will be hidden in soil and may not be detected. The lack of data associated with this pathway is reflected by a low confidence.

Qu. 1.7b. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: The entry of *P. americana* via the pathway: Transport – Contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation) has a moderately likelihood. The species can remain undetected within soil and other habitat material but the pathway remains closed for soil within EU countries (e.g. importation of soil and growing medium as such is prohibited in the EU, and is regulated when associated with plants (Regulation (EU) 2019/2072)). The lack of data associated with this pathway is reflected by a low confidence.

(3) Pathway name: Transport – stowaway (machinery/equipment)

Qu. 1.2c. Is introduction along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Entry via this pathway is unintentional movement of the species via machinery and equipment.

Qu. 1.3c. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in introduction whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Machinery and equipment used for forestry and agricultural purposes may include seeds of *P. americana* attached within tyre treads or other areas of machinery and equipment where soil is also attached.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

There is no evidence that the species has entered the RA area via this pathway and there is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. However, as in areas where the species is present, the seed bank density can be high, and thus there is a potential for seeds to become attached to tires of vehicles. Dumas (2011), when considering spread, highlight that ‘the transport of seeds by the soil retained in the tread pattern of machine tires is a ‘hypothesis that we cannot exclude’. Thus, it should also be considered for movement into the RA area.

The lack of data associated with this pathway is reflected by a low confidence.

Qu. 1.4c. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species is unlikely to reproduce along this pathway. But as the seeds are small the species can survive along the pathway. See Qu.1.4b for details on the viability of the seeds.

Qu. 1.5c. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: If following cleaning methods suggested in ISPM 41 (FAO, 2017), removing debris or filters - abrasive blasting - pressure washing - steam cleaning - sweeping and vacuuming - compressed air cleaning, potential survival of the species should be considered as low. However, it is not known if all machinery/equipment introduced followed all the steps of the ISPM 41

Qu. 1.6c. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	very likely		
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Response: Seeds are small and therefore they can remain undetected within crevices of used machinery.

Qu. 1.7c. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Based on international Standards and requirements within (ISPM 41: FAO, 2017), the entry of *P. americana* as a hitchhiker of used machinery is moderately likely. However, incorrect application of the cleaning of machinery could lead to the entry of seed via this pathway. In addition, volumes of movement of used machinery into the RA area is not known and therefore the uncertainty is scored low, in part to reflect this.

(4) Pathway name: unaided

Qu. 1.2d. Is introduction along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Entry via this pathway is pathway is the unintentional movement of the species into the risk assessment area. This pathway would cover the movement of the species from areas where it is non-native, into the risk assessment area (for example Serbia into the EU).

Unaided introduction is most likely to be via dispersal of birds which feed on the berries and disperse the seeds across borders. Sauer (1952) report that the species is poorly suited to dispersal by wind or water.

Qu. 1.3d. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in introduction whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Within the RA area, Balogh and Juhasz (2008) detail the following bird species feeding on fruits in the following countries: in Italy: blackcap (*Sylvia atricapilla*), whitethroat (*Sylvia communis*), song thrush (*Turdus philomelos*), blackbird (*Turdus merula*), blue rock thrush (*Monticola solitarius*), robin (*Erithacus rubecula*); in South France: robin and blackcap; in New-Zealand: the pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus*). Villemenot & Mischler (2012) list several bird species eating fleshy berries as responsible of *P. americana* spread: pigeons (*Columba* spp.), turtledoves (*Streptopelia decaocto*) and starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*), but also probably blackbirds (*Turdus merula*), thrushes (*Turdus* spp.) and warblers (*Sylvia* spp.).

There is no data available on the volumes or number of individuals or frequency of movement along this pathway. However, it is not expected that large numbers of *P. americana* will be introduced via this pathway into the RA area.

Only a small number of viable seeds would be enough to support an introduction.

Qu. 1.4d. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The germination of seed is increased when the seed moves through a bird digestive tract (Dumas, 2011). It is noted that, 'Orrock (2005) studied the influence that can have the transit of seeds in the digestive tract of birds where a positive effect on the germination rate, which goes from 67% for controls to 88% for seeds from the fruits consumed'.

Qu. 1.5a. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during transport and storage along the pathway?

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is likely that *P. americana* can survive existing management practices during movement along this pathway. *P. americana* is suited to disturbed habitats especially disused waste ground. It is therefore likely that the current urbanization trend occurring in Europe may favor the establishment of the species. Additionally, management practices in forests, may act to open the canopy and favour disturbance that would be beneficial for the germination of the seedbank. Birds can also disperse the seeds widely throughout the risk assessment area.

Qu. 1.6d. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is very likely that *P. americana* will be introduced into the risk assessment area undetected along this pathway as the seeds will be inside a birds gut.

Qu. 1.7d. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is likely the species will be introduced into the risk assessment area based on this pathway but a low confidence highlights the lack of data and the large unknown on the volumes of seed moved along this pathway.

(5) People and their luggage/equipment (in particular tourism)

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2014-2020

Qu. 1.2e. Is introduction along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Introduction via this pathway is for this species considered the unintentional movement of the species via seeds. In the sense of this pathway, the main risk is of introduction into new areas by the species (seeds) being incorporated into the tread of hiking boots or other equipment and moved accidentally to other areas.

This movement would relate from the introduction of the species from a non- EU country (e.g. Serbia, into an EU county).

Qu. 1.3e. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in introduction whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. As the fruit of the species does not have any spiny spurs there is a low chance of the fruits attaching to clothes and other material.

Qu. 1.4e. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely	CONFIDENCE	low
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	unlikely moderately likely likely very likely		medium high
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Response: The seeds of the species are small and therefore they could survive during transport along this pathway. The substrate would be conducive to maintain survival. The species would not reproduce along this pathway or increase.

Qu. 1.5e. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Careful methodical management practices coupled with inspection of tread on boots would be needed to ensure that the species is not introduced into the RA area. However, often biosecurity measures are not widely known by the general public.

Qu. 1.6e. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The seeds are relatively small and potentially can remain undetected within the tread of hiking boots. Additionally, the seeds may not be easily identifiable to non-botanists and thus may be overlooked.

Qu. 1.7e. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no data on the movement of the species along this pathway and there is no information if the seeds can maintain being adhered to the tread of hiking boots for long periods of time.

Qu. 1.8. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area based on all pathways and specify if different in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions.

Provide a thorough assessment of the risk of introduction in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions: providing insight in to the risk of introduction into the Union.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: When considering all pathways into the RA area, it is likely that *P. americana* can enter the RA area with a medium confidence. All biogeographical regions would have similar likelihood scores based on the pathways described.

Qu. 1.9. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area based on all pathways in foreseeable climate change conditions?

Thorough assessment of the risk of introduction in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

- the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)
- the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)
- what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the likelihood of introduction (e.g. change in trade or user preferences)

The thorough assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment of likely introduction within a medium timeframe scenario (e.g. 30-50 years) with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	likely very likely		
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Response: Within the next 30/50 years, under the medium climate change prediction (RCP 5.5), there is an overall likely score that *P. americana* will enter the RA area with a medium confidence. As this question is only considering introduction into the RA area, all biogeographical regions would have similar likelihood scores based on the pathways described. Climate change is unlikely to change the current pathways but it may extend the areas where the species can be grown to the north and restrict the areas where the species may grow in the Mediterranean region, i.e. regions where someone could introduce it for planting could change accordingly

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

2 PROBABILITY OF ENTRY

Important instructions:

Entry is the release/escape/arrival in the environment, i.e. occurrence in the wild. Entry is not to be confused with spread, the movement of an organism within the risk assessment area.

The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD) should be used. For detailed explanations of the CBD pathway classification scheme consult the IUCN/CEH guidance document¹² and the provided key to pathways¹³.

For organisms which are already present in the risk assessment area, only complete this section for current active or if relevant potential future pathways. This section need not be completed for organisms which have entered in the past and have no current pathway of entry.

Qu. 2.1. List relevant pathways through which the organism could enter into the environment.

For each pathway answer questions 2.2 to 2.7 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than one pathway, e.g. 2.2a, 2.3a, etc. and then 2.2b, 2.3b etc. for the next pathway.

In this context a pathway is the route or mechanism of entry of the species into the environment.

If there are no active pathways or potential future pathways this should be stated explicitly here, and there is no need to answer the questions 2.2-2.8

Entry pathways considered in this section are:

- (1) Horticulture (escape from confinement).
- (2) Release in nature for use
- (3) Transport – Contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation)
- (4) Transport – stowaway (machinery/equipment)

Pathway name: (1) Horticulture (escape from confinement).

Qu. 2.2a. Is entry into the environment intentional (e.g. the organism is released for a specific purpose) or unintentional (e.g. the organism escapes from a confinement)?

¹² <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/738e82a8-f0a6-47c6-8f3b-aeddb535b83b/TSSR-2016-010%20CBD%20categories%20on%20pathways%20Final.pdf>

¹³ <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/0aeba7f1-c8c2-45a1-9ba3-bcb91a9f039d/TSSR-2016-010%20CBD%20pathways%20key%20full%20only.pdf>

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The pathway is the escape of the species from horticulture into the natural environment. Thus, this in its strictest definition would be an unintentional occurrence of the species in the environment outside of cultivation.

RHS reports the species being available in 16 nurseries in UK, see:
<https://www.rhs.org.uk/Plants/12895/i-Phytolacca-americana-i/Details>

This pathway also involves the dumping of garden waste which may include *P. americana* plant parts (seeds or root fragments).

Qu. 2.3a. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will enter into the environment along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of entry into the environment based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in entry whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information on the volumes of movement along this entry pathway. A single plant can produce over 2 500 fruits and 25 000 seeds (Dumas 2011).

These fruit can be eaten by birds and seeds transferred from the confines of a garden into the wild of the RA area (Li et al., 2016). In addition, the species can grow to reasonable heights and potentially overhang garden fences and walls where it can release fruit into the natural environment.

If eradication measures are taken following dumping, there is the potential that the species can re-establish if it is dumped again. As one plant can produce up to 25000 seeds, only a small population is needed to result in subsequent establishment.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 2.4a. How likely is the organism to enter into the environment within the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Fruit/seeds can enter the risk assessment area from garden sources and can remain undetected until they germinate and grow. Seeds can remain viable in the seed bank for a long period of time (DiTomaso et al., 2013).

The species can enter the natural environment via the dumping of garden waste. If plant waste has mature berries this would increase the likelihood. One plant can produce up to 25 000 seeds, large numbers of propagules can enter the natural environment as a result of a single dumping of one plant, if the plant contains material that contain viable seeds. *Phytolacca americana* can grow in dense stands where numerous plants would be managed and controlled and potentially dumped.

Qu. 2.5a. How likely is the organism to enter into the environment during the months of the year most appropriate for establishment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Seeds would enter the environment during summer and autumn months and the seeds be included in the soil and remain viable in a seed bank. These times would also be the time that most management of gardens is occurring.

Qu. 2.6a. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host in the environment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: As previously mentioned, the fruit/seeds can be moved via birds and other entry pathways including small mammals and also via dropping seeds over walls or garden fences from plants

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

contained within gardens. Dumping of garden waste would potentially place viable seeds directly in a suitable habitat.

Qu. 2.7a. Estimate the overall likelihood of entry into the environment within the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is very likely that the species can enter the environment within the risk assessment area based on the pathway Horticulture (escape from confinement).

Pathway name: (2) Release in nature for use

Qu. 2.2b. Is entry into the environment intentional (e.g. the organism is released for a specific purpose) or unintentional (e.g. the organism escapes from a confinement)?

RESPONSE	Intentional Unintentional	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: *Phytolacca americana* can be used for a number of purposes, especially medical purposes including use for achy muscles and joints (rheumatism); swelling of the nose, throat, and chest; tonsillitis; hoarse throat (laryngitis); swelling of lymph glands (adenitis); swollen and tender breasts (mastitis); mumps; skin infections including scabies, tinea, sycosis, ringworm, and acne; fluid retention (edema), skin cancers, menstrual cramps (dysmenorrhea), and syphilis. In addition, the species can be used as a food plant.

This entry pathway deals with the release of the species in nature for use other than horticulture. This would and would involve the deliberate planting of the species for utilization as detailed above.

Qu. 2.3b. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will enter into the environment along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules,

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

GVERNUL ROMÂNIEI

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication if relevant, comment on the likelihood of entry into the environment based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in entry whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The species would be deliberately planted within the environment. It is not expected that large numbers would enter the environment via this pathway mainly as the species is only likely to be used as a medical or food plant by a very limited number of the population within EU Member States.

Qu. 2.4b. How likely is the organism to enter into the environment within the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The species would be deliberately planted within the environment.

Qu. 2.5b. How likely is the organism to enter into the environment during the months of the year most appropriate for establishment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The species would be deliberately planted within the environment. Seeds would most likely be planted during the spring and summer months and the seeds be included in the soil and remain viable in a seed bank.

Qu. 2.6b. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

habitat or host in the environment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The species would be deliberately planted within the environment and it is very likely that those people who plant the species would be planting it in habitats that are suitable for its growth.

Qu. 2.7b. Estimate the overall likelihood of entry into the environment within the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: It is moderately likely that the species can enter the environment within the risk assessment area based on the pathway release in nature for use. The overall score is lower than that for horticulture escape from confinement as the use of the species for medicinal purposes or as a food plant would be considerably lower than that for horticulture use.

Pathway name: (3) Transport – Contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation))

Qu. 2.2c. Is entry into the environment intentional (e.g. the organism is released for a specific purpose) or unintentional (e.g. the organism escapes from a confinement)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The pathway is the entry of the species as a contaminant of habitat material (soil or vegetation) into the natural environment. Thus, this is the unintentional occurrence of the species in the environment.

Qu. 2.3c. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will enter into the environment along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of entry into the environment based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in entry whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: There is no information on the volumes of movement along this entry pathway. As the pathway is mainly closed within EU Member States, the likelihood is only moderately likely with a low uncertainty.

Qu. 2.4c. How likely is the organism to enter into the environment within the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: Seeds can enter the environment as a contaminant undetected as they are small and may be hidden in habitat material.

Qu. 2.5c. How likely is the organism to enter into the environment during the months of the year most appropriate for establishment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: Such material could enter the environment at any time of the year and seeds can be long lived and can remain viable for up to 50 years (UC Weed Science, 2018) .

Qu. 2.6c. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host in the environment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The material relevant to this pathway is habitat material (soil or vegetation) and as such this material could be deliberately placed in a suitable habitat within the environment where the seed contaminants could enter the environment.

Qu. 2.7c. Estimate the overall likelihood of entry into the environment within the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: It is moderately likely that the species can enter the environment within the risk assessment area based on this pathway.

Pathway name: (4) Transport – stowaway (machinery/equipment)

Qu. 2.2d. Is entry into the environment intentional (e.g. the organism is released for a specific purpose) or unintentional (e.g. the organism escapes from a confinement)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The pathway is the entry of the species as a stowaway of machinery/equipment into the natural environment. Thus, this is the unintentional occurrence of the species in the environment.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 2.3d. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will enter into the environment along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of entry into the environment based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in entry whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: There is no information on the volumes of movement along this entry pathway. There is also no information on the volumes of movement of used machinery/equipment from outside the RA area into the RA area. Used equipment and machinery may enter the risk assessment area for a number of purposes including forest management and industrial machinery for major infrastructure renovations.

As detailed in the response to Qu. 1.3.c, movement along this pathway has been considered for spread and it is also possible for the movement from non-EU countries bordering EU countries.

Qu. 2.4d. How likely is the organism to enter into the environment within the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: Seeds are small and can remain undetected within crevices of used machinery. Without proper cleaning of equipment at source, or before it enters the environment, it is likely that seed can remain as a contaminant of used machinery

Qu. 2.5d. How likely is the organism to enter into the environment during the months of the year most appropriate for establishment?

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: Used equipment, especially equipment used for forestry management etc. could enter the environment at any time of the year and seeds are long lived and can remain viable for a number of years.

Qu. 2.6d. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host in the environment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: Used equipment, especially equipment used for forestry management etc. could be deliberately placed in a suitable habitat within the environment where the seed hitchhikers could enter the environment.

Qu. 2.7d. Estimate the overall likelihood of entry into the environment within the risk assessment area based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is moderately likely that the species can enter the environment within the risk assessment area based on this pathway.

Qu. 2.8. Estimate the overall likelihood of entry into the environment within the risk assessment area based on all pathways in current conditions and specify if different in relevant biogeographical regions.

Provide a thorough assessment of the risk of entry into the environment in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: When considering all pathways into the RA area, it is likely that *P. americana* can enter the environment within the RA area with a high confidence. All biogeographical regions would have similar likelihood scores based on the pathways described.

Qu. 2.9. Estimate the overall likelihood of entry into the environment within the risk assessment area based on all pathways in foreseeable climate change conditions and specify if different in relevant biogeographical regions.

Thorough assessment of the risk of entry in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk, specifically if likelihood of entry is likely to increase or decrease for specific pathways.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: When considering all pathways into the RA area, it is likely that *P. americana* can enter habitats within the RA area with a high confidence. Climate change may extend the areas where the species can be grown to the north and restrict the areas where the species may grow in the Mediterranean region. Both increased summer and winter temperatures would benefit the species. Increased precipitation and CO2 levels as a result of climate change may also favor the species. All biogeographical regions would have similar likelihood scores based on the pathways described.

3 PROBABILITY OF ESTABLISHMENT

Important instructions:

For organisms which are already established in parts of the risk assessment area, answer the questions with regard to those areas, where the species is not yet established.

Qu. 3.1. How likely is it that the organism will be able to establish in the risk assessment area based on the history of invasion by this organism elsewhere in the world (including similarity between other abiotic conditions within it and the organism's current distribution)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: *Phytolacca americana* is already established within the RA area (Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Malta, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain). It is likely that further areas of establishment are present within the RA area.

In its native range, the species is established in Köppen-Geiger climate zones of Dfa, Dfb, Cfa, Csa. All of these Köppen-Geiger climate zones are present within the EU and the habitats where the species can persist are present throughout the RA area.

Species modelling shows that *P. americana* has the potential to establish over much of the European Union, see Annex VII.

Qu. 3.2. How widespread are habitats or species necessary for the survival, development and multiplication of the organism in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very isolated isolated moderately widespread widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: Balogh and Juhasz (2008) detail that *P. americana* is mostly a ruderal species growing in disturbed habitats. The species is able to grow in both sunny and shady sites. In its native range, *P. americana* primarily grows as a pioneer plant of disturbed and open surfaces of damp soiled forests (for example around badger's burrows), on the fringe of forests and on riverbanks. Of the anthropogenic habitats it can be found in cuttings, waysides, fields and fallows. The species prefer the eutrophic, flimsy, damp soils. It occurs rarely on sites where the temperature goes under -15°C

permanently in the winter, propagation is favourable if the average temperature is around 20 °C in July. In its native range it occurs up to 1400 m of elevation.

Within the Europe, the species occurs in clear-cut areas (for example in Austria, Lajta hills), and along hedgerows and wasteland (e.g. in Switzerland). Balogh and Juhasz (2008) report that in Italy it can be found on field sides, along canals, along the coast, and in black locust plantations. The species is found in forest plantations in Hungary and in disturbed woodlands. In addition, in Hungary, the species is found in sandy grassland and alder swamp forests that has no surface water. It prefers the more humid habitats, and the half-shade; on sunny sites it grows usually under shrubs or trees. Balogh and Juhasz (2008) highlight that the species generally favours loose soils that developed on acidic or neutral, sandy or pebble bedrock. Dumas (2011) detail that the species can also grow on limestone, the edges of streams. In France, the species can be found in riparian habitats, clearings and forest edges, near dwellings, in wastelands, railway stations, old quarries, rubble, and corn crops (Fried, 2017). It prefers sandy and / or humus soils.

In the EU, the species can be found growing in uncultivated vineyards, orchards, and arable fields and row crop cultures (paprika, tomato, sunflower) (Balogh and Juhasz,2008). The species is often found growing within urban areas where it can form dense stands if the land is left unmanaged.

The species has been recorded in natural habitats, in particular in Carei Plain Natural protected area in Western Romania where it is reported to occur in natural and planted forests and anthropogenically affected areas (Szatmari, 2012).

Many Slovene forests have been severely damaged by ice-storm, wind-throws and bark-beetle attacks since 2014. In disturbed forests *P. americana* formed great and dense stands very quickly. It spreads also very fast under power lines and from there to the forests. It has been detected also in corn fields and meadows. (Information system Invazivke (Life Artemis projects): <https://www.invazivke.si/> (May 29, 2020))

All of the aforementioned habitats are widespread within the RA area.

Qu. 3.3. If the organism requires another species for critical stages in its life cycle then how likely is the organism to become associated with such species in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	N/A	CONFIDENCE	
	very unlikely		low
	unlikely		medium
	moderately likely		high
	likely		
	very likely		

Response: *Phytolacca americana* does not require another species for any critical stage in its lifecycle.

Qu. 3.4. How likely is it that establishment will occur despite competition from existing species

in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It is very likely that *P. americana* will establishment despite competition from existing species (Dumas, 2011a/b). *P. americana* is highly competitive species which has been shown to successfully outcompete native plant species within the RA area. The ability of the species to form dense monocultures, coupled with the lack of natural enemies provides the species with an advantage over native species (Dumas, 2011a/b).

Qu. 3.5. How likely is it that establishment will occur despite predators, parasites or pathogens already present in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	N/A very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Phytolacca americana* is native to North America and thus co-evolved natural enemies would be present in this region and not within the risk assessment area. Those more generalist organisms naturally present in the risk assessment area, which might feed on the species, are unlikely to prevent the establishment of the species.

Qu. 3.6. How likely is the organism to establish despite existing management practices in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There are a number of management practices applied to *P. americana* within the risk assessment area (see management annex for this species). However, these management practices are mainly applied to established populations or where populations may start to establish in areas of high conservation value. Other areas, such as ruderal habitats may be overlooked and therefore provide habitats for establishment despite existing management practices.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.7. How likely are existing management practices in the risk assessment area to facilitate establishment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: As detailed in section (3.2), the establishment of *P. americana* is suited to disturbed habitats especially disused waste ground. It is therefore likely that the current urbanization trend occurring in Europe may favor the establishment of the species. Additionally, management practices in forests, or maintenance of power lines, may act to open the canopy and favour disturbance that would be beneficial for the germination of the seedbank.

Qu. 3.8. How likely is it that biological properties of the organism would allow it to survive eradication campaigns in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species produces a large amount of seed, which can remain dormant for long periods of time (DiTomaso et al., 2013). It also has a high seed bank density and thus all seeds would need to be removed (DiTomaso et al., 2013). Therefore, these factors may hinder eradication efforts. In addition, the seed bank may be widespread as the plant can be widely spread by birds and other animals.

Qu. 3.9. How likely are the biological characteristics of the organism to facilitate its establishment in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

a list and description of the reproduction mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the Union

an indication of the propagule pressure of the species (e.g. number of gametes, seeds, eggs or propagules, number of reproductive cycles per year) of each of those reproduction mechanisms in relation to the environmental conditions in the Union.

If relevant, comment on the likelihood of establishment based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in establishment whereas for others high

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Phytolacca americana* can reproduce by both seed and regeneration from a tuberous taproot. Each inflorescence can contain numerous berries, each containing 10 seeds. McDonnell *et al.* (1984) counted up to 78 ripe fruits per inflorescence. A single plant can produce over 2 500 fruits and 25 000 seeds (Dumas 2011). Dumas (2011), citing Armesto (1983) estimate a density of 592 seeds per m⁻¹. The species is self-fertilizing and flowering can occur in the first year of growth. Mature berries can occur from August to early November (France) and germination rates have been reported as high as 80 % though it varies within the population (0 – 100 %) (Dumas, 2008; Armesto *et al.*, 1983; Vuilleminot & Mischler, 2012). Seeds can remain viable in the soil for approximately forty years (Dumas, 2011; Vuilleminot & Mischler, 2012) and can germinate following disturbance in the soil and/or a clearing of an area (for example a woodland). This has been shown to be the case in all the lowland forests of the Jura, France (Vuilleminot & Mischler, 2012).

It is interesting to note that germination of seed is increased when the seed moves through a bird digestive tract (Dumas, 2011). It is noted that, ‘Orrock (2005) studied the influence that can have the transit of seeds in the digestive tract of birds where a positive effect on the germination rate, which goes from 67% for controls to 88% for seeds from the fruits consumed’.

In addition, the species appears to be resistant to a number of environmental constraints. For example, the species can withstand high levels of heavy metals in soils enabling the species to grow in polluted habitats (Min *et al.* 2006; Peng, 2008). It is noted that soil texture and acidity does not limit the occurrence of *P. americana* (Sauer, 1952). The species is reported to tolerate a wide range of soil pH (Sauer, 1952).

Seed of the species appears to be tolerant of fire and can promote its germination. After forest fires, seed can germinate from the seed bank (Glasgow *et al.*, 2007).

Qu. 3.10. How likely is the adaptability of the organism to facilitate its establishment?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Phytolacca americana* has a high level of plasticity being tolerant to a variety of environmental conditions and as such habitats. The species thrives in ruderal habitats where disturbances occur (Dumas, 2011).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

There are some indications that the species has adapted to the RA area and as detailed by Dumas (2011a), the climatic limits of the species in the RA area are unlikely to have been reached. Dumas (2011a) highlight that if the climatic characteristics defined by Sauer (1952) in the area of origin, are applied to France, the species should not be present in the Fontainebleau region, where it is currently widespread. This region of France does not meet the temperature and rainfall requirements.

Qu. 3.11. How likely is it that the organism could establish despite low genetic diversity in the founder population?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species has established within the RA area though it is not known how many introductions have taken place from founder populations to realize this establishment.

Qu. 3.12. If the organism does not establish, then how likely is it that casual populations will continue to occur?

Consider, for example, a species which cannot reproduce in the risk assessment area, because of unsuitable climatic conditions or host plants, but is present because of recurring introduction, entry and release events. This may also apply for long-living organisms.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species is already established within the RA area. In areas in the RA area where it is not established, as the species is spread by birds and other animals, casual population of the species may occur with the RA area in space and time.

Qu. 3.13. Estimate the overall likelihood of establishment in the risk assessment area based on the similarity between climatic conditions within it and the organism's current distribution under current climatic conditions. In addition, details of the likelihood of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions under current climatic conditions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the risk of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions: providing insight in the risk of establishment in (new areas in) the Union.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Phytolacca americana* is present in the Koppen Giger climate zones of Csb, Csc, Cfb within the EU. Csb (warm-summer Mediterranean climate) and Cfb (oceanic climate with warm summers) are widespread zones within the EU.

Phytolacca americana is present in the following biogeographical regions: Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, , Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic (based on GBIF data, 2019).

The species still has the potential for further establishment in the aforementioned biogeographical regions.

Qu. 3.14 Estimate the overall likelihood of establishment in the risk assessment area under foreseeable climate change conditions. In addition, details of the likelihood of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions under foreseeable climate change conditions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the risk of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the likelihood of establishment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The thorough assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment of likely establishment within a medium timeframe scenario (e.g. 30-50 years) with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided.

However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: Under a climate change scenario of (RCP 4.5, over the next 30/50 years), when considering establishment into the RA area, it is likely that *P. americana* will establish within the RA area with a medium confidence. Climate change may extend the areas where the species can be grown to the north and restrict the areas where the species may grow in the Mediterranean region (see species distribution modelling annex). Both increased summer and winter temperatures would benefit the species. Increased precipitation and CO₂ levels as a result of climate change may also favor the species. An increase in fires within the RA area due to increased temperature may act to promote the germination of the seed bank and increase the population. All biogeographical regions would have similar likelihood scores based on the pathways described. See Annex VII for more details.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

4 PROBABILITY OF SPREAD

Important instructions:

Spread is defined as the expansion of the geographical distribution of an alien species within the risk assessment area.

Repeated releases at separate locations do not represent continuous spread and should be considered in the probability of entry section. In other words, intentional anthropogenic “spread” via release or escape (“jump-dispersal”), should be dealt within the entry section. However, as repeated releases contribute to the spread of the target organism in the risk assessment area, the relevant pathway(s) should be briefly discussed here too, with an explicit reference to the entry section for additional details.

Qu. 4.1. How important is the expected spread of this organism within the risk assessment area by natural means? (List and comment on each of the mechanisms for natural spread.)

including the following elements:

a list and description of the natural spread mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

an indication of the rate of each of those spread mechanisms in relation to the environmental conditions in the Union.

The description of spread patterns should include elements of the species life history and behavioural traits able to explain its ability to spread, including: reproduction or growth strategy, dispersal capacity, longevity, dietary requirements, environmental and climatic requirements, specialist or generalist characteristics.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Natural spread is a key factor in the dispersal of *P. americana* in the RA area. Birds have been reported to spread the species within the RA area. In America, it is reported that up to 29 bird species feed on the fruits of *P. americana* (Armesto, 1983). Within the RA area, some data exist. For example, Balogh and Juhasz (2008) detail the following species feeding on fruits in the following countries: in Italy: blackcap (*Sylvia atricapilla*), whitethroat (*Sylvia communis*), song thrush (*Turdus philomelos*), blackbird (*Turdus merula*), blue rock thrush (*Monticola solitarius*), robin (*Erithacus rubecula*); in South France: robin and blackcap; in New-Zeland: the pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus*). Villemenot & Mischler (2012) list several bird species eating fleshy berries as responsible of *P. americana* spread: pigeons (*Columba* spp.), turtledoves (*Streptopelia decaocto*) and starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*), but also probably blackbirds (*Turdus merula*), thrushes (*Turdus* spp.) and warblers (*Sylvia* spp.). Birds can also feed on the dried berries in the winter.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Sauer (1952) report that the species is poorly suited to dispersal by wind or water (information from the native range, Sauer, 1952).

Benvenuti (2004) detail that the starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*), is the main species responsible of this spread in the city of Pisa, *P. americana* grows under trees the species chooses as nesting sites. He also notes that the latter germinate faster (4 to 5 days earlier) than the control seeds.

Balogh and Juhasz (2008) write: ‘Ad hoc observations prove that the young shoots of *P. americana* is eaten by big games (red deer, fallow deer) living in the Hungarian forests. The sheep and the goat kept on sandy pasture-land consume this plant too’. However, it is not known if they can act to spread the plant through seed. In addition, Dumas (2011b) include rodents as seed feeders. In the forest of Fontainebleau, cervids are also suspected to be vectors of the seeds (Villemenot & Mischler, 2012). Indeed, all such species have the potential to spread seed within the RA area.

It should be noted, that in Belgium, there are increasing observations of the species in the natural environment, along with other *Phytolacca* species, in particular *P. acinosa*) indicating the increased spread of the species (Adriaens *et al*, 2019).

Qu. 4.2. How important is the expected spread of this organism within the risk assessment area by human assistance? (List and comment on each of the mechanisms for human-assisted spread and provide a description of the associated commodities.)

including the following elements:

a list and description of the anthropogenic spread mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the Union.

an indication of the rate of each of those spread mechanisms in relation to the environmental conditions in the Union.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Human assisted spread can play a factor in the spread of the species due to the use of machinery and management of certain habitats (such as woodland management). Vuillemonot & Mischler (2012), detail that harvesters in softwood plantations have acted to promote the spread of the species. The intervention of harvesters in the softwood plantations of would trigger the germination of the seed bank, due to ground disturbances.

Vuillemonot & Mischler (2012) also highlight that seeds can become incorporated into the tread of tyres and hiking boots that can then act to spread the species into new areas.

Soil can also contain large amounts of seeds (and it is detailed that the seed bank can have a longevity of up to 50 years (UC Weed Science, 2018)), thus the movement of soil may also act to facilitate the spread of the species within the RA area.

Qu. 4.2a. List and describe relevant pathways of spread. Where possible give detail about the specific origins and end points of the pathways. For each pathway answer questions 4.3 to 4.9 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than one pathway, e.g. 4.3a, 4.4a, etc. and then 4.3b, 4.4b etc. for the next pathway.

including the following elements:

a list and description of pathways with an indication of their importance and associated risks (e.g. the likelihood of spread in the Union, based on these pathways; likelihood of survival, or reproduction, or increase during transport and storage; ability and likelihood of transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host). Where possible details about the specific origins and end points of the pathways shall be included.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication.

All relevant pathways should be considered. The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity shall be used.

Spread pathways considered in this section include:

Transport – stowaway: Machinery/ equipment

Unaided (natural spread)

Pathway name: Transport – contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation)

Pathway name: People and their luggage/ equipment (in particular tourism)

Pathway name: Transport – stowaway: Machinery/ equipment

Qu. 4.3a. Is spread along this pathway intentional or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The spread of *P. americana* via machinery/ equipment is the unintentional spread of the species within the RA area.

Qu. 4.4a. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway

if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. However, as in areas where the species is present, the seed bank density can be high, and thus there is a potential for spread. Dumas (2011b), when considering spread, highlight that ‘the transport of seeds by the soil retained in the tread pattern of machine tires is a hypothesis that we cannot exclude’. Buhk (2016) also highlight the role of machines used in forestry as a potential for the spread of the species.

Qu. 4.5a. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The seeds of the species are small and therefore they could survive during transport along this spread pathway. The species is unlikely to increase along the pathway until it finds a suitable habitat.

Qu. 4.6a. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	very likely		
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Response: With the right cleaning and disinfecting of used machinery, the species would probably be removed from the machinery. However, such practices are not always common and therefore the species may survive existing management practices during this mode of spread.

Qu. 4.7a. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The seeds are relatively small and potentially can remain hidden in soil in cracks and crevices in machinery and equipment. Such machinery can be moved around the RA area transporting the seed to new areas.

Qu. 4.8a. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread? (including, where possible, details about the specific origins and end points of the pathway)

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: It would be very likely that *P. americana* can transfer to a suitable habitat if the species is a stowaway on machinery/ equipment. The machinery in question, such as forest vehicles or harvesters are utilized in suitable habitats.

Qu. 4.9a. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread within the Union based on this pathway? (please provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The overall potential rate of spread within the RA area for the pathway Transport – stowaway: Machinery/ equipment is rated as moderately with a low confidence. Dumas (2011b), has

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

highlight this pathway as a potential pathway, but as previously mentioned, there is no information on rates of spread, hence the low confidence score.

Pathway name: UNAIDED (natural spread)

Qu. 4.3b. Is spread along this pathway intentional or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	unintentional	CONFIDENCE	high
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Response: The spread of *P. americana* via natural methods (birds and other small mammals) is the unintentional spread of the species within the RA area. As highlighted in question 4.1, natural spread is considered a significant pathway for spread of the species in the RA area.

Qu. 4.4b. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway

if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. Natural spread is a key factor in the dispersal of *P. americana* in the RA area. In particular, birds have been reported to spread the species with the RA area. In America, it is reported that up to 29 bird species feed on the fruits of *P. americana* (Armesto, 1983). Within the RA area, some data exist. For example, Balogh and Juhasz (2008) detail the following species feeding on fruits in the following countries: in Italy: blackcap (*Sylvia atricapilla*), whitethroat (*Sylvia communis*), song thrush (*Turdus philomelos*), blackbird (*Turdus merula*), blue rock thrush (*Monticola solitarius*), robin (*Erithacus rubecula*); in South France: robin and blackcap; in New-Zeland: the pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus*).

Sauer (1952) report that the species is poorly suited to dispersal by wind or water (information from the native range, Sauer, 1952).

Benvenuti (2004) detail that the starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*), is the main species responsible of this spread in the city of Pisa, *P. americana* grows under trees the species chooses as nesting sites. He also notes that the latter germinate faster (4 to 5 days earlier) than the control seeds.

Balogh and Juhasz (2008) write: ‘Ad hoc observations prove that the young shoots of *P. americana* is eaten by big games (red deer, fallow deer) living in the Hungarian forests. The sheep and the goat kept on sandy pasture-land consume this plant too’. In addition, Dumas (2011b) include rodents as seed feeders. Indeed, all such species have the potential to spread seed within the RA area.

Qu. 4.5b. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The seeds of the species can remain viable following movement through the digestive system of animals and birds. Thus, seeds can survive, though they will not reproduce or increase during this spread pathway.

Qu. 4.6b. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Management practices will be very limited for this spread pathway. Controlling birds and small mammal movement is not an option for management.

Qu. 4.7b. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: Birds and other small mammals can carry the seeds over long distances (e.g. < 10 km) and can be dispersed in areas undetected. The seeds will remain in the gut of the species for some time and be deposited in the soil.

Qu. 4.8b. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread? (including, where possible, details about the specific origins and end points of the pathway)

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Birds and other small mammals can carry the seeds over large distances and the seeds can be dispersed in habitats suitable for the species.

Qu. 4.9b. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread within the Union based on this pathway? (please provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The overall potential rate of spread via this pathway is estimated as rapidly with a medium confidence.

Pathway name: Transport – contaminant (transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation))

Qu. 4.3c. Is spread along this pathway intentional or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The spread of *P. americana* via transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation) is the unintentional spread of the species within the RA area.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 4.4c. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway

if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. However, as in areas where the species is present, the seed bank density can be high, and thus there is a potential for spread (Hyatt and Casper, 2000).

Qu. 4.5c. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The seeds of the species are small and therefore they could survive during transport along this spread pathway. The substrate would be conducive to maintain survival.

Qu. 4.6c. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	very likely		
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Response: Careful methodical management practices coupled with inspection would be needed to ensure that the species did not spread with contaminated soil. This is often not feasible with such small seeds.

Qu. 4.7c. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely	CONFIDENCE	low
	unlikely		medium
	moderately likely		high
	likely		
	very likely		

Response: The seeds are relatively small and potentially can remain undetected within soil. Soil and other habitat material can be moved throughout the RA area and seeds can be spread within such material.

Qu. 4.8c. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread? (including, where possible, details about the specific origins and end points of the pathway)

RESPONSE	very unlikely	CONFIDENCE	low
	unlikely		medium
	moderately likely		high
	likely		
	very likely		

Response: It would be very likely that *P. americana* can transfer to a suitable habitat if seed of the species is incorporated in soil. Topsoil and habitat material is often physically transferred to suitable habitats and thus it is very likely that the species will transfer to suitable habitats.

This fact that the species is often recorded in urban development areas further supports the hypothesis that the species can be moved by soil and habitat material.

Qu. 4.9c. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread within the Union based on this pathway? (please provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly	CONFIDENCE	low
	slowly		medium
	moderately		high
	rapidly		

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	very rapidly		
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Response: Response: The overall potential rate of spread via this pathway is estimated as moderately with a medium confidence.

Pathway name: People and their luggage/ equipment (in particular tourism)

Qu. 4.3d. Is spread along this pathway intentional or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	Low Medium high
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Response: The spread of *P. americana* via people and their luggage/equipment in particular tourism is for this species considered the unintentional movement of the species via seeds. In the sense of this pathway, the main risk is of introduction into new areas via spread is that the species could be incorporated into the tread of hiking boots or other equipment and moved accidentally to other areas.

Qu. 4.4d. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway

if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. As the fruit of the species does not have any spiny spurs there would be less chance of the fruits attaching to clothes and other material. This spread pathway is not considered by the authors of this RA as a major spread pathway.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 4.5d. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The seeds of the species are small and therefore they could survive during transport along this spread pathway. The substrate would be conducive to maintain survival. The species would not reproduce along this pathway or increase.

Qu. 4.6d. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Careful methodical management practices coupled with inspection of tread on boots would be needed to ensure that the species did not spread. However, often biosecurity measures are not widely known by the general public.

Qu. 4.7d. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The seeds are relatively small and potentially can remain undetected within the tread of hiking boots. Additionally, the seeds may not be easily identifiable to non-botanists and thus may be overlooked.

Qu. 4.8d. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread? (including, where possible, details about the specific origins and end points of the pathway)

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It would be very likely that *P. americana* can transfer to a suitable habitat if seed of the species is attached to hiking boots. Top soil and habitat material is often physically transferred to suitable habitats and thus it is very likely that the species will transfer to suitable habitats.

This fact that the species is often recorded in urban development areas (per sobs, authors) further supports the hypothesis that the species can be moved by soil and habitat material.

Qu. 4.9d. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread within the Union based on this pathway? (please provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Response: The overall potential rate of spread via this pathway is estimated as moderately with a medium confidence. Seeds and plant material can be moved by human means.

Qu. 4.10. Within the risk assessment area, how difficult would it be to contain the organism in relation to these pathways of spread?

RESPONSE	very easy easy with some difficulty difficult very difficult	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The spread pathways are numerous and varied making the management of the spread pathways difficult. In particular, natural spread is a difficult pathway to manage.

Qu. 4.11. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread in relevant biogeographical regions under current conditions for this organism in the risk assessment area (indicate any key issues and provide quantitative data where possible).

Thorough assessment of the risk of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions, providing insight in the risk of spread into (new areas in) the Union.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species is currently present in the following biogeographical regions: Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic (based on GBIF data, 2019). Within all of these regions, the spread is likely to be rapidly.

Qu. 4.12. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions (provide quantitative data where possible).

Thorough assessment of the risk of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk, specifically if rates of spread are likely slowed down or accelerated.

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Climatic change will allow *P. americana* to establish further north than present but its inherent rate of spread should remain rapidly with a medium confidence.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

5 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT

Important instructions:

Questions 5.1-5.5 relate to biodiversity and ecosystem impacts, 5.6-5.8 to impacts on ecosystem services, 5.9-5.13 to economic impact, 5.14-5.15 to social and human health impact, and 5.16-5.18 to other impacts. These impacts can be interlinked, for example a disease may cause impacts on biodiversity and/or ecosystem functioning that leads to impacts on ecosystem services and finally economic impacts. In such cases the assessor should try to note the different impacts where most appropriate, cross-referencing between questions when needed.

Each set of questions starts with the impact elsewhere in the world, then considers impacts in the risk assessment area (=EU excluding outermost regions) separating known impacts to date (i.e. past and current impacts) from potential future impacts (including foreseeable climate change).

Only negative impacts are considered in this section (socio-economic benefits are considered in Qu. A.7)

Biodiversity and ecosystem impacts

Qu. 5.1. How important is the impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation caused by the organism in its non-native range excluding the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

Biodiversity means the variability among living organisms from all sources, including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems

impacted chemical, physical or structural characteristics and functioning of ecosystems

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comment: *Phytolacca americana* is reported to form dense stands that can outcompete native vegetation and can act to retard forest regeneration (FOEN, 2006; Orwig and Foster 1998). Apart from this and other references to the species being invasive (e.g. in China, Dong et al., 2011, where they do not provide specific details), there are no other known studies that have evaluated the impact of the species on biodiversity. However, as the species is able to form dense stands these impacts may include outcompeting native plant species for space, light and nutrients.

In Switzerland, *P. americana* is listed on a 'watch list'.

Qu. 5.2. How important is the current known impact of the organism on biodiversity at all

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2014-2020

levels of organisation (e.g. decline in native species, changes in native species communities, hybridisation) in the risk assessment area (include any past impact in your response)?

Discuss impacts that are currently occurring or are likely occurring or have occurred in the past in the risk assessment area. Where there is no direct evidence of impact in the risk assessment area (for example no studies have been conducted), evidence from outside of the risk assessment area can be used to infer impacts within the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comment: Dumas (2007) indicates that as soon as *P. americana* reach 50% cover, there is 24% decrease in species richness of invaded communities. When it is abundant, *P. americana* can modify several plant resident plant communities, by competing with notably *Rubus* spp. and *Cytisus scoparius*, especially in all the open environments associated with forest, such as the hems and the clearings, megaphorbiaies, wastelands and moors, etc. (Villemenot & Mischler, 2012).

However, Dumas (2011a) considers that studies on the impact of *P. americana* on native biodiversity within the RA area is poorly documented. In addition, Fried (2012) considers that overall the impact of this species is low, since the vast majority of *P. americana* populations are found in ruderal or post-crop areas (vines abandoned).

A study by Schirmel (2019) in southwest Germany, showed that *P. americana* invasion resulted in an altered arthropod community structure. The cricket *Nemobius sylvestris* was negatively affected by *P. americana*.

There are suggestions, that chemical leaching from seeds fallen to the ground may also be toxic to the soil macro- and micro-biota (Dumas, 2011a).

Balogh and Juhasz (2008) detail that *P. americana* can out-compete native species on sandy grasslands by completing for space and light. The species can shade out native species and in different forest communities its presence can reduce the conservation value. Dispersion of *P. americana* in the protected area of Barcsi Borokas (originally with dominance of *Juniperus communis*) causes large problems, where along with an invasive tree, black cherry (*Prunus serotina*) it occurs in mass in open perennial grasslands (*Festuco-Corynephorum*), Molinia-Turkey oak forests (*Molinio litoralis-Quercetum*) and alder swamp forests (*Carici elongatae-Alnetum*) too. In West Hungary it also endangers the oak-hornbeam forests.

Campana *et al.* (2002) detail a disruptive impact on earthworm populations highlighting that the species seem to repel most earthworm species. This may be due to the allelopathic properties of the species. Given its molluscicidal potency, *P. americana* probably has the same effect on gastropods (Dumas, 2011; Villemenot & Mischler, 2012).

Henneuse *et al.* (2007) observed a reduction in plant species richness when the recovery of *P. americana* increases.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Phytolacca americana has been detailed as one of the top invasive plants (most harmful) by Protected Area Managers where it was recorded as present in 4 Protected Areas (Monaco and Genovesi, 2014). In comparison, *Fallopia japonica* was recorded as present in 48 Protected Areas

Qu. 5.3. How important is the potential future impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation likely to be in the risk assessment area?

See comment above. The potential future impact shall be assessed only for the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comment: Impacts, although not currently scientifically evaluated, are likely to be moderate in the future as the species can form dense monocultures which can potentially outcompete native plant species. Further spread is likely throughout the RA area, especially in ruderal habitats and forests.

Qu. 5.4. How important is decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the organism currently in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

native species impacted, including red list species, endemic species and species listed in the Birds and Habitats directives

protected sites impacted, in particular Natura 2000

habitats impacted, in particular habitats listed in the Habitats Directive, or red list habitats

the ecological status of water bodies according to the Water Framework Directive and environmental status of the marine environment according to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comment: There are no detailed scientific studies to evaluate the impact of *P. americana* on native species and thus any decline in conservation value to habitats. As mentioned, the species predominantly grows in ruderal habitats within the RA area and these are often of little conservation importance. However, in the areas where the species is established, *P. americana* has invaded natural habitats which can act to decrease local biodiversity (see question 5.2). In Hungary, the species is present in protected areas (Balogh and Juhasz 2008). *Phytolacca americana* has been detailed as

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

one of the top invasive plants (most harmful) by Protected Area Managers where it was recorded as present in 4 Protected Areas (Monaco and Genovesi, 2014). In comparison, *Fallopia japonica* was recorded as present in 48 Protected Areas.

Qu. 5.5. How important is decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

native species impacted, including red list species and species listed in the Birds and Habitats directives

protected sites impacted, in particular Natura 2000

habitats impacted, in particular habitats listed in the Habitats Directive, or red list habitats

the ecological status of water bodies according to the Water Framework Directive and environmental status of the marine environment according to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comment: There are no detailed scientific studies to evaluate the impact of *P. americana* on native species and thus any decline in conservation value to habitats. As mentioned, the species predominantly grows in ruderal habitats within the RA area and these are often of little conservation importance. However, in the areas where the species is established, *P. americana* has invaded natural habitats which can act to decrease local biodiversity (see question 5.2).

Ecosystem Services impacts

Qu. 5.6. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services in its non-native range excluding the risk assessment area?

For a list of relevant services use the CICES classification V5.1 provided as an annex.

Impacts on ecosystem services build on the observed impacts on biodiversity (habitat, species, genetic, functional) but focus exclusively on reflecting these changes in relation to their links with socio-economic well-being.

Quantitative data should be provided whenever available and references duly reported.

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

between “no information found” and “no impact found”.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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There are no scientific studies that have evaluated the impact of *P. americana* on ecosystem services in the RA area. There is some anecdotal evidence that the species can retard forest regeneration (Dong et al., 2011) though further research is needed on the subject. According to Dumas (2011a), another effect of *P. americana* on abiotic conditions would be the enrichment of potassium that this species causes on soils, constituting reserves of this element in the biotope.

Qu. 5.7. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services currently in the different biogeographic regions or marine sub-regions where the species has established in the risk assessment area (include any past impact in your response)?

See guidance to Qu. 5.6.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comment: Vuilleminot & Mischler (2012) detail that the description of the species to natural forest regeneration is often mentioned as a negative impact. The presence of the species may affect some recreational activities especially if the species forms dense monocultures in natural habitats blocking pathways and other recreational areas.

The species has been reported as having allelopathic properties which can affect the microbial soil community other organisms though there has not been any research conducted on this aspect at present.

Qu. 5.8. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services likely to be in the different biogeographic regions or marine sub-regions where the species can establish in the risk assessment area in the future?

See guidance to Qu. 5.6.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	major massive		
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Comment: *Phytolacca americana* may spread northwards within the RA area as a result of climate change though the impacts score is likely to be the same as under the current situation (moderate with a medium confidence). Impacts in the Mediterranean may be less if the climate is not conducive to establishment.

Economic impacts

Qu. 5.9. How great is the overall economic cost caused by the organism within its current area of distribution (excluding the risk assessment area), including both costs of / loss due to damage and the cost of current management.

Where economic costs of / loss due to the organism have been quantified for a species anywhere in the world these should be reported here. The assessment of the potential costs of / loss due to damage shall describe those costs quantitatively and/or qualitatively depending on what information is available. Cost of / loss due to damage within different economic sectors can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comment: *Phytolacca americana* can incur control costs within the risk assessment area particularly in clearing the species from areas where it has colonized urban development sites. In addition, the species can impact on woodland plantation as the species will need to be cleared and eradicated prior to planting of forest trees.

In the USA, there are reports the species can impact on yields of various crops though there are no direct studies that have evaluated crop yield reduction due to the presence of *P. americana*. In Pennsylvania, studies have been conducted to assess chemical control options for the species in maize and soybean fields highlighting there is management of the species and a cost associated (Patches et al., 2017).

Steckel (2006) highlights that the stain (from the berries) can impact on soybeans during harvest.

Although no monetary figure exist on costs associated with *P. americana* damage, costs are likely as Steckel (2006) highlights that the species can be very competitive for row crops. However, it is likely that the species is a minor economic problem compared to other weedy species in North America (e.g. *Amaranthus palmeri* – where there are numerous publications highlighting 70 -80 % crop yield reductions).

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Cucumber mosaic virus (CMV) has been reported in *P. americana* plants from northern Italy (Davino et al., 2012). This could have economic impacts to plant health within the EU.

Qu. 5.10. How great is the economic cost of / loss due to damage (excluding costs of management) of the organism currently in the risk assessment area (include any past costs in your response)?

Where economic costs of / loss due to the organism have been quantified for a species anywhere in the EU these should be reported here. Assessment of the potential costs of damage on human health, safety, and the economy, including the cost of non-action. A full economic assessment at EU scale might not be possible, but qualitative data or different case studies from across the EU (or third countries if relevant) may provide useful information to inform decision making. In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. Cost of / loss due to damage within different economic sectors can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

RESPONSE	minimal	CONFIDENCE	low
	minor		medium
	moderate		high
	major		
	massive		

Comments: The species has been shown to be problematic in maize crops, especially due to the berries that can release their liquid when crushed and stain the crops. Steckel (2006) highlights that the stain can impact on soybeans during harvest.

It is locally an important weed in maize crops of southwestern France where its harmfulness is considered very high (Mamarot & Rodriguez, 2002). It is also a weed in forestry where it can damage young plantations of trees (Villemeot & Mischler, 2012). In forest patches driven by natural regeneration, such as a mature oak forest whose coppice has been cut, the invasion of *P. americana* seems much more important. In this case, the density of *P. americana* stands questions the possibility of germination and development of young trees (Villemeot & Mischler, 2012). It has also been supposed that the reduced dietary interest for cervids of plots largely invaded by *P. americana* can reduce the hunting interest of some forests and the related income for forest owners (Villemeot & Mischler, 2012).

Kumschick *et al.* (2015) score the species as 1 for socio-economic costs ‘Minor impacts, in the range of native species, only locally, negligible economic loss’.

Cucumber mosaic virus (CMV) has been reported in *P. americana* plants from northern Italy (Davino et al., 2012). This could have economic impacts to plant health within the EU.

Qu. 5.11. How great is the economic cost of / loss due to damage (excluding costs of

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

management) of the organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 5.10.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comments: It is locally an important weed in maize crops of southwestern France where its harmfulness is considered very high (Mamarot & Rodriguez, 2002). It is also a weed in forestry where it can compete for light and resources with young plantations of trees (Villemenot & Mischler, 2002). In plots that have been cleared and where young tree seedlings have been introduced, the presence of *P. americana* can be an inconvenience to the forester, by requiring more regular clearing work until the tops of the young planted trees exceed the *P. americana* stands. Once this stage is over, the young trees released from competition will grow; but even if the density of the *P. americana* declines due to the shade created by the new settlement, this species seems to be maintained apparently for a long time and compete with species in shrub and herbaceous strata. In forest patches driven by natural regeneration, such as a mature oak forest whose coppice has been cut, the invasion of *P. americana* seems much more important. In this case, the density of *P. americana* stands questions the possibility of germination and development of young trees (Villemenot & Mischler, 2002). With an increase in geographical occurrence, the species may potentially cause greater economic costs.

Qu. 5.12. How great are the economic costs / losses associated with managing this organism currently in the risk assessment area (include any past costs in your response)?

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comments: The weeding of this species is costly in maize crop where herbicide spraying is only efficient on seedlings, but not on regrowth, and it requires an additional spray increasing the weed management cost (Mamarot & Rodriguez, 2003). Villemenot & Mischler (2012) also indicate that in forest, *P. americana* requires more regular clearance work until the top of the young trees exceeds *P. americana*. However, as the species often invades ruderal habitats and waste land, the economic management cost of the species is likely to be moderate within the RA area.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

In southwest Germany, costs have been detailed for managing *P. americana* at the Hoher Stein dune where figures in Euros range from 700 euros per ha to 3 800 euros per ha depending on the time of year (Rupp et al., 2017).

Qu. 5.13. How great are the economic costs / losses associated with managing this organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 5.12.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comments: No information has been found on the issue. With an increase in geographical occurrence, the species may potentially cause greater economic costs but this is difficult to predict.

Social and human health impacts

Qu. 5.14. How important is social, human health or other impact (not directly included in any earlier categories) caused by the organism for the risk assessment area and for third countries, if relevant (e.g. with similar eco-climatic conditions).

The description of the known impact and the assessment of potential future impact on human health, safety and the economy, shall, if relevant, include information on

illnesses, allergies or other affections to humans that may derive directly or indirectly from a species;

damages provoked directly or indirectly by a species with consequences for the safety of people, property or infrastructure;

direct or indirect disruption of, or other consequences for, an economic or social activity due to the presence of a species.

Social and human health impacts can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comments: *Phytolacca americana*, although edible, is a toxic species that cause vomiting and diarrhea when eaten raw. Balogh and Juhasz (2008) detail: ‘The most toxic part of the plant is the

root, which contains saponins, among them phytolaccatoxin that is toxic to vertebrates. In respects of human health the most dangerous is the lectin content. In the new roots of *P. americana* hemagglutinin compound was detected – which is similar to the ones in the seeds of castor bean and Calabar bean – that contains much cysteine (a sulphur-laden amino-acid) and has mitogenic effect. It can stimulate the abnormal cell division of the poise B- and T- lymphocytes, and it can damage the chromosomes too’.

Ogzewalla *et al.* (1962) highlights that in the USA, children can often eat the berries and become ill. The fruits, due to their deep red colour can be inviting to children and can resemble berries of other species (similar to that in the RA region). There are reports of deaths through consuming *P. americana*, though it is generally reported that such fatalities are uncommon.

Phytolacca americana can also be toxic to animal species. For example, Dumas (2011b), citing Barnett (1975) highlights that the species can be toxic to turkeys, where a 38 % mortality is recorded in birds who diet consisted of 10 % of *P. americana* seeds (data from the USA). Additionally, Dumas (2011a) detail that mortality has been recorded in pigs, cows and horses.

Qu. 5.15. How important is social, human health or other impact (not directly included in any earlier categories) caused by the organism in the future for the risk assessment area.

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comments: All known and potential impacts are listed in the previous categories.

Other impacts

Qu. 5.16. How important is the impact of the organism as food, a host, a symbiont or a vector for other damaging organisms (e.g. diseases)?

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comments: There is no information on this issue.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 5.17. How important might other impacts not already covered by previous questions be resulting from introduction of the organism?

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comments: The previous sections have covered all impacts known for the species and other impacts are likely to be minimal.

Qu. 5.18. How important are the expected impacts of the organism despite any natural control by other organisms, such as predators, parasites or pathogens that may already be present in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Comments: The expected impacts of *P. americana* would remain the same within the RA area as there are no natural enemies that would impact on the species. Any generalist natural enemies that do attack the species would not inflict a significant impact on the population.

Qu. 5.19. Estimate the overall impact in the risk assessment area under current climate conditions. In addition, details of overall impact in relevant biogeographical regions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the overall impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, with impacts on economy as well as social and human health as aggravating factors, in current conditions.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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The overall impact in the risk assessment area under current climate conditions is moderate with medium uncertainty. There are studies that have highlighted the impact of the species on biodiversity where measurable damage to native species has been documented but it is neither evident that this damage is long term or irreversible. There is no evidence on local extinctions. There is no detailed evidence of the impact of the species on ecosystem services. There is some anecdotal evidence that

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

the species can retard forest regeneration (Dong et al., 2011) though this is not supported at present with scientific studies. Kumschick *et al.* (2015) score the species as low for socio-economic costs ‘Minor impacts, in the range of native species, only locally, negligible economic loss’.

Qu. 5.20. Estimate the overall impact in the risk assessment area in foreseeable climate change conditions. In addition, details of overall impact in relevant biogeographical regions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the overall impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, with impacts on economy as well as social and human health as aggravating factors, under future conditions.

RESPONSE	minimal	CONFIDENCE	low
	minor		medium
	moderate		high
	major		
	massive		

Comment: The overall impact in RA area in foreseeable climate change conditions is unlikely to change from that of the current climatic conditions. New (northern) areas of the RA area may be suitable for the establishment of the species but it is likely that the impact will remain moderate with a medium confidence to reflect the uncertainty of climate change prediction. Areas in the Mediterranean may become less suitable for the establishment of the species in the natural environment and thus less impact may be seen in these areas.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RISK SUMMARIES			
	RESPONSE	CONFIDENCE	COMMENT
Summarise Introduction*	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	low medium high	When considering all pathways into the RA area, it is likely that <i>P. americana</i> can enter the region with a medium confidence. There are three potential active pathways of introduction: horticulture, release in nature for use and transport - contamination. However, it should be noted that the risk of these pathways is negligible in view of the already established populations of the species in the RA area.
Summarise Entry*	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	low medium high	When considering all pathways for entry into the RA area, it is likely that <i>P. americana</i> can enter the natural environment, with a medium confidence.
Summarise Establishment*	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	low medium high	The species is already established within the RA area and further establishment in climatically similar environments is likely. Habitats within the RA area are widespread.
Summarise Spread*	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	low medium high	The species can spread by human assisted and natural spread. Both are major spread pathways for the species within the RA area.
Summarise Impact*	minimal minor moderate major massive	low medium high	The species can form dense monocultures which can act to outcompete native plant species. <i>Phytolacca americana</i> can invade ruderal and natural habitats.
Conclusion of the risk assessment (overall risk)	low moderate high	low medium high	There are active pathways where the species can enter the RA area, and the natural environment. The species is capable of establishing in the RA area and spreading moderately. The impact of the species needs further research, but is within this RA considered as moderate. Based on these scores the overall assessment of risk is moderate with a medium uncertainty.

*in current climate conditions and in foreseeable future climate conditions

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

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2014-2020

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MANAGEMENTUL
SPECIILOR INVAZIVE
DIN ROMÂNIA

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Distribution Summary

Please answer as follows:

- Yes if recorded, established or invasive
 – if not recorded, established or invasive
 ? Unknown; data deficient

The columns refer to the answers to Questions A5 to A12 under Section A.

For data on marine species at the Member State level, delete Member States that have no marine borders. In all other cases, provide answers for all columns.

Member States

	Recorded	Established (currently)	Possible establishment (under current climate)	Possible establishment (under foreseeable climate)	Invasive (currently)
Austria	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Belgium	YES		YES	YES	
Bulgaria	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Croatia	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Cyprus	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Czech Republic	YES		YES	YES	
Denmark				YES	
Estonia			YES	YES	
Finland			YES	YES	
France	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Germany	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Greece	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Hungary	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Ireland					
Italy	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Latvia			YES	YES	
Lithuania			YES	YES	
Luxembourg			YES	YES	
Malta			YES	YES	
Netherlands	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Poland	YES		YES	YES	
Portugal	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Romania	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Slovakia	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Slovenia	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Spain	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Sweden				YES	
United Kingdom	YES			YES	

Biogeographical regions of the risk assessment area

	Recorded	Established (currently)	Possible establishment (under current climate)	Possible establishment (under foreseeable climate)	Invasive (currently)
Alpine	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Atlantic	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Black Sea	YES	YES	YES	YES	
Boreal	YES		YES	YES	
Continental	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Mediterranean	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Pannonian	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Steppic	YES	YES	YES	YES	

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DIN ROMÂNIA

ANNEX I Scoring of Likelihoods of Events

(taken from UK Non-native Organism Risk Assessment Scheme User Manual, Version 3.3, 28.02.2005)

Score	Description	Frequency
Very unlikely	This sort of event is theoretically possible, but is never known to have occurred and is not expected to occur	1 in 10,000 years
Unlikely	This sort of event has not occurred anywhere in living memory	1 in 1,000 years
Possible	This sort of event has occurred somewhere at least once in recent years, but not locally	1 in 100 years
Likely	This sort of event has happened on several occasions elsewhere, or on at least one occasion locally in recent years	1 in 10 years
Very likely	This sort of event happens continually and would be expected to occur	Once a year

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ANNEX II Scoring of Magnitude of Impacts

(modified from UK Non-native Organism Risk Assessment Scheme User Manual, Version 3.3, 28.02.2005)

Score	Biodiversity and ecosystem impact	Ecosystem Services impact	Economic impact (Monetary loss and response costs per year)	Social and human health impact, and other impacts
	<i>Question 5.1-5</i>	<i>Question 5.6-8</i>	<i>Question 5.9-13</i>	<i>Question 5.14-18</i>
Minimal	Local, short-term population loss, no significant ecosystem effect	No services affected ¹⁴	Up to 10,000 Euro	No social disruption. Local, mild, short-term reversible effects to individuals.
Minor	Some ecosystem impact, reversible changes, localised	Local and temporary, reversible effects to one or few services	10,000-100,000 Euro	Significant concern expressed at local level. Mild short-term reversible effects to identifiable groups, localised.
Moderate	Measureable long-term damage to populations and ecosystem, but reversible; little spread, no extinction	Measureable, temporary, local and reversible effects on one or several services	100,000-1,000,000 Euro	Temporary changes to normal activities at local level. Minor irreversible effects and/or larger numbers covered by reversible effects, localised.
Major	Long-term irreversible ecosystem change, spreading beyond local area	Local and irreversible or widespread and reversible effects on one / several services	1,000,000-10,000,000 Euro	Some permanent change of activity locally, concern expressed over wider area. Significant irreversible effects locally or reversible effects over large area.
Massive	Widespread, long-term population loss or extinction, affecting several species with serious ecosystem effects	Widespread and irreversible effects on one / several services	Above 10,000,000 Euro	Long-term social change, significant loss of employment, migration from affected area. Widespread, severe, long-term, irreversible health effects.

¹⁴ Not to be confused with “no impact”.

ANNEX III Scoring of Confidence Levels

(modified from Bacher *et al.* 2017)

Each answer provided in the risk assessment must include an assessment of the level of confidence attached to that answer, reflecting the possibility that information needed for the answer is not available or is insufficient or available but conflicting.

The responses in the risk assessment should clearly support the choice of the confidence level.

Confidence level	Description
Low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g. only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence <i>and/or</i> Impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the assessment area <i>and/or</i> Evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g. because it is strongly ambiguous <i>and/or</i> The information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.
Medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred <i>and/or</i> Impacts are recorded at a small spatial scale, but rescaling of the data to relevant scales of the assessment area is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty <i>and/or</i> The interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.
High	There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment (including causality) <i>and</i> Impacts are recorded at a comparable scale <i>and/or</i> There are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa <i>and</i> The interpretation of data/information is straightforward <i>and/or</i> Data/information are not controversial or contradictory.

ANNEX IV Ecosystem services classification (CICES V5.1, simplified) and examples

For the purposes of this risk assessment, please feel free to use what seems as the most appropriate category / level / combination of impact (Section – Division – Group), reflecting information available.

Section	Division	Group	Examples (i.e. relevant CICES “classes”)
Provisioning	Biomass	Cultivated <i>terrestrial</i> plants	Cultivated terrestrial plants (including fungi, algae) grown for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from cultivated plants, fungi, algae and bacteria for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Cultivated plants (including fungi, algae) grown as a <u>source of energy</u> <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to crops, orchards, timber etc.</i>

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

		Cultivated <i>aquatic</i> plants	Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown as an <u>energy source</u> . <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to aquatic plants cultivated for nutrition, gardening etc. purposes.</i>
		Reared animals	Animals reared for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from reared animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Animals reared to provide <u>energy</u> (including mechanical) <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to livestock</i>
		Reared <i>aquatic</i> animals	Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from animals grown by in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture as an <u>energy source</u> <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to fish farming</i>
		Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic)	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used for <u>nutrition</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used as a <u>source of energy</u> <i>Example: reduction in the availability of wild plants (e.g. wild berries, ornamentals) due to non-native organisms (competition, spread of disease etc.)</i>
		Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic)	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from wild animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used as a <u>source of energy</u> <i>Example: reduction in the availability of wild animals (e.g. fish stocks, game) due to non-native organisms (competition, predations, spread of disease etc.)</i>
Genetic material from all biota	Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi	<u>Seeds, spores and other plant materials</u> collected for maintaining or establishing a population; Higher and lower plants (whole organisms) used to <u>breed new strains or varieties</u> ; Individual genes extracted from higher and lower plants for the <u>design and construction of new biological entities</u> <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms due to interbreeding</i>	
	Genetic material from animals	Animal material collected for the purposes of maintaining or establishing a population; Wild animals (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties; Individual genes extracted from organisms for the design and construction of new biological entities <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms due to interbreeding</i>	

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2014-2020

	Water ¹⁵	Surface water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Surface water for <u>drinking</u> ; Surface water used as a material (<u>non-drinking purposes</u>); Freshwater surface water, coastal and marine water used as an <u>energy source</u> <i>Example: loss of access to surface water due to spread of non-native organisms</i>
		Ground water for used for nutrition, materials or energy	Ground (and subsurface) water for <u>drinking</u> ; Ground water (and subsurface) used as a material (<u>non-drinking purposes</u>); Ground water (and subsurface) used as an <u>energy source</u> <i>Example: reduced availability of ground water due to spread of non-native organisms and associated increase of ground water consumption by vegetation.</i>
Regulation & Maintenance	Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	<u>Bio-remediation</u> by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals; <u>Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation</u> by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem functioning and ability to filtrate etc. waste or toxics</i>
		Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	<u>Smell reduction; noise attenuation; visual screening</u> (e.g. by means of green infrastructure) <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem structure, leading to reduced ability to mediate nuisances.</i>
	Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Baseline flows and extreme event regulation	Control of <u>erosion</u> rates; Buffering and attenuation of <u>mass movement</u> ; <u>Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation</u> (Including flood control, and coastal protection); <u>Wind</u> protection; <u>Fire</u> protection <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem functioning or structure leading to, for example, destabilisation of soil, increased risk or intensity of wild fires etc.</i>
		Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	<u>Pollination</u> (or 'gamete' dispersal in a marine context); <u>Seed dispersal</u> ; Maintaining <u>nursery populations and habitats</u> (Including gene pool protection) <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the abundance and/or distribution of wild pollinators; changes to the availability / quality of nursery habitats for fisheries</i>
		Pest and disease control	Pest control; Disease control <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the abundance and/or distribution of pests</i>
		Soil quality regulation	<u>Weathering processes</u> and their effect on soil quality; <u>Decomposition and fixing processes</u> and their effect on soil quality <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to vegetation structure and/or soil fauna leading to reduced soil quality</i>
		Water conditions	Regulation of the <u>chemical condition</u> of freshwaters by living processes; Regulation of the chemical condition of salt waters by living processes <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to buffer strips along water courses that remove nutrients in runoff and/or fish communities that regulate the resilience and resistance of water bodies to eutrophication</i>

¹⁵ Note: in the CICES classification provisioning of water is considered as an abiotic service whereas the rest of ecosystem services listed here are considered biotic.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

		Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation of <u>chemical composition</u> of atmosphere and oceans; Regulation of <u>temperature and humidity</u> , including ventilation and transpiration <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystems' ability to sequester carbon and/or evaporative cooling (e.g. by urban trees)</i>
Cultural	Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting	Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through <u>active or immersive interactions</u> ; Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through <u>passive or observational interactions</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.) that make it attractive for recreation, wild life watching etc.</i>
		Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>scientific investigation</u> or the creation of traditional ecological knowledge; Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>education and training</u> ; Characteristics of living systems that are resonant in terms of <u>culture or heritage</u> ; Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>aesthetic experiences</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.) that have cultural importance</i>
	Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Elements of living systems that have <u>symbolic meaning</u> ; Elements of living systems that have <u>sacred or religious meaning</u> ; Elements of living systems used for <u>entertainment or representation</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.) that have sacred or religious meaning</i>
		Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Characteristics or features of living systems that have an <u>existence value</u> ; Characteristics or features of living systems that have an <u>option or bequest value</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystems designated as wilderness areas, habitats of endangered species etc.</i>

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ANNEX V EU Biogeographic Regions and MSFD Subregions

See <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2> ,
http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/biogeog_regions/

and

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/msfd-regions-and-subregions-1/technical-document/pdf>

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MANAGEMENTUL
SPECIILOR INVAZIVE
DIN ROMÂNIA

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ANNEX VI Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/968 of 30 April 2018

see <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32018R0968>

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ANNEX VII Projection of climatic suitability for *Phytolacca americana* establishment

Björn Beckmann, Rob Tanner, Richard Shaw, Beth Purse and Dan Chapman

30 October 2019

Aim: To project the suitability for potential establishment of *Phytolacca americana* in Europe, under current and predicted future climatic conditions.

Data for modelling

Species occurrence data were obtained from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) (18598 records), the Biodiversity Information Serving Our Nation database (BISON) (6638 records), the Integrated Digitized Biocollections (iDigBio) (1327 records), the Atlas of Living Australia (179 records), the Berkeley Ecoinformatics Engine database (113 records), and a small number of additional records from the risk assessment team. We scrutinised occurrence records from regions where the species is not known to be established and removed any dubious records (e.g. fossils, captive records) or where the georeferencing was too imprecise (e.g. records referenced to a country or island centroid) or outside of the coverage of the predictor layers (e.g. small island or coastal occurrences). The remaining records were gridded at a 0.25 x 0.25 degree resolution for modelling, yielding 4321 grid cells with occurrences (Figure 1a). As a proxy for recording effort, the density of Tracheophyta records held by GBIF was also compiled on the same grid (Figure 1b).

(a) Species distribution used in modelling

(b) Estimated recording effort (log10-scaled)

Figure 1. (a) Occurrence records obtained for *Phytolacca americana* and used in the modelling, showing native and invaded distributions. (b) The recording density of Tracheophyta on GBIF, which was used as a proxy for recording effort.

Climate data were selected from the ‘Bioclim’ variables contained within the WorldClim database (Hijmans et al., 2005), originally at 5 arcminute resolution (0.083 x 0.083 degrees of longitude/latitude) and aggregated to a 0.25 x 0.25 degree grid for use in the model.

Based on the biology of *Phytolacca americana*, the following climate variables were used in the modelling:

Minimum temperature of the coldest month (Bio6)

Mean temperature of the warmest quarter (Bio10)

Climatic moisture index (CMI): ratio of mean annual precipitation to potential evapotranspiration, log+1 transformed. For its calculation, monthly potential evapotranspirations were estimated from the WorldClim monthly temperature data and solar radiation using the simple method of Zomer et al. (2008) which is based on the Hargreaves evapotranspiration equation (Hargreaves, 1994).

To estimate the effect of climate change on the potential distribution, equivalent modelled future climate conditions for the 2070s under the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) 2.6 and 4.5 were also obtained. There represent low and medium emissions scenarios, respectively. The above variables were obtained as averages of outputs of eight Global Climate Models (BCC-CSM1-1, CCSM4, GISS-E2-R, HadGEM2-AO, IPSL-CM5A-LR, MIROC-ESM, MRI-CGCM3, NorESM1-M), downscaled and calibrated against the WorldClim baseline (see http://www.worldclim.org/cmip5_5m).

Species distribution model

A presence-background (presence-only) ensemble modelling strategy was employed using the BIOMOD2 R package v3.3-7.1 (Thuiller et al., 2019, Thuiller et al., 2009). These models contrast the environment at the species' occurrence locations against a random sample of the global background environmental conditions (often termed 'pseudo-absences') in order to characterise and project suitability for occurrence. This approach has been developed for distributions that are in equilibrium with the environment. Because invasive species' distributions are not at equilibrium and subject to dispersal constraints at a global scale, we took care to minimise the inclusion of locations suitable for the species but where it has not been able to disperse to (Chapman et al. 2019). Therefore the background sampling region included:

The area accessible by native *Phytolacca americana* populations, in which the species is likely to have had sufficient time to disperse to all locations. Based on presumed maximum dispersal distances, the accessible region was defined as a 400km buffer around the native range occurrences; AND

A 30km buffer around the non-native occurrences, encompassing regions likely to have had high propagule pressure for introduction by humans and/or dispersal of the species; AND

Regions where we have an *a priori* expectation of high unsuitability for the species so that absence is assumed irrespective of dispersal constraints (see Figure 2). The following rules were applied to define a region expected to be highly unsuitable for *Phytolacca americana* at the spatial scale of the model:

Minimum temperature of the coldest month (Bio6) < -27

Mean temperature of the warmest quarter (Bio10) < 3

Climatic moisture index (CMI) < log_{1p}(0.20)

Altogether, only 0.2% of occurrence grid cells were located in the unsuitable background region.

Within the background region, 10 samples of 5000 randomly sampled grid cells were obtained, weighting the sampling by recording effort (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The background from which pseudo-absence samples were taken in the modelling of *Phytolacca americana*. Samples were taken from a 400km buffer around the native range and a 30km buffer around non-native occurrences (together forming the accessible background), and from areas expected to be highly unsuitable for the species (the unsuitable background region). Samples were weighted by a proxy for recording effort (Figure 1(b)).

Each dataset (i.e. combination of the presences and the individual background samples) was randomly split into 80% for model training and 20% for model evaluation. With each training dataset, seven statistical algorithms were fitted with the default BIOMOD2 settings and rescaled using logistic regression, except where specified below:

Generalised linear model (GLM)

Generalised boosting model (GBM)

Generalised additive model (GAM) with a maximum of four degrees of freedom per smoothing spline

Artificial neural network (ANN)

Multivariate adaptive regression splines (MARS)

Random forest (RF)

Maxent

Since the background sample was larger than the number of occurrences, prevalence fitting weights were applied to give equal overall importance to the occurrences and the background. Normalised variable importance was assessed and variable response functions were produced using BIOMOD2's default procedure.

Model predictive performance was assessed by the following three measures:

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2014-2020

AUC, the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (Fielding & Bell 1997). Predictions of presence-absence models can be compared with a subset of records set aside for model evaluation (here 20%) by constructing a confusion matrix with the number of true positive, false positive, false negative and true negative cases. For models generating non-dichotomous scores (as here) a threshold can be applied to transform the scores into a dichotomous set of presence-absence predictions. Two measures that can be derived from the confusion matrix are sensitivity (the proportion of observed presences that are predicted as such, quantifying omission errors), and specificity (the proportion of observed absences that are predicted as such, quantifying commission errors). A receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve can be constructed by using all possible thresholds to classify the scores into confusion matrices, obtaining sensitivity and specificity for each matrix, and plotting sensitivity against the corresponding proportion of false positives (equal to $1 - \text{specificity}$). The use of all possible thresholds avoids the need for a selection of a single threshold, which is often arbitrary, and allows appreciation of the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) is often used as a single threshold-independent measure for model performance (Manel, Williams & Ormerod 2001). AUC is the probability that a randomly selected presence has a higher model-predicted suitability than a randomly selected absence (Allouche et al. 2006).

Cohen's Kappa (Cohen 1960). This measure corrects the overall accuracy of model predictions (ratio of the sum of true presences plus true absences to the total number of records) by the accuracy expected to occur by chance. The kappa statistic ranges from -1 to +1, where +1 indicates perfect agreement and values of zero or less indicate a performance no better than random. Advantages of kappa are its simplicity, the fact that both commission and omission errors are accounted for in one parameter, and its relative tolerance to zero values in the confusion matrix (Manel, Williams & Ormerod 2001). However, Kappa has been criticised for being sensitive to prevalence (the proportion of sites in which the species was recorded as present) and may therefore be inappropriate for comparisons of model accuracy between species or regions (McPherson, Jetz & Rogers 2004, Allouche et al. 2006).

TSS, the true skill statistic (Allouche et al. 2006). TSS is defined as $\text{sensitivity} + \text{specificity} - 1$, and corrects for Kappa's dependency on prevalence. TSS compares the number of correct forecasts, minus those attributable to random guessing, to that of a hypothetical set of perfect forecasts. Like kappa, TSS takes into account both omission and commission errors, and success as a result of random guessing, and ranges from -1 to +1, where +1 indicates perfect agreement and values of zero or less indicate a performance no better than random (Allouche et al. 2006).

An ensemble model was created by first rejecting poorly performing algorithms with relatively extreme low AUC values and then averaging the predictions of the remaining algorithms, weighted by their AUC. To identify poorly performing algorithms, AUC values were converted into modified z-scores based on their difference to the median and the median absolute deviation across all algorithms (Iglewicz & Hoaglin, 1993). Algorithms with $z < -2$ were rejected. In this way, ensemble projections were made for each dataset and then averaged to give an overall suitability, as well as its standard deviation. The projections were then classified into suitable and unsuitable regions using the 'minROCDist' method, which minimizes the distance between the ROC plot and the upper left corner of the plot (point (0,1)).

We also produced limiting factor maps for Europe following Elith et al. (2010). For this, projections were made separately with each individual variable fixed at a near-optimal value. These were chosen

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

as the median values at the occurrence grid cells. Then, the most strongly limiting factors were identified as the one resulting in the highest increase in suitability in each grid cell.

Results

The ensemble model suggested that suitability for *Phytolacca americana* was most strongly determined by Climatic moisture index (CMI), accounting for 40.1% of variation explained, followed by Mean temperature of the warmest quarter (Bio10) (31.2%) and Minimum temperature of the coldest month (Bio6) (28.8%) (Table 1, Figure 3).

Table 1. Summary of the cross-validation predictive performance (AUC, Kappa, TSS) and variable importance of the fitted model algorithms and the ensemble (AUC-weighted average of the best performing algorithms). Results are the average from models fitted to 10 different background samples of the data.

Algorithm	AUC	Kappa	TSS	Used in the ensemble	variable importance (%)		
					Climatic moisture index (CMI)	Mean temperature of the warmest quarter (Bio10)	Minimum temperature of the coldest month (Bio6)
GLM	0.902	0.611	0.647	yes	42	32	26
GAM	0.902	0.609	0.644	yes	40	30	30
ANN	0.906	0.607	0.653	yes	38	32	30
GBM	0.906	0.604	0.649	yes	41	30	29
MARS	0.901	0.603	0.642	yes	43	30	27
RF	0.842	0.480	0.580	no	36	36	29
Maxent	0.901	0.593	0.635	yes	35	34	30
Ensemble	0.906	0.608	0.650		40	31	29

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Figure 3. Partial response plots from the fitted models. Thin coloured lines show responses from the algorithms in the ensemble, while the thick black line is their ensemble. In each plot, other model variables are held at their median value in the training data. Some of the divergence among algorithms is because of their different treatment of interactions among variables.

(a) Projected suitability

(b) Standard deviation in projected suitability

Figure 4. (a) Projected global suitability for *Phytolacca americana* establishment in the current climate. For visualisation, the projection has been aggregated to a 0.5 x 0.5 degree resolution, by taking the maximum suitability of constituent higher resolution grid cells. Values > 0.28 may be suitable for the species. Grey areas have climatic conditions outside the range of the training data and were excluded from the projection. (b) Uncertainty in the ensemble projections, expressed as the among-algorithm standard deviation in predicted suitability, averaged across the 10 datasets.

Figure 5. (a) Projected current suitability for *Phytolacca americana* establishment in Europe and the Mediterranean region. Grey areas have climatic conditions outside the range of the training data and were excluded from the projection. (b) Uncertainty in the ensemble projections, expressed as the among-algorithm standard deviation in predicted suitability, averaged across the 10 datasets.

Figure 6. The most strongly limiting factors for *Phytolacca americana* establishment estimated by the model in Europe and the Mediterranean region in current climatic conditions.

Figure 7. (a) Projected suitability for *Phytolacca americana* establishment in Europe and the Mediterranean region in the 2070s under climate change scenario RCP2.6, equivalent to Figure 5. Grey areas have climatic conditions outside the range of the training data and were excluded from the

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2014-2020

projection. (b) Uncertainty in the ensemble projections, expressed as the among-algorithm standard deviation in predicted suitability, averaged across the 10 datasets.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Figure 8. (a) Projected suitability for *Phytolacca americana* establishment in Europe and the Mediterranean region in the 2070s under climate change scenario RCP4.5, equivalent to Figure 5. Grey areas have climatic conditions outside the range of the training data and were excluded from the projection. (b) Uncertainty in the ensemble projections, expressed as the among-algorithm standard deviation in predicted suitability, averaged across the 10 datasets.

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Figure 9. Variation in projected suitability for *Phytolacca americana* establishment among Biogeographical regions of Europe (Bundesamt für Naturschutz (BfN), 2003). The bar plots show the proportion of grid cells in each region classified as suitable in the current climate and projected climate for the 2070s under two RCP emissions scenarios. The location of each region is also shown. The Arctic and Macaronesian biogeographical regions are not part of the study area, but are included for completeness (although unsuitable for all scenarios for this species).

Figure 10. Variation in projected suitability for *Phytolacca americana* establishment among European Union countries. The bar plots show the proportion of grid cells in each country classified as suitable in the current climate and projected climate for the 2070s under two RCP emissions scenarios.

To remove spatial recording biases, the selection of the background sample was weighted by the density of Tracheophyta records on the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). While this is preferable to not accounting for recording bias at all, it may not provide the perfect measure of recording bias.

There was substantial variation among modelling algorithms in the partial response plots (Figure 3). In part this will reflect their different treatment of interactions among variables. Since partial plots are made with other variables held at their median, there may be values of a particular variable at which this does not provide a realistic combination of variables to predict from.

Other variables potentially affecting the distribution of the species, such as land cover were not included in the model.

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Verbesina encelioides

**Risk assessment template developed under the "Adequate management of invasive species in Romania, in accordance with EU Regulation 1143/2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species" POIM2014+ 120008
Contract No 231/27.11.2018**

Name of organism: *Verbesina encelioides* (Cav.) Benth. & Hook.f. ex A.Gray

Author(s) of the assessment:

Mihaela Urziceanu, University of Bucharest/Faculty of Biology, Bucharest, Romania

Risk Assessment Area: The risk assessment area is the territory of the European Union 27

Date of completion: 10/06/2023

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Contents

SECTION A – Organism Information and Screening	258
SECTION B – Detailed assessment	278
1 PROBABILITY OF INTRODUCTION AND ENTRY	278
2 PROBABILITY OF ESTABLISHMENT	288
3 PROBABILITY OF SPREAD	294
4 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT	307
Biodiversity and ecosystem impacts	307
Ecosystem Services impacts	310
Economic impacts	312
Social and human health impacts	314
Other impacts	315
RISK SUMMARIES	317
REFERENCES	320
ANNEX I Scoring of Likelihoods of Events	323
ANNEX II Scoring of Magnitude of Impacts	324
ANNEX III Scoring of Confidence Levels	326
ANNEX IV CBD pathway categorisation scheme	327
ANNEX V Ecosystem services classification (CICES V5.1, simplified) and examples	328
ANNEX VI EU Biogeographic Regions and MSFD Subregions	332
ANNEX VII Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/968 of 30 April 2018	333

SECTION A – Organism Information and Screening

A1. Identify the organism. Is it clearly a single taxonomic entity and can it be adequately distinguished from other entities of the same rank?

including the following elements:

the taxonomic family, order and class to which the species belongs;

the scientific name and author of the species, as well as a list of the most common synonym names;

names used in commerce (if any)

a list of the most common subspecies, lower taxa, varieties, breeds or hybrids

As a general rule, one risk assessment should be developed for a single species. However, there may be cases where it may be justified to develop one risk assessment covering more than one species (e.g. species belonging to the same genus with comparable or identical features and impact). It shall be clearly stated if the risk assessment covers more than one species, or if it excludes or only includes certain subspecies, lower taxa, hybrids, varieties or breeds (and if so, which subspecies, lower taxa, hybrids, varieties or breeds). Any such choice must be properly justified.

Response: The risk assessment covers one species, *Verbesina encelioides* (Cav.) Benth. & Hook.f. ex A.Gray (PoW0, 2023). The species belongs to the Asteraceae family, Asterales Order and is native to U.S.A. to Mexico, Caribbean, Ecuador to S. South America (PoW0, 2023).

Verbesina encelioides is an erect, branched annual plant, reaching a height of about 30-50 cm, but sometimes reaching up to 130 cm (Hansen 1976; Anastasiu et al., 2009). The leaves are simple, with petioles, opposite below and without auricles, and alternate above, with toothed edges and fine white hairs on the underside. The flower heads resemble small sunflowers and can be solitary or in clusters of up to three heads (up to 42 flower heads per plant) (Anastasiu et al., 2009). The ligulate florets are yellow to bright-yellow and measure 10-15, 15-25 mm in length, with 3 lobes at the apex. The tubular florets are also yellow. The achenes of the ligulate florets are triangular, tuberculate, blackish, measuring 4.2 mm, while the achenes of the tubular florets are flattened, white-winged, covered with fine hairs, blackish, measuring 5-5.5 mm in length and 4-4.5 mm in width. Each flower head can produce approximately 100 flattened achenes and 10 triangular achenes. *Verbesina encelioides* has no closely related species in the Romanian flora, making it easily distinguishable from other taxa (Anastasiu et al., 2009).

Taxonomy (Euro+Med 2006+)

Kingdom	<i>Plantae</i>
Phylum	<i>Tracheophyta</i>
Class	<i>Magnoliopsida</i>
Order	<i>Asterales</i>
Family	<i>Asteraceae</i>
Genus	<i>Verbesina</i>
Species	<i>Verbesina encelioides</i> (Cav.) Benth. & Hook.f. ex A.Gray

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Synonyms (Euro+Med 2006+, PoWo 2023)

Ximenesia encelioides Cav.

Encelia albescens A.Gray

Pallasia serratifolia Sm.

Verbesina australis Baker

Verbesina encelioides var. *cana* B.L.Rob. & Greenm.

Verbesina encelioides subsp. *exauriculata* (B.L.Rob. & Greenm.) J.R.Coleman

Verbesina encelioides var. *exauriculata* Rob. & Greenm.

Verbesina encelioides var. *exauriculata* B.L.Rob. & Greenm.

Verbesina exauriculata (B.L.Rob. & Greenm.) Cockerell

Verbesina microptera (DC.) Herter

Verbesina scabra Benth.

Ximenesia australis Hook. & Arn. ex DC.

Ximenesia encelioides var. *exauriculata* (B.L.Rob. & Greenm.) Mohlenbr

Ximenesia encelioides var. *pachyptera* DC.

Ximenesia exauriculata (B.L.Rob. & Greenm.) Rydb.

Ximenesia microptera DC.

Common names

According to CABI (2023), EPPO (2022) common names in the European region are:

Catalan: verbesina

English: American dogweed, cowpen daisy, crownbeard

German: goldgelbe Verbesine

Hebrew: kanfon zahov, קנפון זהב

Polish: niechętek filcowaty, werbezyna filcowata

Portuguese: verbesina

Russian: вербесина энцелиевидная; ксименезия энцелиевидная

Spanish: flor de Santa Maria, girasolcito, girasoleito, girasolillo, hierba de la bruja, mirasolillo, yuyo de Santa María

Ukrainian ксименезія енцелієвидна

In Romania, the common name of this species is: Iarbă de tiță (Sîrbu & Oprea, 2011).

Most common subspecies, lower taxa, varieties, breeds or hybrids

Variations in *V. encelioides* have been observed in different environments, with slight differences noted. In Saudi Arabia, seeds obtained from plants cultivated in open and sand dune habitats were larger compared to seeds from plants grown in shaded and brick kiln habitats (Kaul and Mangal, 1987; Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

According to Feenstra and Clements, 2008, there are the following subspecies of *V. encelioides*:

Verbesina encelioides subsp. *encelioides* has semioval auricles on most leaves and acute achene wing apices, with phyllaries typically over 12 mm long. It has a smaller distribution compared to *V. encelioides* subsp. *exauriculata* and can be found in southeastern locations in North America, as well as on the Islands of Hawai'i and Puerto Rico.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Verbesina encelioides subsp. *exauriculata* has oblong auricles mainly restricted to the petioles of upper leaves and obtuse achene wing apices, with phyllaries averaging less than 12 mm long. This subspecies is widespread throughout the central and western United States, including some northern states, but is not found in Hawai'i, Puerto Rico, or the Virgin Islands. According also with Feenstra and Clements (2008), Strother (2006) did not consider *V. encelioides* subsp. *exauriculata* as taxonomically distinctive

A2. Provide information on the existence of other species that look very similar [that may be detected in the risk assessment area, either in the environment, in confinement or associated with a pathway of introduction]

Include both native and non-native species that could be confused with the species being assessed, including the following elements:

other alien species with similar invasive characteristics, to be avoided as substitute species (in this case preparing a risk assessment for more than one species together may be considered);

other alien species without similar invasive characteristics, potential substitute species;

native species, potential misidentification and mis-targeting

Response: *Verbesina encelioides* is an erect annual plant that can reach heights of 30 cm up to 160 cm. It possesses a taproot system. The leaves of this species are either toothed or lobed and exhibit two distinct growth patterns. The lower leaves are arranged in an opposite fashion and have a triangular shape, while the upper leaves are alternate and lance-shaped. On the undersides of the leaves and on the stem, you will find fine white hairs. The flower heads are vibrant yellow and appear on elongated stalks, resembling small sunflowers. They typically measure 2.5 to 5 cm in diameter. The seeds of *V. encelioides* are grayish-brown achenes, flat and winged along the margins. They have a length ranging from 5.4 mm to 6.7 mm and a width of 3.1 mm to 3.6 mm. (EPPO, 2012).

Existence of other non-native species that look very similar

Non-native similar-looking species can be distinguished by the following differences (CABI 2023):

Encelia spp. *V. encelioides* bears a resemblance to other species within the Asteraceae family, such as those found in the genus *Encelia*. However, unlike *Encelia*, *V. encelioides* emits an unpleasant odor, and its stems are covered in dense, short hairs. Additionally, the majority of its leaves are arranged alternately.

Verbesina alternifolia (Wingstem): This native North American species closely resembles *V. encelioides*. The flowerheads are 6-8 rays, slightly larger in size. Leaves are longer (10-25+ cm) and narrower compared to their width, opposite in seedlings, but usually alternate in mature plants higher up the stem. Seedheads are globe-shaped. Awns (bristle-like projections) stick out in all directions except towards the base. Seeds have wings.

Verbesina occidentalis (Crownbeard): Tall perennial native to the southeastern US. Flowerheads are 1-3 rays, occasionally more or none. Leaves are shorter (6-12cm) and stout, often tapering to a point but can have a simple acute angle or be slightly rounded at the tip. Leaves and branching are opposite throughout the plant, especially near the main stem. More numerous, smaller flowerheads (typically

20-100 or more) on mature plants. Seedheads are upright and cup-shaped at the base. Awns mostly point in the same direction as the seedhead. Seeds are ridged, but not winged.

Existence of other native species that look very similar

V. encelioides bears resemblance to *Helianthus annuus*; however, distinguishing factors include the presence of opposite leaves on the lower part of the plant and substantially smaller heads (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

A3. Does a relevant earlier risk assessment exist? Give details of any previous risk assessment, including the final scores and its validity in relation to the risk assessment area.

Response: No previous risk assessment has been conducted for the specified risk assessment area.

Outside of the risk assessment area

Australian/New Zealand Weed Risk Assessment adapted for Hawaii.

USA - Hawaii

The protocols are not intended to provide a field evaluation of the species' current distribution and impact in Australia, Hawaii, the Pacific islands, Florida, or the continental U.S. Instead, they are primarily based on available scientific literature and documented sources to predict the potential invasiveness of the species in these regions. It's important to note that the assessments do not directly assess the species' existing presence or the extent of its impact in those areas. While they generally offer a reliable indication of a species' invasiveness, they cannot anticipate its behavior under all circumstances. The risk assessments conducted for Australia, Hawaii, and the Pacific islands, as well as for Florida in the United States, utilize a scoring system to determine the potential invasiveness of a species. It's important to note that in some Australian assessments, a score of 6 may be indicated as "reject." However, the score could actually be slightly higher than 6 but less than 7, or the environmental or agricultural scores may exceed 6, leading to the "reject" recommendation. For Pacific and Florida risk assessments, scores ranging from 1 to 6 undergo a secondary evaluation to determine a final recommendation.

According to the Hawaiian Ecosystems at Risk project (HEAR, 2023) *Verbesina encelioides* is assessed as High risk, score: 19

(http://www.hear.org/pier/wra/pacific/verbesina_encelioides_htmlwra.htm)

The relevant answers are:

issue	answer
Broad climate suitability (environmental versatility)	yes
Native or naturalized in regions with tropical or subtropical climates	yes
Does the species have a history of repeated introductions outside its natural range?	yes
Naturalized beyond native range $y = 1 * multiplier$	yes
Garden/amenity/disturbance weed $y = 1 * multiplier$	yes

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Agricultural/forestry/horticultural weed $y = 2 * multiplier$	yes
Toxic to animals	yes
Tolerates a wide range of soil conditions (or limestone conditions if not a volcanic island)	yes
Produces viable seed.	yes
Hybridizes naturally	yes
Self-compatible or apomictic	yes
Propagules likely to be dispersed unintentionally	yes
Propagules dispersed intentionally by people	yes
Propagules likely to disperse as a produce contaminant	yes
Propagules adapted to wind dispersal	yes
Propagules dispersed by other animals (externally)	yes
Prolific seed production (>1000/m ²)	yes
Evidence that a persistent propagule bank is formed (>1 yr)	yes
Well controlled by herbicides	yes

Hawaii has different climatic conditions than regions in the EU, though basic information on e.g. biology and habitat preferences of the species, can be taken into account. The assessment of e.g. invasiveness has to be reviewed accordingly to the different conditions in the risk assessment area.

Australia - Victoria

The Weed Risk Assessment (WRA) developed by the

https://vro.agriculture.vic.gov.au/dpi/vro/vrosite.nsf/pages/impact_crown_beard

Accordingly, VRO (Victorian Resources Online) (2023) conducted an impact assessment of *Verbesina encelioides*. During the assessment of biological data, criteria are assigned intensity ratings (criteria ratings) of high (H), medium-high (MH), medium (M), medium-low (ML), and low (L), to score each species.

Relevant high (H) respectively medium-high (MH) rated criterions in the impact assessment are:

Criteria	Establishment	Rating
Reduce biomass	<i>V. encelioides</i> prevents the growth of less aggressive native plants. Allelopathic effects may also contribute to the species' dominant coverage and success in inhibiting native plant growth. It may slightly decrease biomass.	MH
Benefits fauna	No evidence suggests that <i>V. encelioides</i> provides any benefit for indigenous fauna	H
Injurious to fauna	Livestock consuming <i>V. encelioides</i> may experience poisoning, leading to symptoms such as dullness and loss of appetite. Severe cases can be fatal due to extensive organ lesions and internal bleeding. <i>V. encelioides</i> is not commonly consumed by livestock unless food availability is limited. Sheep are more susceptible, while cattle and pigs are less affected (Parsons and Cuthbertson 2001). The dense growth of <i>V. encelioides</i> can pose a risk to ground-nesting and burrowing bird species, potentially causing entanglement or trapping	H
Impact on agriculture yield	In the USA, <i>V. encelioides</i> is considered a troublesome weed due to its rapid infestation of fallow peanut fields. It has a competitive impact on peanut yield, with weed interference shown to reduce peanut yield by 50%. Additionally, it poses a potential risk to livestock due to the ingestion of toxins within the plant (as described above). In India, <i>V. encelioides</i> infests fields of maize, pearl millet, wheat, rice, peanut, gram, rape, and mustard. In the Arabian Peninsula, it has been recorded as "completely	H

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2014-2020

	overwhelming the crop.	
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A4. Where is the organism native?

including the following elements:

an indication of the continent or part of a continent, climatic zone and habitat where the species is naturally occurring

if applicable, indicate whether the species could naturally spread into the risk assessment area

Verbesina encelioides is native to Alabama, Argentina (Northeast, Northwest, South), Arizona, Arkansas, Bahamas, Bolivia, California, Chile (North), Colombia, Colorado, Cuba, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Florida, Georgia, Haiti, Illinois, Iowa, Kansas, Louisiana, Mexico (Central, Gulf, Northeast, Northwest, Southeast, Southwest), Missouri, Montana, Nebraska, Nevada, New Mexico, New York, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Paraguay, Pennsylvania, Puerto Rico, Rhode Island, South Carolina, South Dakota, Tennessee, Texas, Turks and Caicos Islands, Uruguay, Utah, and Wyoming (POWO, 2022). It is also indicated as native to the southwestern USA, Mexico, and South America by multiple sources (Shluker, 1999; Carr, 2012 as cited by CABI, 2023). However, there are some doubts about its specific native origins within certain states in the USA and South America (Coleman, 1974). The native range is generally considered to include most of the USA and Mexico, reaching as far east as Florida and as far north as Michigan (CABI, 2023).

A5. What is the global non-native distribution of the organism outside the risk assessment area?

Response: Table 1 and Figure 1 give an overview of the global native and non-native distribution outside the risk assessment area. Considering the native range in southwestern USA, Mexico and South America (CABI, 2023), available spatial and non-spatial data describe the non-native distribution of *V. encelioides* covering parts of Africa (Algeria, Botswana, Cape Provinces, Egypt, Ethiopia, Mauritius, Morocco, Namibia, Rodrigues, Réunion, South Africa, Sudan, West Siberia, Zimbabwe), Asia (India, Pakistan, Palestine, Saudi Arabia, Sinai), Europa (Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Norway, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine), Oceania: Australia (Queensland, New South Wales, South Australia, Victoria), Line Islands, New Guinea, Northern Territory (CABI 2023, POWO 2023, Anastasiu et al. , 2009).

Figure 1 Native range and global non-native occurrence records of *Verbesina encelioides* outside the risk assessment area (map designed by POWO - 2023/07/18)

Table 1 countries with *Verbesina encelioides* occurrences mentioned

Continent/region	country	general remarks	source
Africa	Algeria	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Euro+Med 2006+
	Benin	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023); GBIF (2012)
	Botswana	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023); Feenstra and Clements (2008)
	Egypt	Present/ Introduced/ Naturalized	CABI (2023), Euro+Med 2006+
	Ethiopia	Present/ Introduced / naturalized	CABI (2023); Witt and Luke (2017), Feenstra and Clements (2008)
	Mauritius	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022)
	Morocco	Present/ Introduced / naturalized	CABI (2023), Feenstra and Clements (2008)
	Namibia	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Feenstra and Clements (2008)
	Réunion	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022)
	Senegal	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), GBIF (2012)
	Somalia	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), GBIF (2012)
	South Africa	Present/	CABI (2023), Holm et al. (1979)

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Continent/region	country	general remarks	source
		Introduced/Widespread	
	Sudan	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), GBIF (2012)
	Zimbabwe	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Seebens et al. (2017)
Asia	India	Present/ Introduced/ Widespread	CABI (2023), Holm et al. (1979)
	- Delhi	Present/ Introduced/ Widespread	CABI (2023), Inderjit et al. (1999)
	- Haryana	Present/ Introduced/ Widespread	CABI (2023), Kaul and Mangal (1987)
	- Punjab	Present/ Introduced/ Widespread	CABI (2023); Coleman (1966)
	Israel	Present/ Introduced/ Widespread	CABI (2023); Dafni and Heller (1982)
	Jordan	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Euro+Med 2006+
	Saudi Arabia	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023)
	United Arab Emirates	Present/ Introduced/ Few occurrences	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022)
	Yemen	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), GBIF (2012)
Europe	Austria	Present/ Introduced/ Few occurrences	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022), Seebens et al. (2017)
	Belgium	Present/ Introduced	Euro+Med (2012), Seebens et al. (2017)
	Czechia	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Euro+Med 2006+
	Denmark	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Tutin et al. (1976), Euro+Med 2006+, EPPO (2022)
	France	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Euro+Med 2006+
	Germany	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Tutin et al. (1976), Euro+Med 2006+, EPPO (2022)
	Norway	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Euro+Med 2006+, Seebens et al. (2017)
	Poland	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Euro+Med (2012)
	Romania	Present/ Naturalized	Anastasiu et al. (2009)
	Spain	Present/ Introduced/ Widespread	CABI (2023), Euro+Med (2012), GBIF (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Canary Islands	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Euro+Med (2012)

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Continent/region	country	general remarks	source
	Sweden	Absent, Unconfirmed presence record(s)	CABI (2023), Tutin et al. (1976), GBIF (2012), EPPO (2022)
	Switzerland	Absent, Unconfirmed presence record(s)	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022), Tutin et al. (1976)
	Ukraine	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Seebens et al. (2017), Euro+Med (2012)
	United Kingdom	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Euro+Med (2012), EPPO (2022)
North America	Bahamas	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Feenstra and Clements (2008)
	Cuba	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Feenstra and Clements (2008)
	Dominican Republic	Present/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Feenstra and Clements (2008)
	Mexico	Present/ Native/ Widespread/	CABI (2023), GBIF (2012)
	Puerto Rico	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), Feenstra and Clements (2008)
	United States	Present/ Native/ Widespread/	CABI (2023), GBIF (2012)
	- Alabama	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Arizona	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Arkansas	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- California	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Colorado	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Florida	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Georgia	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Hawaii	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Illinois	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Iowa	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
- Kansas	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)	

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Continent/region	country	general remarks	source
			(2022)
	- Louisiana	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Maryland	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Massachusetts	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Michigan	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Missouri	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Nebraska	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Nevada	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- New Mexico	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- New York	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- North Carolina	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- North Dakota	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Oklahoma	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Pennsylvania	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Rhode Island	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- South Carolina	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- South Dakota	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Tennessee	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Texas	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
	- Utah	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Continent/region	country	general remarks	source
			(2022)
	- Wyoming	Present/ Native	CABI (2023), USDA-NRCS (2012), EPPO (2022)
Oceania	Australia	Present	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022), GBIF (2012)
	- New South Wales	Present/ Widespread/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Oelrichs and Valley (1981), EPPO (2022)
	- Northern Territory	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022)
	- Queensland	Present/ Widespread/ Introduced	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022), Osten et al. (2007), Oelrichs and Valley (1981)
	- South Australia	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022)
	- Victoria	Present/ Widespread/ Introduced	CABI (2023), Oelrichs and Valley (1981), EPPO (2022)
	- Western Australia	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023), EPPO (2022)
	United States Minor Outlying Islands - Midway Islands	Present / Introduced/ Invasive	CABI (2023), PIER (2013)
South America	Argentina	Present/ Widespread/ invasive	CABI (2023); EPPO (2022), GBIF (2012), Lopez et al. (1996)
	Bolivia	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023); GBIF (2012)
	Brazil - Rio de Janeiro	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023); GBIF (2012) Coleman (1966)
	Chile	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023); Seebens et al. (2017), GBIF (2012)
	- Easter Island	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023); Shluker (1999)
	Colombia	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023); GBIF (2012)
	Ecuador	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023); GBIF (2012)
	Paraguay	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023); GBIF (2012)
	Uruguay	Present / Introduced	CABI (2023); GBIF (2012)

A6. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area has the species been recorded and where is it established? The information needs to be given separately for recorded (including casual or transient occurrences) and established occurrences. “Established” means the process of an alien species successfully producing viable offspring with the likelihood of continued survival¹⁶.

¹⁶ Convention on Biological Diversity, Decision VI/23

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

A6a. Recorded: List regions

A6b. Established: List regions

Freshwater / terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic

Marine regions:

Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea

Marine subregions:

Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel, Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast, Western Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Central Mediterranean Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea.

Comment on the sources of information on which the response is based and discuss any uncertainty in the response.

For delimitation of EU biogeographical regions please refer to <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2> (see also Annex VI).

For delimitation of EU marine regions and subregions consider the Marine Strategy Framework Directive areas; please refer to <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/msfd-regions-and-subregions/technical-document/pdf> (see also Annex VI).

Response: Based on the delimitation of EU biogeographical regions <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2> and the distribution information available to CABI 2023 and table no. 1 above, we made a classification of *Verbesina encelioides* in the specified bioregions, based on these criteria:

For *Recorded appearance* we take in the consideration the Present/ Introduced criteria

For *Established Appearances* we take in the consideration Naturalized/Widespread/Invasive criteria:

Taking into account the delineation of EU biogeographical regions as provided by <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2>, along with the distribution information available from CABI 2023 and the table presented above, we have classified *Verbesina encelioides* in the specified bioregions according to the following criteria:

Recorded Appearances: We considered the criteria of Present/Introduced.

Established Appearances: We considered the criteria of Naturalized/Widespread/Invasive.

The Arctic, Anatolian and Macaronesian biogeographical regions are not part of the risk assessment area, but included for completeness. Table 2 give an overview about occurrences of the species in the biogeographical regions. In the Black Sea, Boreal, Pannonian and Steppic regions, no occurrence data is available.

Response (6a): *Verbesina encelioides* is recorded in the Alpine, Atlantic, Continental and Mediterranean biogeographical regions. No recorded occurrence data is available for Black Sea, Boreal, Pannonian and Steppic biogeographical regions. However, according to the presence data in

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Romania for the species *V. encelioides*, it appears that it is also present in the steppic bioregion (Anastasiu et al., 2009).

Response (6b): According to the available information, *V. encelioides* can be considered as “established” in the Atlantic, Continental, Mediterranean biogeographical regions.

Table 2 biogeographical regions with recorded/established *Verbesina encelioides* occurrences (grey cell – biogeographical region not covered by the risk assessment area)

biogeographical region	recorded	established	source of recorded occurrences	source of established occurrences
Alpine	Yes	No	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Anatolian	No	No	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Arctic	No	No	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Atlantic	Yes	Yes	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Black Sea	No	No	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Boreal	NO	No	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Continental	Yes	Yes	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Macaronesian	Yes	Yes	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Mediterranean	Yes	Yes	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Pannonian	No	No	CABI (2023)	CABI (2023)
Steppic	Yes	No	Anastasiu et al. (2009)	CABI (2023)

A7. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area could the species establish in the future under current climate and under foreseeable climate change? The information needs to be given separately for current climate and under foreseeable climate change conditions.

A7a. Current climate: List regions

A7b. Future climate: List regions

With regard to EU biogeographic and marine (sub)regions, see above.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the risk assessment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

change scenarios, as long as an assessment with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response (7a):

Table 3 Biogeographic regions and suitability under current conditions

Biogeographic region	likeliness	confidence
Alpine		
Anatolian		
Arctic		
Atlantic		
Black Sea		
Boreal		
Continental		
Macaronesian		
Mediterranean		
Pannonian		
Steppic		

Response (7b):

Table 4 Biogeographic regions and suitability under projected scenario conditions for the 2070s

biogeographic region	Scenario RCP 2.6		Scenario RCP 4.5	
	likeliness	confidence	likeliness	confidence
Alpine				
Anatolian				
Arctic				
Atlantic				
Black Sea				
Boreal				
Continental				
Macaronesian				
Mediterranean				
Pannonian				
Steppic				

A8. In which EU Member States has the species been recorded and in which EU Member States has it established? List them with an indication of the timeline of observations. The information needs be given separately for recorded and established occurrences.

A8a. Recorded: List Member States

A8b. Established: List Member States

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden

The description of the invasion history of the species shall include information on countries invaded and an indication of the timeline of the first observations, establishment and spread.

Response: Table 5 give an overview about occurrences of the species in the EU Member States. Sources of information are CABI (2023) and national floristic or invasive species references. An indication of the first observation is not possible for every member state but given if possible.

Response (8a): *Verbesina encelioides* is recorded in 9 out of 27 Member States (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, France, Germany, Poland, Romania, Spain).

Response (8b): Based upon the available data, *Verbesina encelioides* can be assessed as established in two Member States (Romania and Spain).

Table 5 EU member states with recorded/established *Verbesina encelioides* occurrences

country	recorded	established	source recorded	source established	general remarks	timeline of observations
Austria	Yes	No	CABI (2023); EPPO (2022); Seebens et al. (2017)	-	-	-
Belgium	Yes	No	CABI (2023); Manual of the Alien Plants of Belgium (2022); Seebens et al. (2017).	-	casual alien	First reported 1950
Bulgaria	No	No				
Croatia	No	No				
Cyprus	No	No				
Czechia	Yes	No	Euro+Med (2012)	-	Cultivated	-
Denmark	Yes	No	Tutin et al. (1976); Euro+Med (2012); EPPO (2022)		Cultivated	
Estonia	No	No				
Finland	No	No				

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

country	recorded	established	source recorded	source established	general remarks	timeline of observations
France	Yes	No	Euro+Med (2012)		Casual alien	
Germany	Yes	No	Tutin et al. (1976); Euro+Med (2012); EPPO (2022)		Casual alien	
Greece	No	No				
Hungary	No	No				
Ireland	No	No				
Italy	No	No				
Latvia	No	No				
Lithuania	No	No				
Luxembourg	No	No				
Malta	No	No				
Netherlands	No	No				
Poland	Yes	No	Euro+Med (2012)		Casual alien	
Portugal	No	No				
Romania	Yes	Yes	Anastasiu et al. (2009)	Naturalized	Cultivated	First reported 2009
Slovakia	No	No				
Slovenia	No	No				
Spain	Yes	Yes	Euro+Med (2012); GBIF (2012); EPPO (2022)		Naturalized	Naturalized alien
Sweden	No	No	Tutin et al. (1976); GBIF (2012); EPPO (2022)	Tutin et al. (1976); GBIF (2012); EPPO (2022)	Absent, Unconfirmed presence record(s)	Absent, Unconfirmed presence record(s)

A9. In which EU Member States could the species establish in the future under current climate and under foreseeable climate change? The information needs to be given separately for current climate and under foreseeable climate change conditions.

A9a. Current climate: List Member States

A9b. Future climate: List Member States

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

With regard to EU Member States, see above.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the risk assessment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

Response (9a): EU Members States with suitability under current conditions

country	likeliness	confidence
Austria		
Belgium		
Bulgaria		
Croatia		
Cyprus		
Czechia		
Denmark		
Estonia		
Finland		
France		
Germany		
Greece		
Hungary		
Ireland		
Italy		
Latvia		
Lithuania		
Luxembourg		
Malta		
Netherlands		
Poland		
Portugal		
Romania		
Slovakia		
Slovenia		

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

country	likeliness	confidence
Spain		
Sweden		

Response (9b): EU Members States with suitability under projected conditions for the 2070s

country	Scenario RCP 2.6		Scenario RCP 4.5	
	likeliness	confidence	likeliness	confidence
Austria				
Belgium				
Bulgaria				
Croatia				
Cyprus				
Czechia				
Denmark				
Estonia				
Finland				
France				
Germany				
Greece				
Hungary				
Ireland				
Italy				
Latvia				
Lithuania				
Luxembourg				
Malta				
Netherlands				
Poland				
Portugal				
Romania				
Slovakia				
Slovenia				
Spain				
Sweden				

A10. Is the organism known to be invasive (i.e. to threaten or adversely impact upon biodiversity and related ecosystem services) anywhere outside the risk assessment area?

Response: According to CABI (2023), *V. encelioides* is known to be invasive and has adverse impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services. It has been observed to be invasive in the northern Hawaiian Islands, where it displaces native plant species and negatively affects breeding colonies of marine birds (CABI, 2023). It is also a dominant invasive species on Midway Atoll (PIER, 2013). In addition,

V. encelioides invades agricultural crops, especially peanuts, in the United States, Argentina, Australia, and India, and its allelopathic properties may interfere with crop growth (CABI, 2023).

The species has a significant impact on habitats, particularly when invading oceanic islands like the Hawaiian Islands, where it forms monotypic stands, displaces native vegetation, and disrupts nesting behavior of marine birds (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). It has been observed to negatively affect native plant species, such as *Scaveola sericea* and *Ipomea pescaprae* (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

In India, *V. encelioides* is widespread, but its specific impact on native vegetation is not well-documented (Kaul and Mangal, 1987).

Regarding biodiversity, *V. encelioides* has been found to affect the nesting activities of marine birds, trapping hatchlings and young birds with its entangling branches in the northwest Hawaiian islands (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

Research on the impact of *V. encelioides* on carbon pools, nutrient cycling, and microorganism populations is limited or non-existent (CABI, 2023).

In the Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia, a study conducted in 2020 confirmed adverse consequences on native plant biodiversity, particularly at low altitudes, roadside areas, and crop fields. The high density of *V. encelioides* significantly reduced the diversity of other plant communities (Fufa et al., 2022).

Another study demonstrated the allelopathic potential of *V. encelioides*, with its aqueous extracts inhibiting the growth and photosynthetic parameters of co-occurring species in a concentration-dependent manner (Mehal et al., 2022).

A11. In which biogeographic region(s) or marine subregion(s) in the risk assessment area has the species shown signs of invasiveness? Indicate the area endangered by the organism as detailed as possible.

Freshwater / terrestrial biogeographic regions:

Alpine, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Mediterranean, Pannonian, Steppic

Marine regions:

Baltic Sea, North-east Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea

Marine subregions:

Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel, Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast, Western Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Central Mediterranean Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea

Response: *Verbesina encelioides* exhibits a widespread distribution in parts of the Mediterranean biogeographical region (Table 2). There are documented signs of invasiveness in this region, especially in Spain (CABI 2023; POWO 2023; GBIF 2012) and Romania (Anastasiu et al., 2009). In Romania, *V. encelioides* has also shown signs of invasiveness in the steppic biogeographic region of Dobrogea in Romania, specifically in the central Dobrogea region. It has been reported in several localities, including Sarighiol de Deal (Tulcea County) and Râmnicul de Jos, Grădina, and Cheia (Constanța County). The plant has become fully naturalized in these localities, covering large areas of

276

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

disturbed habitats along roadsides, in fallow lands, and lucerne fields. The region has a steppe climate with dry and hot summers (Anastasiu et al., 2009).

A12. In which EU Member States has the species shown signs of invasiveness? Indicate the area endangered by the organism as detailed as possible.

Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden

Response: There are documented signs of invasiveness in Spain (Euro+Med, 2012; GBIF, 2012, EPPO 2022) and Romania (Anastasiu et al. 2009).

A13. Describe any known socio-economic benefits of the organism.

including the following elements:

Description of known uses for the species, including a list and description of known uses in the risk assessment area and third countries, if relevant.

Description of social and economic benefits deriving from those uses, including a description of the environmental, social and economic relevance of each of those uses and an indication of associated beneficiaries, quantitatively and/or qualitatively depending on what information is available.

If the information available is not sufficient to provide a description of those benefits for the entire risk assessment area, qualitative data or different case studies from across the risk assessment area or third countries shall be used, if available.

Response: There is limited information available regarding the socio-economic benefits of *Verbesina encelioides* in the risk assessment area. According to Anastasiu et al. (2009), although *V. encelioides* is a beautiful plant, the population in Dobrogea, Romania does not cultivate it due to its unpleasant odor.

However, it has been reported that the species has been used in horticulture and for medicinal purposes. The floral extracts of *V. encelioides* have been found to contain flavonol 3,7-diglycosides, which have potential medicinal value as scavengers of reactive oxygen species and may help suppress oxidative DNA damage (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). The phenolic moieties present in the plant may also lower the risk of cancer, oxidized LDL cholesterol carriers, heart disease, and wrinkled skin (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

Furthermore, *V. encelioides* has been used in traditional medicine by various Native American tribes, such as the Hopi, Navajo, Kayenta, Ramah, and Zuni tribes. Different parts of the plant have been used to treat fever, itching, spider bites, stomachaches, cramps, worms, rattlesnake bites, hemorrhoids, ulcers, digestive disorders, and as a soap and food source (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). Extracts of the plant have also been reported to have anti-inflammatory properties useful for treating gum sores or hemorrhoids (Ledlow, 1999, as cited in Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

Additionally, *V. encelioides* serves as a food source for the bordered patch butterfly (*Chlosyne lacinia*). The butterfly feeds on the nectar of the plant's flowers and lays its eggs on the underside of the leaves. The caterpillars consume the leaves and stems of *V. encelioides* during their development (Struttman, 2004 as cited in Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

277

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APELOR ȘI PĂDURILOR

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MANAGEMENTUL
SPECIILOR INVAZIVE
DIN ROMÂNIA

SECTION B – Detailed assessment

Important instructions:

In the case of lack of information the assessors are requested to use a standardized answer: “No information has been found.” In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

With regard to the scoring of the likelihood of events or the magnitude of impacts see Annexes I and II.

With regard to the confidence levels, see Annex III.

Highlight the selected response score and confidence level in bold but keep the other scores in normal text (so that the selected score is evident in the final document).

1 PROBABILITY OF INTRODUCTION AND ENTRY

Important instructions:

Introduction is the movement of the species into the risk assessment area (it may be either in captive conditions and/or in the environment, depending on the relevant pathways).

Entry is the release/escape/arrival in the environment, i.e. occurrence in the wild

Introduction and entry may coincide for species entering through pathways such as “corridor” or “unaided”, but it also may differ. If different, please consider all relevant pathways, both for the introduction into the risk assessment area and the entry in the environment.

For each described pathway, in each of the questions below, ensure that there are separate comments explicitly addressing both the “introduction” and “entry” where applicable and as appropriate. The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD) should be used (see Annex IV). For detailed explanations of the CBD pathway classification scheme consult the IUCN/CEH guidance document¹⁷ and the provided key to pathways¹⁸.

For organisms which are already present (recorded or established) in the risk assessment area, the likelihood of introduction and entry should be scored as “very likely” by default.

Repeated (independent) introductions and entries at separate locations in the risk assessment area should be considered here (see Qu. 1.7).

Qu. 1.1. List relevant pathways through which the organism could be introduced into the risk assessment area and/or enter into the environment. Where possible give details about the

¹⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f8627bbc-1f15-11eb-b57e-01aa75ed71a1>

¹⁸ <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/0aeba7f1-c8c2-45a1-9ba3-bcb91a9f039d/TSSR-2016-010%20CBD%20pathways%20key%20full%20only.pdf>

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

specific origins and end points of the pathways as well as a description of any associated commodities.

For each pathway answer questions 1.2 to 1.8 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than one pathway, e.g. 1.2a, 1.3a, etc. and then 1.2b, 1.3b etc. for the next pathway.

In this context a pathway is the route or mechanism of introduction and/or entry of the species.

The description of commodities with which the introduction of the species is generally associated shall include a list and description of commodities with an indication of associated risks (e.g. the volume of trade; the likelihood of a commodity being contaminated or acting as vector).

If there are no active pathways or potential future pathways this should be stated explicitly here, and there is no need to answer the questions 1.2-1.9.

(1): Horticulture (escape from confinement)

In the South-Western United States, specifically in New Mexico and Texas where *V. encelioides* is native, a few companies promote the planting of this species for its fast-growing abilities and drought resistance qualities (CABI, 2023). This pathway involves the intentional introduction of *V. encelioides* for ornamental and landscaping purposes.

(2): Ornamental purpose other than horticulture (escape from confinement)

(3): Soil importation

In the case of the Midway Atoll in Hawaii, it is suspected that *V. encelioides* arrived as seeds contaminating the 9000 tonnes of imported soil, which aimed to improve the quality of life on the island during its military base period (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). This pathway involves the unintentional introduction of *V. encelioides* through the importation of contaminated soil.

(4): Contamination through equipment

There is a possibility that *V. encelioides* seeds may have contaminated equipment, such as machinery, vehicles, or other equipment used in agricultural or landscaping activities, resulting in unintentional introductions to new areas (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

(5): Seed dispersal through hay and cereal grain

V. encelioides seeds may also be spread as contaminants in pasture hay and cereal grain, potentially occurring during harvesting, storage, or transportation processes (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

(6): Wool trade

According to Feenstra and Clements (2008), *V. encelioides* seeds have been reported to be introduced with wool from Australia in the British Isles. This suggests that unintentional introductions could occur through the trade of wool, with *V. encelioides* seeds associated with the shipments.

(7): Land vehicles

Unintentional transport of *V. encelioides* seeds on military vehicle tires within and between Hawaiian Islands is another pathway for the introduction of this species (Woodward, 1972). This unintentional dispersal occurs through the movement of vehicles.

279

MINISTERUL MEDIULUI,
APELOR ȘI PĂDURILOR

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MANAGEMENTUL
SPECIILOR INVAZIVE
DIN ROMÂNIA

(8): Wind dispersal

V. encelioides naturally spreads by seed, which are dispersed by the wind (Kaul and Mangal, 1987). Wind dispersal serves as a natural pathway for the colonization of new areas by *V. encelioides*.

(9): Biotic vector transmission

There is potential for *V. encelioides* to be dispersed by birds, serving as a biotic vector for the seeds of this plant (CABI, 2023).

It should be noted that intentional introductions are not reported, but there is potential for accidental or purposeful introductions to occur through horticultural or medicinal activities (CABI, 2023).

Pathway name: Horticulture (escape from confinement)

Qu. 1.2a. Is introduction and/or entry along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	intentional	CONFIDENCE	low
	unintentional		medium
			high

Response: Horticulture is the intentional introduction of the species into the risk assessment area for the commercial culturing. The pathway includes the movement of plant material via e-commerce. The species is available via the large retail suppliers (e.g. eBay and Amazon). The Horticulture pathway should be applied to plants escaping from commercial culturing facilities (nurseries, greenhouses; including the deliberate dumping of plant material) or during transport to/from the nursery trade. Therefore, this pathway includes the bulk shipment of live plants for nurseries and gardens centres, and the intentional introduction of seeds for planting.

Qu. 1.3a. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced and/or enter into the environment through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction and/or entry based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in subsequent establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species is an ornamental species and grown in the risk assessment area. There are a number of suppliers listed throughout EU Member states. Although much of the stock that is sold within the risk assessment area is propagated in the risk assessment area, historically the species would have entered the risk assessment area via this pathway.

It is moderately likely that the species will enter the natural environment via this pathway. Potentially, if planted in nurseries and garden centers, plant material may escape from confined areas into the natural environment. There is no data on the number of suppliers of the species in the risk assessment area.

However, *V. encelioides* is found in a wide variety of habitats with differing temperatures, climates, and elevations. In its native range in North and South America, particularly in Mexico and the states of Texas, Arizona, and North Dakota, it is found at elevations of up to 2,750 m (Walther, 2004 as cited by CABI, 2023). Typically, the plant is found in dry and disturbed areas (Walther, 2004 as cited by CABI, 2023). Seeds of *V. encelioides* survive and remain viable under climactic conditions that include drought and high temperatures (Kaul and Mangal, 1987).

Qu. 1.4a. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *V. encelioides* is both self-and cross-pollinated and reproduces by seeds. A single flower head can produce 300 to 350 seeds, and each plant can produce 2 to 6 flowers, resulting in the potential production of 600 to 2100 seeds per plant (Feenstra and Clements, 2008; EPPO 2012). Seeds of *V. encelioides* have been reported to germinate during autumn or early spring and can survive drought and high temperatures (EPPO 2012). They exhibit long periods of seed dormancy and have high germination rates. Once in the soil, the seeds typically take 14-30 days to germinate, increasing their chances of establishing in suitable areas.

V. encelioides is considered drought-tolerant and does not require large amounts of water (EPPO 2012) which suggests it has the ability to survive and establish in various environments along the pathway.

The species has various seed dispersal mechanisms, such as dispersal under or near the parent plant, as well as through light winds. Additionally, seeds can travel long distances by adhering to various materials like wool, fur, clothing, sacks, and other fibrous materials. These mechanisms could

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

facilitate the spread of seeds along the pathway, increasing the chances of establishing new populations.

Overall, considering the species' seed germination, survival capabilities, adaptability, and high seed production, *V. encelioides* is likely to have a reasonable chance of survival, reproduction, and potential population increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism).

Qu. 1.5a. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices before and during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Preventing the spread of *V. encelioides* should be focused on transportation, particularly via vehicle translocation. Cleaning soil from potentially contaminated vehicles or shoes can decrease the likelihood of transport. Implementing such preventive measures can effectively reduce the chances of the species spreading to new areas during transportation. However, the species is likely to survive.

Qu. 1.6a. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment undetected?

Please note that “detection” here is considered as any system or event that may actively contribute to record the presence of a species in a way that appropriate management measures could be potentially undertaken by relevant authorities.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The species could enter the environment undetected as it can escape from garden centers and nurseries via seeds. Thus, it would be difficult to quickly detect the plant, as this could lead to an uncontrolled and difficult to manage spread of the species in the environment.

Qu. 1.7a. How isolated or widespread are possible points of introduction and/or entry into the environment in the risk assessment area?

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	isolated widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: For the introduction of plant material nursery and similar facilities, the entry points are widespread as anyone with an internet connection and a postal address can obtain seeds of the species from outside the risk assessment area. Therefore, introduction points are widespread within the risk assessment area.

Qu. 1.8a. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: This pathway is active, and it is moderately likely that the species is being moved along the pathway from outside the risk assessment area into the risk assessment area.

Seeds may be imported into the risk assessment area for sale in the horticulture industry.

Pathway name: Ornamental purpose other than horticulture (escape from confinement)

Qu. 1.2b. Is introduction and/or entry along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is imported for trade) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of imported goods)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: This pathway involves the intentional introduction of the species for ornamental purposes, though entry into the natural environment would be unintentional. This pathway includes the movement of all potential plant parts into the risk assessment area.

For escape/entry into the environment, this pathway includes the spreading seeds (both intentionally and unintentionally) into the natural environment.

Qu. 1.3b. How likely is it that large numbers of the organism will be introduced and/or enter into the environment through this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

discuss how likely the organism is to get onto the pathway in the first place. Also comment on the volume of movement along this pathway.

an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of individuals / propagules, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication

if relevant, comment on the likelihood of introduction and/or entry based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in subsequent establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information on frequency or volumes entering the risk assessment area or the environment.

The species is listed on popular market sale websites, like:

eBay:

<https://www.ebay.com/sch/i.html?from=R40&trksid=p2334524.m570.11313&nkw=Verbesina+encelioides&sacat=0&odkw=wandering+jew&osacat=0>

Amazon:

https://www.amazon.fr/s?k=Verbesina&mk_fr_FR=%C3%85M%C3%85%C5%BD%C3%95%C3%91&crd=2LAVG0K4B8XG1&sprefix=verbena+%2Caps%2C90&ref=nb_sb_noss_2

Etsy:

https://www.etsy.com/listing/1475490659/cowpen-daisy-verbesina-encelioides?ga_order=most_relevant&ga_search_type=all&ga_view_type=gallery&ga_search_query=Verbesina+encelioides&ref=sr_gallery-1-1&frs=1&organic_search_click=1

Entry into the natural environment is likely as the species will be planted in gardens, sometimes in close proximity to the natural environment. Seeds can spread into the natural environment from planting in gardens.

Qu. 1.4b. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely	CONFIDENCE	low medium
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	moderately likely likely very likely		high
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Response: Seeds is the commodity itself and it is deliberately moved for sale within the risk assessment area. Therefore, seeds are likely to survive along the pathway to the end point where it is planted in a garden.

Qu. 1.5b. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices before and during transport and storage along the pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Management practices before and during transport are very likely to facilitate the survival of the species as it is the commodity itself. Management practices during storage (e.g. temperature) may affect the survival of the species and this could increase or decrease the length of time seed is viable.

Qu. 1.6b. How likely is the organism to be introduced into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment undetected?

Please note that “detection” here is considered as any system or event that may actively contribute to record the presence of a species in a way that appropriate management measures could be potentially undertaken by relevant authorities.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: As the pathway is intended for ornamental use in gardens and parks, it is very unlikely that the organism introduction into the risk assessment area is undetected. There is a small possibility of misidentification, though this would only be relevant for a few species and therefore not a significant issue.

Qu. 1.7b. How isolated or widespread are possible points of introduction and/or entry into the

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

environment in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	isolated widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The plant seeds being available for online sale, it is highly likely that they can be easily acquired by homeowners with yards or gardens. Consequently, the spread of seeds from gardens into the external environment is quite probable, given their potential dispersal through the wind.

Qu. 1.8b. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment based on this pathway?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: We can estimate a moderate likelihood of the species' introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment through this pathway. *V. encelioides* it demonstrates a wide range of germination temperatures and the ability to grow in various soil conditions, which enhances its potential to spread and adapt to new environments. However, it is not expected to build persistent soil seed banks due to rapid loss of viability under accelerated aging (Goyal et al., 2019). Therefore, the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area and/or entry into the environment based on this pathway can be considered moderate.

Qu. 1.9. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment based on all pathways and specify if different in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions.

Provide a thorough assessment of the risk of introduction in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions: providing insight in to the risk of introduction into the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Verbesina encelioides* is very likely to be introduced and enter the risk assessment area with a high confidence. The species is already present in the risk assessment area.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 1.10. Estimate the overall likelihood of introduction into the risk assessment area or entry into the environment based on all pathways in foreseeable climate change conditions?

Thorough assessment of the risk of introduction in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the likelihood of introduction (e.g. change in trade or user preferences)

The thorough assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment of likely introduction within a medium timeframe scenario (e.g. 30-50 years) with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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2 PROBABILITY OF ESTABLISHMENT

Important instructions:

For organisms which are already established in parts of the risk assessment area or have previously been eradicated, the likelihood of establishment should be scored as “very likely” by default.

Discuss the risk also for those parts of the risk assessment area, where the species is not yet established.

Qu. 2.1. How likely is it that the organism will be able to establish in the risk assessment area based on similarity of climatic and abiotic conditions in its distribution elsewhere in the world?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Not evaluated.

Qu. 2.2. How widespread are habitats or species necessary for the survival, development and multiplication of the organism in the risk assessment area? Consider if the organism specifically requires another species to complete its life cycle.

RESPONSE	very isolated isolated moderately widespread widespread ubiquitous	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In Romania, the species covers large areas of disturbed habitats such as wastelands, fallow lands, and roadside areas with carbonate chernozem soils, particularly in the steppe climate conditions characterized by hot and dry summers (Anastasiu et al., 2009).

According to CABI (2023), *V. encelioides* can be found in a variety of habitats, from riparian to coastal to upland to island regions, preferring tropical to subtropical conditions with disturbed porous sandy soils and an open canopy. The species is abundant along roadsides in India and does well on alkaline soils.

In Hawaii, PIER (2013) reported the species as 'relatively common in dry, disturbed sites, 0-2,805 m' in altitude.

According to Feenstra and Clements (2008), *V. encelioides* is a mesophytic plant, meaning it does not require large amounts of water and is drought-tolerant once established, needing only monthly

watering. It shows a preference for sandy soils and maximum seed germination occurs in open and sand dune areas (Kaul and Mangal, 1987).

Considering the species' adaptability to various habitats, its drought tolerance, and its presence in disturbed areas, the overall likelihood of introduction and establishment in new environments can be considered moderate.

Qu. 2.3. How likely is it that establishment will occur despite competition from existing species in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Competition with native vegetation is unlikely to limit the establishment of *V. encelioides* in the risk assessment area. *V. encelioides* displays allelopathic effects inhibiting native plants growth. Its aggressive and dominant growth abilities out compete native plants (Shluker, 1999 as cited by Brunnel et al. 2010).

Qu. 2.4. How likely is it that establishment will occur despite predators, parasites or pathogens already present in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: According to (CABI 2023), *V. encelioides* is known to be a major host of Candidatus Phytoplasma trifolii (clover proliferation phytoplasma), indicating its susceptibility to this plant pathogen. It is also a wild host of *Diabrotica balteata* (banded cucumber beetle) and *Frankliniella fusca* (tobacco thrips), both of which are potential pests that can impact the plant's growth and survival. *V. encelioides* is listed as a host of *Helicoverpa armigera* (cotton bollworm) based on source-data mining.

On the Pacific Islands, about 14 fungal pathogens were recorded in association with *V. encelioides* (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). *V. encelioides* is the food plant for the bordered patch butterfly, *Chlosyne lacinia* (Struttman, 2004). *Verbesina encelioides* subsp. *encelioides* is a host for *Phenacoccus solani*, the solanum mealybug (ScaleNet, 2006). The impact of these arthropods on *V. encelioides* remains unstudied, and other arthropods such as aphids have been observed feeding on the plant (Fufa et al. 2023).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 2.5. How likely is the organism to establish despite existing management practices in the risk assessment area? Explain if existing management practices could facilitate establishment.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The establishment of *V. encelioides* is suited to a number of different habitat types, including disturbed habitats. *V. encelioides* has increased adaptability to disturbed habitats and is likely to spread into such areas. In these areas, management practices should focus on controlling the spread of known populations using manual or chemical whole plant removal methods (CABI, 2023).

Qu. 2.6. How likely is it that biological properties of the organism would allow it to survive eradication campaigns in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In the risk assessment area, seed reproduction is known to be viable (Anastasiu et al., 2009). A single flower head produces 300 to 350 seeds and each plant can produce 2 to 6 flowers leading to the production of 600 to 2100 seeds per plant. Seeds are dispersed under or nearby the parent plant, or by light winds. Additionally, seeds can travel long distances by adhering to wool, fur, clothing, sacks and other fibrous material. *V. encelioides*' range can encompass a variety of habitats, temperatures, and elevations (Brunel et al., 2010).

This species should be removed in the same manner as other annual weeds are managed, through physical/mechanical control or chemical control (CABI, 2023).

Qu. 2.7. How likely are the biological characteristics of the organism to facilitate its establishment in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

a list and description of the reproduction mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area

an indication of the propagule pressure of the species (e.g. number of gametes, seeds, eggs or propagules, number of reproductive cycles per year) of each of those reproduction mechanisms in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

If relevant, comment on the likelihood of establishment based on propagule pressure (i.e. for some

290

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

species low propagule pressure (1-2 individuals) could result in establishment whereas for others high propagule pressure (many thousands of individuals) may not.

If relevant, comment on the adaptability of the organism to facilitate its establishment and if low genetic diversity in the founder population would have an influence on establishment.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Verbesina encelioides* are very likely to facilitate its establishment in the risk assessment area due to its reproductive mechanisms and adaptability to environmental conditions.

Reproduction Mechanisms:

V. encelioides reproduces by seeds, and germination occurs in autumn or early spring. The species exhibits long periods of seed dormancy and has high germination rates. Seeds can survive drought and high temperatures. Each flower head produces 300 to 350 seeds, and each plant can produce 2 to 6 flowers, resulting in the production of 600 to 2100 seeds per plant (Sade et al., 2007).

The seeds are dispersed under or nearby the parent plant, and light winds can also disperse them. Additionally, the seeds can be carried over long distances by adhering to various materials like wool, fur, clothing, and sacks (EPPO, 2012).

Propagule Pressure:

V. encelioides shows ample seed production, and the number of seeds per plant is relatively high. This can lead to a significant propagule pressure, enhancing the likelihood of establishment (EPPO, 2012).

Larger and heavier seeds have the highest germination rates and are maintained by plants growing in open and sand dune habitats (Kaul and Mangal, 1987).

Adaptability:

The species exhibits a wide range of adaptability to different environmental conditions. It prefers fine or medium-textured soil, and studies have shown a preference for sandy soils.

V. encelioides can tolerate alkaline soils, but it is not tolerant to salinity or shade. It requires exposure to light for successful establishment and growth. The plant is considered drought-tolerant and does not require large amounts of water (CABI 2023, EPPO, 2012).

Genetic Diversity and Establishment:

Its prolific seed production and rapid growth suggest that *V. encelioides* can establish even with a low genetic diversity in the founder population.

V. encelioides exhibits several reproductive mechanisms that can contribute to a high propagule pressure, enhancing its chances of establishment in the risk assessment area. Its adaptability to different environmental conditions and its ability to reproduce rapidly are key factors contributing to its invasiveness and potential for successful establishment in new habitats.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 2.8. If the organism does not establish, then how likely is it that casual populations will continue to occur?

Consider, for example, a species which cannot reproduce in the risk assessment area, because of unsuitable climatic conditions or host plants, but is present because of recurring introduction, entry and release events. This may also apply for long-living organisms.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In Europe, *V. encelioides* is an incipient invader (EPPO 2012; Anastasiu et al., 2009). However, due to its invasive nature, this plant can pose a real threat in the southern regions of the country, necessitating the implementation of strong quarantine measures (Anastasiu et al., 2009) and eradication through mechanical and chemical means.

The fact that *V. encelioides* is already identified as an incipient invader in Europe suggests that it has managed to establish some casual populations in the region, even though it might not have fully established itself in all areas. The presence of casual populations could be attributed to recurring introduction, entry, and release events, despite the species not having a stable, self-sustaining population in the risk assessment area.

The species' invasive nature and ability to survive and spread under certain environmental conditions may contribute to the continuation of casual populations, even if it does not fully establish as a dominant species in the risk assessment area.

Qu. 2.9. Estimate the overall likelihood of establishment in the risk assessment area under current climatic conditions. In addition, details of the likelihood of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions under current climatic conditions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the risk of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions: providing insight in the risk of establishment in (new areas in) the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The overall likelihood of *V. encelioides* establishing in the risk assessment area is very likely with medium confidence. The species is already established in the Atlantic, Continental, Mediteranean biogeographical regions.

Qu. 2.10. Estimate the overall likelihood of establishment in the risk assessment area under foreseeable climate change conditions. In addition, details of the likelihood of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions under foreseeable climate change conditions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the risk of establishment in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk.

With regard to climate change, provide information on

the applied timeframe (e.g. 2050/2070)

the applied scenario (e.g. RCP 4.5)

what aspects of climate change are most likely to affect the likelihood of establishment (e.g. increase in average winter temperature, increase in drought periods)

The thorough assessment does not have to include a full range of simulations on the basis of different climate change scenarios, as long as an assessment of likely establishment within a medium timeframe scenario (e.g. 30-50 years) with a clear explanation of the assumptions is provided. However, if new, original models are executed for this risk assessment, the following RCP pathways shall be applied: RCP 2.6 (likely range of 0.4-1.6°C global warming increase by 2065) and RCP 4.5 (likely range of 0.9-2.0°C global warming increase by 2065). Otherwise, the choice of the assessed scenario has to be explained.

RESPONSE		CONFIDENCE	
	very unlikely		low
	unlikely		medium
	moderately likely		high
	likely		
	very likely		

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

3 PROBABILITY OF SPREAD

Important instructions:

Spread is defined as the expansion of the geographical distribution of an alien species within the risk assessment area.

Repeated releases at separate locations do not represent continuous spread and should be considered in the probability of introduction and entry section (Qu. 1.7).

Qu. 3.1. How important is the expected spread of this organism within the risk assessment area by natural means? (List and comment on each of the mechanisms for natural spread.)

including the following elements:

a list and description of the natural spread mechanisms of the species in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

an indication of the rate of spread discussed in relation to the species biology and the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

The description of spread patterns here refers to the CBD pathway category “Unaided (Natural Spread)”. It should include elements of the species life history and behavioural traits able to explain its ability to spread, including: reproduction or growth strategy, dispersal capacity, longevity, dietary requirements, environmental and climatic requirements, specialist or generalist characteristics.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The expected spread of *V. encelioides* within the risk assessment area by natural means is of major importance due to its high potential for reproduction and efficient self- and cross-pollination. The plant exhibits efficient self- and cross-pollination, leading to a high number of seeds being produced. On Midway Atoll, Hawai‘i, it was observed that plants produced 300–350 seeds per flower head (Shluker 2002 as cited by Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

Moreover, the species has adaptive mechanisms to ensure the survival of its seeds until favorable conditions for germination occur. Seeds lie dormant until proper conditions exist, typically after the first heavy rains of the season (Kaul and Mangal, 1987).

V. encelioides tends to flourish in humid, hot regions, and its growth and survival are promoted by high relative humidity levels (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). *V. encelioides* thrives in hot, arid climates where there has been disturbance of the native vegetation. The species' ability to form pure colonies in such environments further enhances its potential for spread. In those disturbed habitats, *V. encelioides* tends to form pure colonies (Goel 1987 as cited by Feenstra and Clements 2008).

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Additionally, it should be noted that the species may potentially be dispersed by birds, and accidental transport can occur via contaminated soils on vehicle tires, bulldozer treads, or shoes (CABI 2023).

Qu. 3.2a. List and describe relevant pathways of spread other than "unaided". For each pathway answer questions 3.3 to 3.9 (copy and paste additional rows at the end of this section as necessary). Please attribute unique identifiers to each question if you consider more than one pathway, e.g. 3.3a, 3.4a, etc. and then 3.3b, 3.4b etc. for the next pathway.

including the following elements:

a list and description of pathways of spread with an indication of their importance and associated risks (e.g. the likelihood of spread in the risk assessment area, based on these pathways; likelihood of survival, or reproduction, or increase during transport and storage; ability and likelihood of transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host) in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

an indication of the rate of spread for each pathway discussed in relation to the species biology and the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area.

All relevant pathways of spread (except "Unaided (Natural Spread)", which is assessed in Qu. 3.1) should be considered. The classification of pathways developed by the Convention of Biological Diversity shall be used (see Annex IV).

Spread pathways are detailed in order of importance

1): Ornamental propose

In the South-Western United States, specifically in New Mexico and Texas where *V. encelioides* is native, a few companies promote the planting of this species for its fast-growing abilities and drought resistance qualities (CABI, 2023). This pathway involves the intentional introduction of *V. encelioides* for ornamental and landscaping purposes.

2) Transport – stowaway: Machinery / equipment

There is a possibility that *V. encelioides* seeds may have contaminated equipment, such as machinery, vehicles, or other equipment used in agricultural or landscaping activities, resulting in unintentional introductions to new areas (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

Unintentional transport of *V. encelioides* seeds on military vehicle tires within and between Hawaiian Islands is another pathway for the introduction of this species (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). This unintentional dispersal occurs through the movement of vehicles.

3) Transport – stowaway: Transportation of habitat material (soil, vegetation)

Soil importation: In the case of the Midway Atoll in Hawaii, it is suspected that *V. encelioides* arrived as seeds contaminating the 9000 tonnes of imported soil, which aimed to improve the quality of life on the island during its military base period (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). This pathway involves the unintentional introduction of *V. encelioides* through the importation of contaminated soil.

Seed dispersal through hay and cereal grain: *V. encelioides* seeds may also be spread as contaminants in pasture hay and cereal grain, potentially occurring during harvesting, storage, or transportation processes (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

(5): Wool trade

According to Feenstra and Clements (2008), *V. encelioides* seeds have been reported to be introduced with wool from Australia in the British Isles. This suggests that unintentional introductions could occur through the trade of wool, with *V. encelioides* seeds associated with the shipments.

(7): Wind dispersal

V. encelioides naturally spreads by seed, which are dispersed by the wind (Kaul and Mangal, 1987). Wind dispersal serves as a natural pathway for the colonization of new areas by *V. encelioides*.

(8): Biotic vector transmission

There is potential for *V. encelioides* to be dispersed by birds, serving as a biotic vector for the seeds of this plant (CABI, 2023).

It should be noted that intentional introductions are not reported, but there is potential for accidental or purposeful introductions to occur through horticultural or medicinal activities (CABI, 2023).

Pathway name: (1) Ornamental purposes

Qu. 3.3a. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	Unintentional intentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Verbesina encelioides* is present in the risk assessment area as an ornamental species. From gardens, the seeds of plant can spread naturally to the natural environment.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.4a. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway
- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no quantitative information on the number of sales of the species in the risk assessment area or the numbers of sites where the species has been planted. Sales of the species within the risk assessment area will be whole plants. The species may also be dumped from waste garden material into the natural environment, though again, there are no details and the volume of movement or frequency.

Qu. 3.5a. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Qu. 3.6a. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *V. encelioides* is likely to survive existing management practises during spread. Management of urban and semi-urban habitats is likely to increase disturbance of the habitat, which can act to break up parts of the plant.

Qu. 3.7a. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Qu. 3.8a. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Qu. 3.9a. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (please provide quantitative data where possible).

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *V. encelioides* is a garden ornamental species which is sold in the risk assessment area. There is no quantitative analysis on the spread of the species in the risk assessment area. Via this pathway the species could be spread throughout the risk assessment area and it is likely that the species would survive as the plant is the commodity.

Pathway name: (2) Transport – stowaway: Machinery / equipment

Qu. 3.3b. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: This pathway details the potential spread of the species with contaminated machinery and equipment. There is no quantitative evidence/interceptions to support the movement of the species along this pathway but the high potential is highlighted in a number of studies (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

Qu. 3.4b. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway
- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no information available on the volumes of movement along this pathway. However, there is a possibility that *V. encelioides* seeds may have contaminated equipment, resulting in unintentional introductions to new areas (Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

Qu. 3.5b. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Seeds material could survive during transport and storage along this spread pathway.

Qu. 3.6b. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Seeds can remain hidden within crevices of machinery and equipment. ISPM 41 (IPPC, 2017) 'Intentional movement of machinery and equipment' provides international measures for cleaning, which can be applied to local level movement also. If done properly, this will decrease the potential for survival.

Qu. 3.7b. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Seeds are very small and potentially can remain hidden in soil in cracks and crevices in machinery and equipment. Such machinery can be moved within the risk assessment area transporting seeds to new areas.

Qu. 3.8b. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It would be likely that *V. encelioides* can transfer to a suitable habitat if the seed species is a stowaway on machinery/equipment.

Qu. 3.9b. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Used machinery and equipment can be moved within the risk assessment area at a local and long distances scale. Any seed attached could be spread at a fast rate. It is scored rapidly and thus a number of measures can be adopted against this spread pathway, including inspections of used machinery and equipment coupled with cleaning.

Pathway name: (3) Transport – stowaway: Transportation of habitat material (soil, vegetation)

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.3c. Is spread along this pathway intentional (e.g. the organism is deliberately transported from one place to another) or unintentional (e.g. the organism is a contaminant of translocated goods within the risk assessment area)?

RESPONSE	intentional unintentional	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The spread of *V. encelioides* via transport of habitat material (soil, vegetation) within the risk assessment area is unintentional. Seeds can be spread via this pathway.

Qu. 3.4c. How likely is it that a number of individuals sufficient to originate a viable population will spread along this pathway from the point(s) of origin over the course of one year?

including the following elements:

- an indication of the propagule pressure (e.g. estimated volume or number of specimens, or frequency of passage through pathway), including the likelihood of reinvasion after eradication
- if appropriate, indicate the rate of spread along this pathway
- if appropriate, include an explanation of the relevance of the number of individuals for spread with regard to the biology of species (e.g. some species may not necessarily rely on large numbers of individuals).

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response:

Soil importation pathway:

The introduction of *V. encelioides* seeds through contaminated soil importation to the Midway Atoll in Hawaii indicates a potential for the species to establish a viable population in the new habitat. While the specific volume or number of seeds that contaminated the 9000 tonnes of imported soil is not mentioned (Feenstra and Clements, 2008), the substantial amount of soil involved suggests a significant propagule pressure. Additionally, the unintentional nature of the introduction increases the likelihood of reinvasion even after eradication efforts.

The dispersal of *V. encelioides* seeds as contaminants in pasture hay and cereal grain presents another potential pathway for spread (Feenstra and Clements, 2008). Again, the specific volume or frequency of seed contaminants in these commodities is not mentioned, but if the seeds are consistently present, the propagule pressure can be significant.

The rate of spread along this pathway may be influenced by agricultural practices, such as harvesting, storage, and transportation processes. If these activities facilitate the dispersal of seeds to suitable habitats, the spread can occur over time.

Qu. 3.5c. How likely is the organism to survive, reproduce, or increase during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism)?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The likelihood of *V. encelioides* surviving, reproducing, or increasing during transport and storage along the pathway (excluding management practices that would kill the organism) may vary depending on the specific conditions and practices involved.

During transport and storage of contaminated soil, *V. encelioides* seeds may have a chance to survive, especially if the seeds are protected within the soil particles or crevices of machinery and equipment. The species has a high potential for reproduction, and its seeds can remain dormant until suitable germination conditions arise. Therefore, if the imported soil provides a suitable environment for seed germination and growth, the organism may have a chance to reproduce and increase in numbers during the transport and storage phase.

Qu. 3.6c. How likely is the organism to survive existing management practices during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Careful methodical management practices coupled with inspection would be needed to ensure that the species did not spread with contaminated soil and vegetation.

The likelihood of *V. encelioides* surviving existing management practices during spread depends on the level of awareness, preparedness, and effectiveness of the implemented measures to control the

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

spread of the species. It is essential to have robust and well-implemented management strategies, including early detection and rapid response measures, to prevent and control the spread of invasive species like *V. encelioides* in order to minimize its impact on ecosystems and native biodiversity.

Qu. 3.7c. How likely is the organism to spread in the risk assessment area undetected?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Soil and other habitat material can be moved throughout the risk assessment area and. Shoot material may be small and buried in soil and other material, making them difficult to detect.

Qu. 3.8c. How likely is the organism to be able to transfer from the pathway to a suitable habitat or host during spread?

RESPONSE	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: It would be very likely that *V. encelioides* can transfer to a suitable habitat if seeds of the species is incorporated in soil.

Qu. 3.9c. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread based on this pathway in relation to the environmental conditions in the risk assessment area. (provide quantitative data where possible).

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There is no quantitative data on the spread of the species in relation to habitat material.

Habitat material (excluding soil) can move freely within the single market in the EU enabling contaminated material to spread over long distances. Because of the lack of data, confidence is low.

Qu. 3.10. Within the risk assessment area, how difficult would it be to contain the organism in relation to these pathways of spread?

RESPONSE	very easy easy with some difficulty difficult very difficult	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The difficulty in containing *V. encelioides* in the risk assessment area lies in the unintentional nature of its introduction and the potential for the organism to spread through different pathways (soil importation and seed dispersal) with the movement of materials such as soil, hay, and cereal grain. The lack of data on the spread of the species in relation to habitat material further complicates containment efforts. To effectively manage and contain the species, implementing robust preventive measures, early detection, and rapid response strategies are essential.

Qu. 3.11. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread in relevant biogeographical regions under current conditions for this organism in the risk assessment area (indicate any key issues and provide quantitative data where possible).

Thorough assessment of the risk of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in current conditions, providing insight in the risk of spread into (new areas in) the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: In the risk assessment area, *V. encelioides* reproduces and spreads by seeds. Therefore, spread by natural means can be assessed as very rapidly.

Spread would be highest in biogeographical regions where the species is already present, such as Alpine, Atlantic and Mediterranean biogeographical regions. A higher rate of spread may be seen in biogeographical regions where *V. encelioides* can be considered as established, e.g. Atlantic, Continental and Mediterranean biogeographical regions.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Qu. 3.12. Estimate the overall potential rate of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions (provide quantitative data where possible).

Thorough assessment of the risk of spread in relevant biogeographical regions in foreseeable climate change conditions: explaining how foreseeable climate change conditions will influence this risk, specifically if rates of spread are likely slowed down or accelerated.

RESPONSE	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Spread would maintain in the areas where the species is already established: Mediterranean, Continental and Atlantic biogeographical regions.

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

4 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT

Important instructions:

Questions 4.1-4.5 relate to biodiversity and ecosystem impacts, 4.6-4.8 to impacts on ecosystem services, 4.9-4.13 to economic impact, 4.14-4.15 to social and human health impact, and 4.16-4.18 to other impacts. These impacts can be interlinked, for example, a disease may cause impacts on biodiversity and/or ecosystem functioning that leads to impacts on ecosystem services and finally economic impacts. In such cases the assessor should try to note the different impacts where most appropriate, cross-referencing between questions when needed.

Each set of questions starts with the impact elsewhere in the world, then considers impacts in the risk assessment area (=EU excluding outermost regions) separating known impacts to date (i.e. past and current impacts) from potential future impacts (including foreseeable climate change).

Only negative impacts are considered in this section (socio-economic benefits are considered in Qu. A.7)

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable). Note that in principle, even if no information is available for the risk assessment area, this does not apply to Qu. 4.2 and 4.3, because the information on impact can be inferred from regions outside the risk assessment area. If no information is available from regions outside the risk assessment area either, then this should be discussed explicitly.

Biodiversity and ecosystem impacts

Qu. 4.1. How important is the impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation caused by the organism in its non-native range excluding the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

Biodiversity means the variability among living organisms from all sources, including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems

impacted chemical, physical or structural characteristics and functioning of ecosystems

RESPONSE	minimal	CONFIDENCE	low
	minor		medium
	moderate		high
	major		
	massive		

UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: The impact of *V. encelioides* on biodiversity at all levels of organization in its non-native range, excluding the risk assessment area, is considered significant. The organism has shown various negative effects on the ecosystem and native species in the areas where it has become established.

One of the notable impacts is on marine birds in the northwest Hawaiian islands, such as Laysan albatross, blackfoot albatross, Christmas shearwater, and wedge-tailed shearwaters. *V. encelioides*'s intertwining branches have trapped hatchlings and young birds, affecting their nesting activities.

In addition to its effects on marine birds, *V. encelioides* has become one of the most common weeds in Northern India, where it invades maize, barley, rice, peanut, and millet fields, competing with and displacing native plants (Brunel et al., 2018). Its aggressive and dominant growth abilities outcompete native species, leading to habitat degradation and loss of biodiversity in arable land, pastures, and disturbed habitats.

Furthermore, the plant contains a toxic component called galegine, which poses a risk to livestock, especially sheep. Although it is not a preferred source of feed, livestock may ingest *V. encelioides* when feed is limited. Studies in Argentina have shown that animals ingesting certain quantities of the plant per kilogram of body weight might experience lethargy, anorexia, or even death due to severe internal organ damage and internal hemorrhaging.

In Morocco, *V. encelioides* is reported to be a host for whiteflies such as *Bemisia tabaci* and *Trialeurodes vaporariorum*, which are listed as invasive pests (Taleb and Bouhache, 2006). These insects can further impact agriculture and native vegetation, contributing to ecosystem disruption.

Overall, the uncertainty of the assessment is considered medium. The documented impacts of *V. encelioides* on marine birds, native plants, livestock, and associated insect pests highlight the significant negative effects the organism can have on biodiversity in its non-native range.

A major score is given due to the scale and importance of the impacts detailed above and a medium confidence score is given because of the depth of literature in the invaded range.

Qu. 4.2. How important is the current known impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation (e.g. decline in native species, changes in native species communities, hybridisation) in the risk assessment area (include any past impact in your response)?

Discuss impacts that are currently occurring or are likely occurring or have occurred in the past in the risk assessment area. Where there is no direct evidence of impact in the risk assessment area (for example no studies have been conducted), evidence from outside of the risk assessment area can be used to infer impacts within the risk assessment area.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

Response: Considering the documented impacts of *Verbesina encelioides* on marine birds, native plants, livestock, and associated insect pests, it is evident that the organism has caused significant changes and disruptions to biodiversity at all levels of organization within the risk assessment area. Implementing effective management strategies and preventive measures is crucial to mitigate the impact of *V. encelioides* on biodiversity within the risk assessment area.

Qu. 4.3. How important is the potential future impact of the organism on biodiversity at all levels of organisation likely to be in the risk assessment area?

See comment above. The potential future impact shall be assessed only for the risk assessment area. A potential increase in the distribution range due to climate change does not *per se* justify a higher impact score.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: The potential future impact of *V. encelioides* on biodiversity at all levels of organization in the risk assessment area is likely to be significant. Several factors contribute to this assessment:

V. encelioides has demonstrated aggressive and dominant growth abilities, allowing it to outcompete native plants and disrupt native species communities. This invasive behavior indicates the potential for the species to further expand its range within the risk assessment area, leading to a decline in native species and changes in the composition and structure of local ecosystems.

Qu. 4.4. How important is decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the organism currently in the risk assessment area?

including the following elements:

native species impacted, including red list species, endemic species and species listed in the Birds and Habitats directives

protected sites impacted, in particular Natura 2000

habitats impacted, in particular habitats listed in the Habitats Directive, or red list habitats

the ecological status of water bodies according to the Water Framework Directive and environmental status of the marine environment according to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive

RESPONSE	minimal minor	CONFIDENCE	low medium
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	moderate major massive		high
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Response: The decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the *V. encelioides* currently in the risk assessment area is likely to be major.

V. encelioides has been shown to negatively impact native species in its non-native range. It traps and disrupts the nesting activities of marine birds, including Laysan albatross, blackfoot albatross, Christmas shearwater, and wedge-tailed shearwaters in the northwest Hawaiian islands. The impact on these bird species, some of which may be red-listed or protected under Birds and Habitats directives, can have serious implications for their populations and conservation status.

The spread of *V. encelioides* within the risk assessment area may pose a threat to these protected sites, affecting the ecological integrity of these areas and potentially leading to the decline of native species and habitats within them.

V. encelioides has invasive behavior and aggressive growth abilities, which can outcompete native plants and disrupt native habitats. This could lead to the degradation and decline of habitats listed in the Habitats Directive or identified as red-listed habitats. The loss or alteration of these habitats can further impact the conservation value and ecological balance of the risk assessment area.

Qu. 4.5. How important is decline in conservation value with regard to European and national nature conservation legislation caused by the organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.3. and 4.4.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Decline in conservation values would be exhibited in the areas where the species is already established. In the absence of specific and detailed studies, the score is assessed as moderate with a low confidence.

Ecosystem Services impacts

Qu. 4.6. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services in its non-native range excluding the risk assessment area?

For a list of services use the CICES classification V5.1 provided in Annex V.

Impacts on ecosystem services build on the observed impacts on biodiversity (habitat, species,

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

genetic, functional) but focus exclusively on reflecting these changes in relation to their links with socio-economic well-being.

Quantitative data should be provided whenever available and references duly reported.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: According to Cabi (2023) *V. encelioides* provides pollen, nectar and seeds to insects and birds. It is unknown how this species affects nutrient cycling, carbon pools, soil biota and community ecology.

Qu. 4.7. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services currently in the different biogeographic regions or marine sub-regions where the species has established in the risk assessment area (include any past impact in your response)?

See guidance to Qu. 4.6.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: There are no publications relating to this impact but it can be inferred from the impacts outside the risk assessment area and the fact that there are heavily invaded areas within the risk assessment area. The scale and detail is not known so a minimal score is the only one available and given with low confidence.

Qu. 4.8. How important is the impact of the organism on provisioning, regulating, and cultural services likely to be in the different biogeographic regions or marine sub-regions where the species can establish in the risk assessment area in the future?

See guidance to Qu. 4.6.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: As above impacts can be inferred for the risk assessment area so similar scores are given.

Economic impacts

Qu. 4.9. How great is the overall economic cost caused by the organism within its current area of distribution (excluding the risk assessment area), including both costs of / loss due to damage and the cost of current management.

Where economic costs of / loss due to the organism have been quantified for a species anywhere in the world these should be reported here. The assessment of the potential costs of / loss due to damage shall describe those costs quantitatively and/or qualitatively depending on what information is available. Cost of / loss due to damage within different economic sectors can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage. As far as possible, it would be useful to separate costs of / loss due to the organism from costs of current management.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: NA

Qu. 4.10. How great is the economic cost of / loss due to damage (excluding costs of management) of the organism currently in the risk assessment area (include any past costs in your response)?

Where economic costs of / loss due to the organism have been quantified for a species anywhere in the EU these should be reported here. Assessment of the potential costs of damage on human health, safety, and the economy, including the cost of non-action. A full economic assessment at EU scale might not be possible, but qualitative data or different case studies from across the EU (or third countries if relevant) may provide useful information to inform decision making. In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable). Cost of / loss due to damage within different economic sectors can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

RESPONSE	N/A minimal	CONFIDENCE	low medium
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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

	minor moderate major massive		high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.11. How great is the economic cost of / loss due to damage (excluding costs of management) of the organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.10.

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.12. How great are the economic costs / losses associated with managing this organism currently in the risk assessment area (include any past costs in your response)?

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.13. How great are the economic costs / losses associated with managing this organism likely to be in the future in the risk assessment area?

See guidance to Qu. 4.12.

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Social and human health impacts

Qu. 4.14. How important is social, human health or other impact (not directly included in any earlier categories) caused by the organism for the risk assessment area and for third countries, if relevant (e.g. with similar eco-climatic conditions).

The description of the known impact and the assessment of potential future impact on human health, safety and the economy, shall, if relevant, include information on

illnesses, allergies or other affections to humans that may derive directly or indirectly from a species;

damages provoked directly or indirectly by a species with consequences for the safety of people, property or infrastructure;

direct or indirect disruption of, or other consequences for, an economic or social activity due to the presence of a species.

Social and human health impacts can be a direct or indirect consequence of the earlier-noted impacts on ecosystem services. In such case, please provide an indication of the interlinkage.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *V. encelioides* contains high levels of nitrates, with galegine identified as the toxic component. This poses a high poisoning threat to grazing sheep and cattle. Ingestion of the plant by livestock can lead to galegine poisoning, characterized by symptoms such as dullness and anorexia. Galegine, being an isoprenoid guanidine compound, causes vascular leakage and significant edema, leading to respiratory distress and eventual death in animals (Jain et al., 2008).

The toxic effects of *V. encelioides* on grazing animals can pose a safety risk for both livestock and humans who handle or consume animal products. In cases of severe poisoning, livestock deaths can have serious implications for farmers' livelihoods and may result in economic losses.

Qu. 4.15. How important is social, human health or other impact (not directly included in any

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

earlier categories) caused by the organism in the future for the risk assessment area.

In absence of specific studies or other direct evidences this should be clearly stated by using the standard answer “No information has been found on the issue”. This is necessary to avoid confusion between “no information found” and “no impact found”. In this case, no score and confidence should be given and the standardized “score” is N/A (not applicable).

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: Only limited impacts are recorded in other more heavily invaded countries. There is no reason to assume that the social and human health impacts would increase significantly in the timescale under consideration.

Other impacts

Qu. 4.16. How important is the organism in facilitating other damaging organisms (e.g. diseases) as food source, a host, a symbiont or a vector etc.?

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *V. encelioides* serves as a highly favored host for thrips species that act as vectors of the tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV) (Grichar and Sestak, 1998). The plant's tendency to grow in clusters, along with the visibility of its flowers, makes it very attractive to thrips (Mitchell and Smith, 1996). Consequently, any management action taken to control wild sunflower populations can be beneficial in preventing the spread of the virus (Yudin et al., 1988).

Furthermore, on the Pacific Islands, *V. encelioides* has been associated with about 14 fungal pathogens (Feenstra and Clements, 2008), suggesting that the plant may act as a symbiotic host or provide suitable conditions for the growth and proliferation of these pathogens.

V. encelioides also serves as a food plant for the bordered patch butterfly, *Chlosyne lacinia* (Struttman, 2004), and is a host for *Phenacoccus solani*, the solanum mealybug (ScaleNet, 2006 as cited by Feenstra and Clements, 2008).

Qu. 4.17. How important might other impacts not already covered by previous questions be resulting from introduction of the organism?

RESPONSE	N/A minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: No information has been found on the issue.

Qu. 4.18. How important are the expected impacts of the organism despite any natural control by other organisms, such as predators, parasites or pathogens that may already be present in the risk assessment area?

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *V. encelioides* has no known mammalian predators and is toxic to many mammals (Feenstra and Clements, 2008), potentially acting as a deterrent against mammalian herbivory.

Despite the potential presence of natural controls by other organisms in some areas, the expected impacts of *V. encelioides*, particularly concerning its role in host for multiple pathogens, are still noteworthy. Proper management actions to control the plant's population and prevent the spread of associated diseases are crucial to mitigate the risks posed by *V. encelioides* in the risk assessment area.

Qu. 4.19. Estimate the overall impact in the risk assessment area under current climate conditions. In addition, details of overall impact in relevant biogeographical regions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the overall impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, with impacts on economy as well as social and human health as aggravating factors, in current conditions.

RESPONSE	minimal minor moderate major massive	CONFIDENCE	low medium high
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Response: *Verbesina encelioides* is already established in the Atlantic, Continental and Mediterranean biogeographic region and in two Member States (Spain, Romania). There are also impacts on various levels of ecosystem services in invaded regions outside of the risk assessment area and the lack of literature does not mean that the situation is not similar in heavy invasions now or in the future. The

overall impact in the risk assessment is assessed as moderate with low confidence due to the paucity of impact data in the risk assessment area

Qu. 4.20. Estimate the overall impact in the risk assessment area in foreseeable climate change conditions. In addition, details of overall impact in relevant biogeographical regions should be provided.

Thorough assessment of the overall impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, with impacts on economy as well as social and human health as aggravating factors, under future conditions.

See also guidance to Qu. 4.3.

RESPONSE	CONFIDENCE
minimal	low
minor	medium
moderate	high
major	
massive	

Response: A study conducted by Moshobane and Esser (2022) employed species distribution modeling techniques to determine the potential distribution of the invasive weed *V. encelioides* in South Africa from 2020 to 2090. The ensemble model results, based on current climatic conditions, indicate a high probability of occurrence of *V. encelioides* in all nine provinces of South Africa, across all projected future scenarios (2030, 2050, 2070, and 2090). These predictions suggest that *Verbesina encelioides* is likely to benefit from the projected climate change in South Africa.

Furthermore, a separate study conducted by Mehal et al. (2022) in Punjab, northwestern India, reveals that *V. encelioides* has ecological impacts on vegetation composition across dryland ecosystems. Based on the aridity index for the period of 1991–2016, three major dryland ecosystems, namely arid, semi-arid, and sub-humid, were identified in Punjab. *V. encelioides* led to decreased species diversity and proportion, with a more pronounced impact observed in arid and semi-arid ecosystems. In contrast, species composition showed variations only in arid ecosystems between invaded and uninvaded areas. As the ecological impacts of *V. encelioides* were more evident in conditions of increased aridification, there is concern about the potential impacts of climate change scenarios.

Both the South African and Indian studies indicate that *V. encelioides* can have a significant impact on the risk assessment areas under foreseeable climate change conditions.

RISK SUMMARIES			
	RESPONSE	CONFIDENCE	COMMENT
Summarise Introduction and Entry*	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	low medium high	<i>Verbesina encelioides</i> has been introduced and entered the environment of the risk assessment area. Further introduction and entry is likely as the pathways horticulture and

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

			ornamental purposes other than horticulture remain active.
Summarise Establishment*	very unlikely unlikely moderately likely likely very likely	low medium high	The species is already established in the Mediterranean, Continental and Atlantic biogeographical regions and two EU Member States (Romania, Spain).
Summarise Spread*	very slowly slowly moderately rapidly very rapidly	low medium high	<i>Verbesina encelioides</i> reproduces and spreads by sexual reproduction. Human mediated spread includes intentional movement through ornamental purposes, unintentional movement through contaminated machinery and equipment and habitat material (soil and vegetation).
Summarise Impact*	minimal minor moderate major massive	low medium high	The species has shown impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services through suppression of native species development, reducing species richness and native seedling survival altering the succession trajectory of native plant species and their associated fauna in its invaded range outside of the risk assessment area. This level of impact has not yet been realised in the risk assessment area, but some studies report impacts on biodiversity in the Mediterranean biogeographical region in habitats of nature conservation. Occurrences in Natura 2000 sites in the risk assessment is not documented. The low confidence score incorporates uncertainty from the lack of scientific publications on impacts in the risk assessment area. It is assumed that impacts will increase in the foreseeable future.
Conclusion of the risk assessment (overall risk)	low moderate high	low medium high	Overall, <i>V. encelioides</i> poses a moderate risk to the EU with a medium confidence. This impact score takes into account the

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2014-2020

			<p>moderate impact score, but also the high likelihood of introduction/entry and establishment, coupled with a high spread. The medium confidence score incorporates uncertainty from the lack of scientific publications in the risk assessment area.</p>
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*in current climate conditions and in foreseeable future climate conditions

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UNIUNEA EUROPEANĂ

Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

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2014-2020

ANNEX I Scoring of Likelihoods of Events

(taken from UK Non-native Organism Risk Assessment Scheme User Manual, Version 3.3, 28.02.2005)

Score	Description	Frequency
Very unlikely	This sort of event is theoretically possible, but is never known to have occurred and is not expected to occur	1 in 10,000 years
Unlikely	This sort of event has occurred somewhere at least once in the last millenium	1 in 1,000 years
Moderately likely	This sort of event has occurred somewhere at least once in the last century	1 in 100 years
Likely	This sort of event has happened on several occasions elsewhere, or on at least once in the last decade	1 in 10 years
Very likely	This sort of event happens continually and would be expected to occur	Once a year

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2014-2020

ANNEX II Scoring of Magnitude of Impacts

(modified from UK Non-native Organism Risk Assessment Scheme User Manual, Version 3.3, 28.02.2005)

Score	Biodiversity and ecosystem impact	Ecosystem Services impact	Economic impact (Monetary loss and response costs per year)	Social and human health impact, and other impacts
	<i>Question 4.1-5</i>	<i>Question 4.6-8</i>	<i>Question 4.9-13</i>	<i>Question 4.14-18</i>
Minimal	Local, short-term population decline, no significant ecosystem impact	No services affected ¹⁹	Up to 10,000 Euro	No social disruption. Local, mild, short-term reversible effects to individuals.
Minor	Local, short-term population loss, Localized reversible ecosystem impact	Local and temporary, reversible effects to one or few services	10,000-100,000 Euro	Significant concern expressed at local level. Mild short-term reversible effects to identifiable groups, localised.
Moderate	Local to regional long-term population decline/loss, Measureable reversible long-term damage to ecosystem, little spread, no extinction	Measureable, temporary, local and reversible effects on one or several services	100,000-1,000,000 Euro	Temporary changes to normal activities at local level. Minor irreversible effects and/or larger numbers covered by reversible effects, localised.
Major	Long-term irreversible ecosystem change, spreading beyond local area, population loss or extinction of single species	Local and irreversible or widespread and reversible effects on one / several services	1,000,000-10,000,000 Euro	Some permanent change of activity locally, concern expressed over wider area. Significant irreversible effects locally or reversible effects over large area.
Massive	Long-term irreversible ecosystem change, widespread, population loss or extinction of several species	Widespread and irreversible effects on one / several services	Above 10,000,000 Euro	Long-term social change, significant loss of employment, migration from affected area. Widespread, severe, long-term, irreversible health effects.

¹⁹ Not to be confused with “no impact”.

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2014-2020

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DIN ROMÂNIA

ANNEX III Scoring of Confidence Levels

(modified from Bacher et al. 2017)

Each answer provided in the risk assessment must include an assessment of the level of confidence attached to that answer, reflecting the possibility that information needed for the answer is not available or is insufficient or available but conflicting.

The responses in the risk assessment should clearly support the choice of the confidence level.

Confidence level	Description
Low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g. only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence <i>and/or</i> Impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the assessment area <i>and/or</i> Evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g. because it is strongly ambiguous <i>and/or</i> The information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.
Medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred <i>and/or</i> Impacts are recorded at a small spatial scale, but rescaling of the data to relevant scales of the assessment area is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty <i>and/or</i> The interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.
High	There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment (including causality) <i>and</i> Impacts are recorded at a comparable scale <i>and/or</i> There are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa <i>and</i> The interpretation of data/information is straightforward <i>and/or</i> Data/information are not controversial or contradictory.

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

ANNEX IV CBD pathway categorisation scheme

Overview of CBD pathway categorisation scheme showing how the 44 pathways relate to the six main pathway categories. All of the pathways can be broadly classified into 1) those that involve intentional transport (blue), 2) those in which the taxa are unintentionally transported (green) and 3) those where taxa moved between regions without direct transportation by humans and/or via artificial corridors (orange and yellow). Note that the pathways in the category “Escape from confinement” can be considered intentional for the introduction into the risk assessment area and unintentional for the entry into the environment.

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2014-2020

ANNEX V Ecosystem services classification (CICES V5.1, simplified) and examples

For the purposes of this risk assessment, please feel free to use what seems as the most appropriate category / level / combination of impact (Section – Division – Group), reflecting information available.

Section	Division	Group	Examples (i.e. relevant CICES “classes”)
Provisioning	Biomass	Cultivated <i>terrestrial</i> plants	Cultivated terrestrial plants (including fungi, algae) grown for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from cultivated plants, fungi, algae and bacteria for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Cultivated plants (including fungi, algae) grown as a <u>source of energy</u> <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to crops, orchards, timber etc.</i>
		Cultivated <i>aquatic</i> plants	Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Plants cultivated by in- situ aquaculture grown as an <u>energy source</u> . <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to aquatic plants cultivated for nutrition, gardening etc. purposes.</i>
		Reared animals	Animals reared for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from reared animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Animals reared to provide <u>energy</u> (including mechanical) <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to livestock</i>
		Reared <i>aquatic</i> animals	Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from animals grown by in-situ aquaculture for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Animals reared by in-situ aquaculture as an <u>energy source</u> <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms to fish farming</i>
		Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic)	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used for <u>nutrition</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from wild plants for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials); Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic, including fungi, algae) used as a <u>source of energy</u> <i>Example: reduction in the availability of wild plants (e.g. wild berries, ornamentals) due to non-native organisms (competition, spread of disease etc.)</i>
		Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic)	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used for <u>nutritional purposes</u> ; <u>Fibres and other materials</u> from wild animals for direct use or processing (excluding genetic materials);

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Instrumente Structurale
2014-2020

			Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) used as a <u>source of energy</u> <i>Example: reduction in the availability of wild animals (e.g. fish stocks, game) due to non-native organisms (competition, predations, spread of disease etc.)</i>
	Genetic material from all biota	Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi	<u>Seeds, spores and other plant materials</u> collected for maintaining or establishing a population; Higher and lower plants (whole organisms) used to <u>breed new strains or varieties</u> ; Individual genes extracted from higher and lower plants for the <u>design and construction of new biological entities</u> <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms due to interbreeding</i>
		Genetic material from animals	Animal material collected for the purposes of maintaining or establishing a population; Wild animals (whole organisms) used to breed new strains or varieties; Individual genes extracted from organisms for the design and construction of new biological entities <i>Example: negative impacts of non-native organisms due to interbreeding</i>
	Water ²⁰	Surface water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Surface water for <u>drinking</u> ; Surface water used as a material (<u>non-drinking purposes</u>); Freshwater surface water, coastal and marine water used as an <u>energy source</u> <i>Example: loss of access to surface water due to spread of non-native organisms</i>
		Ground water for used for nutrition, materials or energy	Ground (and subsurface) water for <u>drinking</u> ; Ground water (and subsurface) used as a material (<u>non-drinking purposes</u>); Ground water (and subsurface) used as an <u>energy source</u> <i>Example: reduced availability of ground water due to spread of non-native organisms and associated increase of ground water consumption by vegetation.</i>
Regulation & Maintenance	Transformation of biochemical or physical inputs to ecosystems	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	<u>Bio-remediation</u> by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals; <u>Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation</u> by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem functioning and ability to filtrate etc. waste or toxics</i>
		Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	<u>Smell reduction; noise attenuation; visual screening</u> (e.g. by means of green infrastructure) <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem structure, leading to reduced ability to mediate nuisances.</i>
	Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Baseline flows and extreme event regulation	Control of <u>erosion rates</u> ; Buffering and attenuation of <u>mass movement</u> ; <u>Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation</u> (including flood control, and coastal protection); <u>Wind protection</u> ; <u>Fire protection</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystem functioning or structure leading to, for example, destabilisation of soil, increased risk or intensity of wild fires</i>

²⁰ Note: in the CICES classification provisioning of water is considered as an abiotic service whereas the rest of ecosystem services listed here are considered biotic.

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			etc.
		Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	<u>Pollination</u> (or 'gamete' dispersal in a marine context); <u>Seed dispersal</u> ; Maintaining <u>nursery populations and habitats</u> (Including gene pool protection) <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the abundance and/or distribution of wild pollinators; changes to the availability / quality of nursery habitats for fisheries</i>
		Pest and disease control	Pest control; Disease control <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the abundance and/or distribution of pests</i>
		Soil quality regulation	<u>Weathering processes</u> and their effect on soil quality; <u>Decomposition and fixing processes</u> and their effect on soil quality <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to vegetation structure and/or soil fauna leading to reduced soil quality</i>
		Water conditions	Regulation of the <u>chemical condition</u> of freshwaters by living processes; Regulation of the chemical condition of salt waters by living processes <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to buffer strips along water courses that remove nutrients in runoff and/or fish communities that regulate the resilience and resistance of water bodies to eutrophication</i>
		Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation of <u>chemical composition</u> of atmosphere and oceans; Regulation of <u>temperature and humidity</u> , including ventilation and transpiration <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystems' ability to sequester carbon and/or evaporative cooling (e.g. by urban trees)</i>
Cultural	Direct, in-situ and outdoor interactions with living systems that depend on presence in the environmental setting	Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through <u>active or immersive interactions</u> ; Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through <u>passive or observational interactions</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.) that make it attractive for recreation, wild life watching etc.</i>
		Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment	Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>scientific investigation</u> or the creation of traditional ecological knowledge; Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>education and training</u> ; Characteristics of living systems that are resonant in terms of <u>culture or heritage</u> ; Characteristics of living systems that enable <u>aesthetic experiences</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.)</i>

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			<i>that have cultural importance</i>
	Indirect, remote, often indoor interactions with living systems that do not require presence in the environmental setting	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Elements of living systems that have <u>symbolic meaning</u> ; Elements of living systems that have <u>sacred or religious meaning</u> ; Elements of living systems used for <u>entertainment or representation</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to the qualities of ecosystems (structure, species composition etc.) that have sacred or religious meaning</i>
		Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Characteristics or features of living systems that have an <u>existence value</u> ; Characteristics or features of living systems that have an <u>option or bequest value</u> <i>Example: changes caused by non-native organisms to ecosystems designated as wilderness areas, habitats of endangered species etc.</i>

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ANNEX VI EU Biogeographic Regions and MSFD Subregions

See <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/biogeographical-regions-in-europe-2> ,
http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/natura2000/biogeog_regions/

and

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/msfd-regions-and-subregions-1/technical-document/pdf>

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ANNEX VII Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/968 of 30 April 2018

see <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32018R0968>

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